

MEDINA

Deliverable D3.2

Tools and techniques for the management of trustworthy evidence-v2

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Abstract:	This deliverable will encompass techniques on how to integrate different tools to gather and manage trustworthy evidence on various levels as well as on how to ensure the trustworthiness of evidence across the life-cycle, i.e., using Blockchain/DLT. There will be three iterations of the deliverable, an initial prototype, reflecting an early stage of integration in the technical framework (D3.1), the second release (D3.2) will be based on a refinement of the technical architecture, finally the third iteration (D3.3) will reflect the implementation of the use cases. This deliverable is the result of Task 3.1 and Task 3.5.
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Terms and abbreviations

AM	Asset Management
AMOE	Assessment and Management of Organisational Evidence
API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BC	Business Continuity
CAB	Conformance Assessment Body
CCM	Change and Configuration Management
CI/CD	Continuous integration / continuous deployment
CIS	Centre for Internet Security
CKM	Cryptography and Key Management
CO	Compliance
CPG	Code Property Graph
CS	Communication Security
CSA or EU CSA	EU Cybersecurity Act
CSP	Cloud Service Provider
CSPM	Cloud Security Posture Management tool
DAST	Dynamic application security testing
DEV	Development of Information Systems
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EUCS	European Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Cloud Services
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEC	Generic Evidence Collector
HIDS	Host-based Intrusion Detection Systems
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act
HR	Human Resources
IaC	Infrastructure as Code
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
IAM	Identity, Authentication and Access Control Management
IDS	Intrusion Detection Systems
ING	Dealing with Investigation requests from government agencies
ISP	Information Security Policies
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KR	Key Result
HIDS	Host-based Intrusion Detection System
IM	Incident Management
NIDS	network-based IDS
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
NLP	Natural language processing
OIS	Organizational Information Security
OPS	Operational Security
OSSEC	Open Source HIDS SECURITY
OWASP	Open Web Application Security Project
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PCI DSS	Payment Card Industry Data Security Standard
PI	Portability and Interoperability
PM	Procurement Management

PS	Physical Security
PSS	Product Security
RBAC	Role Based Access Control
REST	Representational State Transfer
RM	Risk Management
SaaS	Software as a Service
SIEM	Security Information and Event Management
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SQL	Structured Query Language
UI	User Interface
DOC	User Documentation
VAT	Vulnerability Assessment Tools
VM	Virtual Machine

Draft

Executive Summary

This document aims at presenting work related to the architecture of the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools* [KR4] and the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* that aims at ensuring that all evidence and assessment results are secured. The architecture, data model and sequence diagrams of the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools* are proposed, extending the models already presented in D5.2 [1].

While the technical details of the tools that compose the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools* [KR4] are presented in D3.5 [2], the main ideas and motivation are presented in this document. Two new evidence management tools have been introduced in this second release: *Assessment and Management of Organisational Evidence* (AMOE) and *Generic Evidence Collector* (GEC). Moreover, the current coverage of the high assurance level requirements identified in the August 2022 draft candidate version of the EUCS scheme [3] has been matched with the different tools comprising the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools*. In addition to that, the future functionalities that should be added in order to comply with the EUCS requirement have been identified.

This document also presents the functional and technical details of the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*, how it fits into the MEDINA framework, the architecture and description of the prototype and how it is delivered, focusing on the updates on D3.1 [4].

Finally, although MEDINA focuses mostly on the automated monitoring and the high-level assurance of the EUCS certification scheme, CSPs may still struggle in the basic level, especially the smaller ones. Therefore, the checklist presented in Section 5 is aimed at these small CSPs so that they can be guided in their self – assessment and can know which kind of evidence they should provide to the CABs when carrying out a third-party assessment. This is an innovation brought in by MEDINA.

Future versions of this document will include updated versions of the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* and the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools*, especially GEC, with new functionalities, as well as an update of the checklist presented in Section 5 and Appendix E: Self-assessment questionnaires.

1 Introduction

1.1 About this deliverable

This document is the second iteration of *Tools and techniques for the management of trustworthy evidence*. It presents an improved version of the tool used for trustworthy evidence management in MEDINA and the architecture of the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools* [KR4]. The technical details of said tools are described in D3.5 [2]. The document also presents a checklist for EUCS-based security self-assessment.

1.1 Document structure

The deliverable is structured as follows. *Section 1* gives the context for the results reported in this document, its scope, structure, and mentions the relationship to other work in the MEDINA project as well as the modifications of this document in comparison with its first version, D3.1 [4].

Section 2 is devoted to the structural description of the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools*, consisting of *Clouditor*, *Wazuh*, the *Vulnerability Assessment Tools (VAT)*, *Codyze*, *Assessment and Management of Organisational Evidence (AMOE)* and the *Generic Evidence Collector (GEC)*. All these tools convene into an orchestrator that is integrated in *Clouditor*. This section explains the architecture, the data model, and the sequence diagrams.

Section 3 briefly introduces the tools that comprise the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools* and demonstrates the coverage of said tools with respect to the high assurance level requirements requiring automated monitoring identified in the August 2022 draft candidate version of the EUCS scheme. This coverage may already be implemented in the tools or there may be some plans for future coverage. The values related to the KPIs are also assessed.

Section 4 develops the updated *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* that has been implemented for this second release, including the functional description, the description of components, as well as the technical specifications and the delivery and usage.

Section 5 presents a self-assessment model developed for the requirements identified as providing basic assurance level. This work is complementary to the work that MEDINA is doing for the requirements of high assurance level. The main target users of this work are small and medium CSPs.

Section 6 summarizes and briefly comments on the reported results.

Appendix A: Current state of practice in tools and techniques in management of evidence presents the current state of practice in the assessment of security performance configuration of cloud workloads, assessment of computing infrastructure and information of data flows, comparing them briefly to the solutions that MEDINA aims to develop. This was firstly introduced in D3.1 [4].

Appendix B: Assessment of Organizational Measures using NLP describes presents some basics for the development of the AMOE tool, that extracts evidence based on metrics from certain documents linked to the organizational measures.

Appendix C: MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System API description contains the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* API description, including returning codes.

Appendix D: EUCS Requirements coverage per tool within the MEDINA Evidence Management Tools presents the EUCS 2022 requirements coverage for each of the evidence management tools: *Clouditor, Codyze, VAT, Wazuh, AMOE* and *GEC*.

Appendix E: Self-assessment questionnaires for EUCS basic requirements presents the exhaustive checklist for self-assessment model developed for the requirements identified as basic assurance level.

1.2 Updates from D3.1

This deliverable evolves from D3.1 [4], so much of its content is common to that included in the previous document, with the ultimate goal of providing a self-contained deliverable that facilitates the reader’s understanding. For simpler tracking of progress and updates with regards to the previous deliverable version (D3.1), Table 1 shows a brief overview of the changes and additions to each of the document sections.

Table 1. Overview of deliverable updates with respect to D3.1

Section	Change
2	<i>MEDINA Evidence Management Tools</i> architecture and data models have been updated.
3	Two new evidence gathering tools have been presented: <i>AMOE</i> and <i>GEC</i> .
4	The description of the <i>MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System</i> has been updated and extended with new functionalities.
5	The description of the checklist for basic assurance level security requirements has been updated to the draft version of the EUCS scheme [3]; new functionalities have been added (scorecards). (*)
Appendix A	New section including a slightly updated version of the state of practice from D3.1 [4].
Appendix B	Updated version of the <i>MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System</i> API.
Appendix C	New section including the analysis of coverage of the draft version of the EUCS scheme for each evidence gathering tool. (*)
Appendix D	Updated version of the basic self-assessment questionnaires updated to the draft version of the EUCS scheme. (*)

(*) Please note that the EUCS requirements referred in this deliverable correspond to a draft version of the ENISA catalogue, and are not intended for being used outside the context of MEDINA

2 Evidence Management Tools Architecture

This section presents the updated architecture of the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools*, which integrates several tools, namely *Vulnerability Assessment Tool (VAT)*, *Wazuh*, *Clouditor*, *Codyze*, *Assessment and Management of Organisational Evidence (AMOE)* and *Generic Evidence Collector (GEC)*, as well as proprietary tools coming from the MEDINA use cases. This section aims to describe the architecture of this component, its data model, and its sequence diagrams.

The description contains much information in common with D3.1 [4] with the final aim of providing a self-contained section that facilitates the reader's understanding. The most important updates are to be found in the updated MEDINA architecture, as *AMOE* and *GEC* have been integrated as new components of the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools*.

2.1 Structural description

2.1.1 Architecture

The architecture of the MEDINA framework has been proposed in the deliverable D5.1 [5] and updated in D5.2 [6]. It is composed by several building blocks, as shown in Figure 1. Each building block corresponds to a well differentiated functionality of the proposed architecture.

In the case of evidence management, more than one of the depicted blocks take part in the whole process. More concretely, the processes involved are: (i) Technical measures collection and assessment (represented in Figure 1 in the block n. 2); (ii) Organizational evidence gathering and processing (represented in Figure 1 in the block n. 1); and (iii) Orchestration of evidence management and trustworthiness processing (represented in Figure 1 in the block n. 3)

Building block 1 in MEDINA's framework implements both a **repository for the organizational evidence**, as well as for the NLP-based techniques for their processing. This processing **assesses related documentation** of the CSP (e.g., security concepts, operation manuals) for conformance with the certification scheme's requirements.

Complementary to this functionality, *building block 2* in MEDINA's framework provides the **assessment of technical measures** by integrating a variety of tools (including native CSP functionalities). This building block targets the multi-layer assessment of the target-of-certification cloud service, i.e., the related IaaS, PaaS, and SaaS stack.

All the assessment results, obtained either from the gathered organizational or technical measures, are holistically **processed, stored and tamper-proofed** by the components shown in *building block 3*. This block also shows the *Orchestrator*, the component responsible for launching and stopping the rest of components as well as forwarding the data it receives.

Figure 1. Building blocks view of the MEDINA framework (source: D5.2 [1])

Figure 2 shows a more detailed schema of the components and architecture involved in evidence management, which is described in the following paragraphs. All relevant tools in this document are depicted in green.

Figure 2. Architecture of the Evidence Management Tools (source MEDINA’s own contribution)

CONTINUOUS EVIDENCE GATHERING TOOLS

The Continuous Evidence Gathering component collects evidence from the CSPs and posts them to the *Security Assessment* component described in D4.2 [7]. There can be evidence of different nature that is gathered by different tools:

- **Technical Evidence Collection** tools from the CSP infrastructure (e.g., *Clouditor*, *Wazuh*, *VAT* or *GEC*).

- **Application-Level Evidence Collection** tools that gather evidence from the static code analysis or specifications of applications (e.g., *Codyze*).
- **Organizational Evidence Gathering** tools that automatically collect organizational evidence by examining the *Repository of Documents* and transform this evidence in the form of technical evidence (e.g., *AMOE* that uses Natural Language Processing (NLP)).

ORCHESTRATOR

The *Orchestrator* is the central component in the MEDINA framework, and as such it is responsible for launching and stopping components in the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools*, as well as forwarding data to other components. The *Orchestrator* receives evidence and assessment results from the *Security Assessment* and stores them. The *Orchestrator* furthermore posts (checksums of) the assessment result to the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*, and forwards assessment results to the *Continuous Certification Evaluation* for evaluating them.

The main sub-components of the *Orchestrator* are the two **databases** for the storage of evidence and assessment results.

MEDINA EVIDENCE TRUSTWORTHINESS MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

The *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* provides a secure mechanism to maintain an audit trail of evidence and assessment results involved in the auditing process. It is implemented by means of smart contracts backed by a Blockchain network.

The sub-components of the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* are:

- Blockchain client, needed by the *Orchestrator* to interact with the Blockchain.
- Blockchain network with the required Smart Contracts to provide the trustworthy functionality.
- Blockchain monitor listening to events from the Smart Contracts.
- Blockchain monitor client to consume the information in the monitor and provide it graphically to auditors.

Every time a new evidence or assessment result is received, the *Orchestrator* writes the corresponding trustworthy information into the component. Then, an event with the information is generated by the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* in Blockchain and received by the Blockchain monitor.

2.1.2 Data Model

The data model of MEDINA framework has been described in the aforementioned architecture deliverable (D5.2 [1]). It describes the different entities that MEDINA components need to function, and which are shared among them. Figure 3 shows how the entities have been categorized into different groups depending on the building block they belong to.

Figure 3. MEDINA framework data model (source: D5.2 [1])

Figure 4 shows a more detailed diagram, extracted from Figure 3, that represents only those entities that have relation with the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools*, their attributes, and relations. The colour code is as follows:

- **Green** entities correspond to evidence gathering and assessment.
- **Purple** entities correspond to evidence trustworthiness or assessment result trustworthiness.
- **Red** entities correspond to Security Assessment rules.

Figure 4. Detail of the Data Model used by the MEDINA Evidence Management Tools

The elements that appear in this entity-relation diagram are described below.

Security Assessment Rule: is the process that applies a specific Metric to assess if the Security Configuration is compliant with a specific Target Value. The Security Assessment Rule compares a Measurement Result with the specific Target Value to obtain a Security Assessment Result. The Security Assessment rule is instantiated from a template which references the Metric to apply, but not the specific Target Value to use for the assessment of the Security Configuration.

Examples:

- Requirement text: Check that the retention time configured for a cloud-based SQL database is set to 35 days.
- Check that the maximum password age on a cloud-based Linux VM is set to 30 days.

A Security Assessment Rule *obtains* **Security Assessment Result**.

Security Assessment Result: is the outcome of a performed Security Assessment Rule.

Examples:

- Compliant
- Non-compliant

A Security Assessment Result is *linked to* one or more **Evidence**.

A Security Assessment Result has a **Trustworthy Assessment Result** which *represents* it.

Evidence: is the existence or verity of something. Objective evidence can be obtained through observation, measurement, test, or by other means. Objective evidence for the purpose of audit generally consists of records, statements of fact or other information which are relevant to the audit criteria and verifiable.

Examples:

- Terraform template for VM being assessed.
- Audit logs from S3 bucket.
- Documented security policy and procedures of a CSP.

An Evidence has a linked **Trustworthy Evidence** which *represents* it.

Trustworthy Evidence: is the representation of an evidence produced, stored, and managed by the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*. This component -based on digital signatures and Blockchain technology- guarantees that all the information stored is trustable, and even more, that every piece of data can always be traced back to its creator. Basically, this entity consists of a hash of the evidence and includes a timestamp too.

Trustworthy Assessment Result: is the representation of an Assessment Result produced, stored, and managed by the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*. It includes a hash of the Assessment Result and a hash of the (possible) non-compliance comments, along with the timestamp. It stores a list of evidence produced by the Security Assessment Result.

A Trustworthy Assessment Result is *linked to* one or more Trustworthy Evidence.

2.1.3 Sequence Diagrams

This section describes the components of the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools* architecture using sequence diagrams. Figure 5 shows one sequence diagram for the components *Continuous evidence gathering and collection*, *Security Assessment* and *Orchestrator*.

2.1.3.1 Continuous Evidence Gathering and collection

The *Continuous evidence gathering and collection* component is used to collect evidence from CSPs and post it to the *Security Assessment* for further processing. The relevant components for the *Continuous evidence gathering and collection* component are as follows:

- *Evidence Collection* tool, e.g., provided by *Clouditor* or *Wazuh*
- *Security Assessment* tool, e.g., provided by *Clouditor*
- Database for the storage of evidence
- Database for the storage of assessment results

In order to be able to collect and store evidence, the tools involved must first be registered. The registration steps can be found in steps 1 and 2 (the numbering corresponds to the sequence

diagram in Figure 5). The sequence for the *Continuous evidence gathering and collection* is as follows: *Orchestrator* -> *Security Assessment* > *Continuous evidence gathering and collection*.

1. The *Evidence Collection* tools must be registered in the *Security Assessment* tool so that the *Security Assessment* can trigger the *Evidence Collection* tool.
2. The *Security Assessment* tool must be registered in the *Orchestrator* to enable the *Orchestrator* to trigger the appropriate *Security Assessment* tool.

Steps 3 and 4 start evidence collection:

3. The *Orchestrator* triggers the *Security Assessment* tool to start the assessment by sending the required metric IDs.
4. The *Security Assessment* tool triggers the *Evidence Collection* tool to start collecting evidence based on the metric IDs.

The actual gathering and collecting evidence takes place in steps 5 and 6:

5. The *Evidence Collection* tool starts the monitoring of the CSPs based on the metric IDs.
6. The *Evidence Collection* posts all evidence to the *Security Assessment* for future processing and storing.

Finally, the *Orchestrator* stores evidence in step 13 to the corresponding database for evidence. If the *Evidence Collection* tool should stop, the *Orchestrator* sends a stop statement in step 15 with the corresponding metric ID which is passed on by the *Security assessment*.

Figure 5. Sequence diagram of the MEDINA Evidence Management Tools architecture

2.1.3.2 Security Assessment

The *Security Assessment* assesses evidence from the *Evidence Collection* tools and pushes the results to the *Orchestrator*. Figure 5 shows the sequence diagram. The *Evidence Collection* tools registration in step 1 has already been described in section 2.1.3.1 . The necessary components for the *Security Assessment* tool are:

- the *Evidence Collection* tools, e.g., *Clouditor* or *Wazuh*
- the *Orchestrator*

Step 3 triggers the *Security* assessment and step 4 triggers the *Evidence collection* tool. Both steps are part of the *security assessment*.

1. The *Orchestrator* triggers the *Security Assessment* tool to start the assessment by sending the required metric IDs.
2. The *Security Assessment* tool triggers the *Evidence Collection* tool to start collecting evidence based on the metric IDs.

The actual *Security Assessment* takes place in steps 6-10:

6. The *Security Assessment* gets the evidence from the *Evidence Collection* tool.
7. The *Security Assessment* gets the target values based on the metric ID contained in the evidence.
8. The *Security Assessment* starts the assessment by using the evidence and the target value of step 7. The result is stored in the assessment result.
9. The *Security Assessment* posts the assessment result to the *Orchestrator* and in a later step the *Orchestrator* stores the assessment result in the database (step 14).
10. The *Security Assessment* posts the evidence to the *Orchestrator* and in a later step the *Orchestrator* stores the evidence in the database (step 13).

If the *Security Assessment* should stop, the *Orchestrator* sends a stop statement in step 15 with the corresponding metric ID which is passed on by the *Security assessment*.

2.1.3.3 Orchestrator

The *Orchestrator* is the central component and is responsible for launching and stopping components in WP3 as well as forwarding data to other components. Figure 5 shows the corresponding sequence diagram. The important components for the *Orchestrator* are:

- The *Security Assessment*
- The *Continuous Certification Evaluation* (WP4)
- The *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*
- The database for evidence
- The database for assessment results

The *Security Assessment* tools are registered in the *Orchestrator* as shown in step 2 and step 3:

2. The *Security Assessment* tool must be registered in the *Orchestrator* to enable the *Orchestrator* to trigger the appropriate *Security Assessment* tool.
3. The *Orchestrator* triggers the *Security Assessment* tool to start the assessment by sending the required metric IDs.

The relevant steps of the *Orchestrator* are steps 9-14 as follows:

9. The *Orchestrator* gets the evidence from the *Security Assessment*.

10. The *Orchestrator* gets the assessment result from the *Security Assessment*.
11. The *Orchestrator* posts the assessment result to the *Continuous Certification Evaluation* for evaluating the result.
12. The *Orchestrator* posts the checksum of the assessment result for the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*.
13. The *Orchestrator* stores the evidence in the database for evidence.
14. The *Orchestrator* stores the assessment result in the database for assessment results.

2.1.3.4 *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*

Figure 6 shows the sequence diagram of the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*. The *Orchestrator* is the only actor to access the system, providing the trustworthy information about evidence and assessment results or checking the previously recorded value in order to check information integrity.

The important components for the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* are:

- The Blockchain client, needed by the *Orchestrator* to interact with the Blockchain
- The Blockchain network with the required Smart Contracts to provide the trustworthy functionality
- A Blockchain monitor listening to events from the Smart Contracts
- A Blockchain monitor client to consume the information in the Monitor and provide it graphically to auditors

The sequence of events for recording new data in the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* is as follows:

- The *Orchestrator* permanently writes the trustworthy information about evidence or assessment results every time a new evidence or assessment result is received.
- Every time new trustworthy information about evidence or assessment results is written in the Blockchain, an event with the information is generated.
- As the Blockchain Monitor is permanently listening to the events from the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* in Blockchain, it will receive all the Blockchain events.
- The monitor client will be subscribed to the interesting events in the Monitor to graphically show the important information.

Once some trustworthy information about evidence and assessment results is recorded in the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*, the validity of a specific information can be also verified following the next sequence of events:

- The *Orchestrator* will check if a specific hash value associated to a specific evidence or assessment result matches the value previously recorded on the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*.
- The *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* will automatically provide the true/false answer about the matching.

Figure 6. Sequence diagram of the MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System

3 MEDINA Tools to Gather Evidence for High Assurance Level Requirements

This section briefly presents the tools that aim to close the gap between the current state of practice (see *Appendix A: Current state of practice in tools and techniques in management of evidence*), the requirements coming from the draft candidate version of the EUCS scheme [3], the MEDINA framework requirements (see D5.2 [1]) and the use cases' needs (see D6.2 [8]).

The description included in this section contains much information in common with D3.1 [4] with the final aim of providing a self-contained section that facilitates the reader's understanding.

As a recap, the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools* as explained in Section 2 is composed of *Clouditor*, *Codyze*, the *Vulnerability Assessment Tool (VAT)* and *Wazuh*. Moreover, the *Assessment and Management of Organisational Evidence (AMOE)* and a new *Generic Evidence Collector (GEC)* are introduced for additional EUCS requirements coverage. The updated technical details of the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools* (implementation and user manual) can be found in the deliverable D3.5 [2].

Furthermore, the current coverage of the EUCS requirements of high assurance level that require an automated monitoring, identified from the August 2022 draft candidate version of the EUCS scheme, has been analysed (see *Appendix D: EUCS Requirements coverage per tool within the MEDINA Evidence Management Tools*). Finally, the evidence gathering tools have been updated to cover more requirements.

Please note that the EUCS requirements referred in this deliverable correspond to a draft version of the ENISA catalogue, and are not intended for being used outside the context of MEDINA.

3.1 Clouditor

Clouditor [9] is an open-source cloud assurance tool with the main goal to continuously evaluate if cloud resources are configured in a secure way and comply with requirements defined by the ENISA draft candidate scheme EUCS, such as data backup and recovery, logging, or data transmission security. *Clouditor* consists of three components that are depicted in Figure 7:

- *Cloud Evidence Collector* for gathering evidence from the CSP.
- *Security Assessment* to assess evidence against metrics and determine the compliance status.
- *Orchestrator* as a central tool for launching components of the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools* and directing data flows between components.

The *Cloud Evidence Collector* component discovers resource properties from various CSPs (e.g., AWS S3) and maps the collected data to *evidence* according to the MEDINA evidence data model, including the ontology terms defined in D2.4 [10].

The *Security Assessment* component provides an interface to evidence gathering components of which the *Cloud Evidence Collector* is only one example. Evidence is assessed against the metrics it retrieves from the *Orchestrator*. *Evidence*, as well as the assessment results, are then sent to the *Orchestrator*. This way, auditors can review also the detailed original evidence alongside the assessment results.

The *Orchestrator* component is a central link in the MEDINA framework and is responsible for launching the rest of the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools* and directing the data flow

between components also across components of different work packages. The *Orchestrator's* tasks comprise the following:

- Trigger the *Evidence Collection* tools, e.g., the *Cloud Evidence Collector*, for collecting evidence.
- Retrieve metrics from the *Catalogue of controls & metrics*.
- Provide metrics to the assessment component(s).
- Receive evidence and assessment results from the *Security Assessment* (and possible further assessment components).
- Securely store evidence and assessment results.
- Send assessment results to the *Continuous Certification Evaluation* component developed in WP4.
- Send checksums of evidence to the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*.

The connections to other components are defined and provided through APIs: An interface for all assessment components is provided, which, in addition to the assessment results, also provides the possibility to send evidence. For the storage of evidence and assessment results in databases, interfaces are provided to an *Evidence storage* and *Assessment result storage*, respectively.

The *Cloudditor* tool with its components is described in further detail in Deliverable D3.5 [2].

Figure 7. Overview of the Cloudditor components (source: D3.5 [2])

3.2 Codyze

Codyze is a static code analysis tool that focuses on verifying security compliance in source code, i.e., by inferring the correct use of cryptographic libraries. It operates on code property graphs and can handle non-compiling or even incomplete code fragments¹. It also aims at helping developers to generate “*insights into coding patterns of Java and C language coding automatically*”².

Codyze collects and assesses evidence from source code of cloud application. It can be integrated into a CI/CD pipeline to collect evidence automatically and generate security assessments for further processing in environments such as Eclipse, IntelliJ, VSCode, and Visual Studio Code.

Codyze uses a domain-specific language called MARK³ to specify what properties source code must exhibit to be considered secure. MARK defines rules that *Codyze* evaluates. Rules are provided with *Codyze* and linked to metrics. An evaluation result of a rule can be evidence or an assessment result. The details depend on the specified rule.

Collected raw evidence is transformed to mapped evidence, according to the format of the ontology defined in D2.4 [10]. If *Codyze* can assess evidence based on MARK rules, it generates assessment results. Evidence and assessment results are submitted to the *Orchestrator* for further processing, presentation, and inspection.

The technical implementation details of *Codyze* can be found on D3.5 [2].

3.3 Vulnerability Assessment Tools (VAT)

Vulnerability Assessment Tools (VAT) act as a modular vulnerability detection and scanning framework. *VAT* is composed of several integrated vulnerability scanner tools and a possibility to easily include custom scripts to monitor the infrastructure either for availability or to detect specific threats. Scanning tasks can be configured to run periodically following a schedule, triggered manually, or integrated into various CI workflows.

VAT can be used by CSPs to satisfy some EUCS requirements or gather evidence for the requirements related to vulnerability detection, use of encrypted communication, detection of new devices on the network, etc.

VAT, installed inside the CSP’s infrastructure, constructs evidence containing measurements made about the monitored resources and sends these evidence objects to the *Security Assessment* component for further processing. Figure 8 shows the schema of closely related components and interactions between them. The interaction with other MEDINA components is implemented with the use of an *Evidence Collector* component that also interacts with *Wazuh* (see Section 3.4). The (*Wazuh* & *VAT*) *Evidence Collector* periodically queries *VAT*’s APIs to examine its configuration and scan results in order to determine compliance with various metrics and generate the respective evidence.

Internally, *VAT* consists of several micro-services: a scheduler that periodically triggers scanning tasks, an API server for external communication, a collection of Docker images that contain the vulnerability scanners (w3af [11], OWASP ZAP [12], Nmap [13]) and logic to interact with other

¹ <https://github.com/Fraunhofer-AISEC/codyze>

² <https://tracxn.com/d/companies/codyze.io>

³ <https://github.com/Fraunhofer-AISEC/codyze-mark-eclipse-plugin>

VAT components, a database for storing results, and a web-based user interface for the configuration and review of scanning results.

The component is described in further detail in Deliverable D3.5 [2].

Figure 8. Schema of Wazuh, VAT and related components (source D3.5 [2])

3.4 Wazuh

Wazuh [14] is an open-source host-based intrusion detection system (HIDS) with multiple modules that support (SIEM-like) security analytics, log data analysis, file integrity monitoring, vulnerability detection, and other defensive security tasks.

In the scope of MEDINA, *Wazuh* is offered to the CSPs as a security solution that can help to check several EUCS requirements about malware protection, logging, threat analytics, and automatic monitoring (alerting). It can also serve as an integration point for various other solutions that produce log files. If any erroneous or anomalous log entries appears, *Wazuh* can alert the user according to the configured rules. By using *Wazuh* at the CSP's side, MEDINA can gather information about the configuration of its modules which provides evidence for fulfilment of the various certification requirements.

The deployment of *Wazuh* consists of several *Wazuh* agents, programs installed on the monitored machines, and a *Wazuh* server that gathers data from the agents and acts as their *Orchestrator*. The *Wazuh* server also contains an Elasticsearch database with a modified Kibana user interface for easier analytics. As presented in Figure 8, *Wazuh* is connected to the MEDINA components through the *Evidence Collection* component, which connects to *Wazuh's* APIs to examine the configurations and possible alerts detected and based on this data generates evidence about the fulfilment of respective metrics.

The component is described in further detail in Deliverable D3.5 [2].

3.5 Assessment and Management of Organisational Evidence (AMOE)

The component Assessment and Management of Organisational Evidence (*AMOE*) is an open-source program, developed to enable evidence extraction and assessment of policy documents. *AMOE* uses specifically developed organisational metrics that aim to measure concrete parts or values in the policy documents. For details of the functional and technical description the reader is referred to D3.5 [2].

Compliance managers or auditors can use *AMOE* to inspect compliance of a policy document to a set of organisational metrics. After uploading a document, the evidence is extracted in the background and can be viewed using the GUI. Besides the extracted evidence, the GUI displays assessment hints. The assessment hints derived by *AMOE* should aid the user to decide the compliance status for each metric. Once a compliance status has been set, the assessment result can be forwarded to the rest of the MEDINA framework – by sending it to the *Orchestrator*. The uploaded policy documents and extracted evidence are linked to a cloud service set by the user. Users can only access data for which they have the permission (set by an attribute in the Keycloak-authentication-token).

The interactive functionality is provided in the GUI but can be also implemented in an external tool like the company compliance dashboard. For the latter purpose, *AMOE* offers a REST API. The main functionalities of GUI and API are:

- Upload a policy document
- Retrieve uploaded documents
- Retrieve extracted evidence including assessment hints
- Set the compliance status / assessment result of an organisational metric
- Forward the assessment result to the *Orchestrator*

Appendix B: Assessment of Organizational Measures using NLP describes different types and methods relevant for organizational evidence extraction. As a summary, the input for an evidence extraction system can include textual, tabular and image files. Depending on the input, different methods need to be applied. To ensure high quality output, a dataset needs to be comprised to test the system.

For natural text documents a possible approach would be to use question-answering systems – e.g., models based on Bert⁴. These can use a question as input and retrieve the answer from a given text. Such models are pre-trained and can be downloaded and used from huggingface⁵. Depending on the model, assumptions and circumstances have to be considered for a successful evidence extraction. The system provides an answer and a pseudo probability to indicate confidence.

Depending on the structure of the log files, evidence can be extracted using regular expressions or XPath queries. NLP might not be necessary as the files are usually not just plain text.

Another possible method to extract the evidence or check for compliance is to compare a document to a previous state or predefined template. The difference analysis depends again on the type of input. Images could be compared by analysing the difference of pixels or apply optical character recognition and compare the text. Alternatively, the bits of the documents could be compared directly, as for the other methods as well, the result highly depends on the goal of the assessment. For textual documents sentence-level differential analysis could be applied

⁴ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/BERT_\(language_model\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/BERT_(language_model))

⁵ <https://huggingface.co/>

(including manual checking of highlighted differences). For textual documents word embeddings and semantic similarities could also be utilized.

The focus is on policy documents as this is relevant for the project partners Bosch and Fabasoft. AMOE works based on a natural language processing (NLP) approach rather than information extraction from log files, difference analysis on images, textual documents or document features, or bitwise comparison. AMOE uses the keywords defined in the organisational metrics to retrieve the relevant sections of a document and then performs queries in the form of questions. The answer to the query is computed with the pre-trained question answering model⁶. The AMOE assessment hint is then calculated on the basis of the metric target value and extracted answer. The results can be investigated via GUI or API.

3.6 The Generic Evidence Collector (GEC)

The requirements defined in the EUCS certification scheme [3] cover a diverse set of categories including human resources, physical security, and procurement management. Therefore, gathering evidence for these categories requires a diverse set of tools and techniques.

For some of the requirements, e.g., configuring a secure protocol for transport encryption, we may assume that a CSP is using one of the large cloud infrastructure providers or a CSPM solution to manage the configuration. In this case, we may address the requirement by an implementation that checks the configuration for this cloud provider, e.g., with the *Cloud Evidence Collector*.

However, for many other requirements there are a multitude of measures that a CSP can implement to fulfil the requirement. Consider the following example of the EUCS requirement HR-03.4H which states: *“All employees shall acknowledge in a documented form the information security policies and procedures presented to them before they are granted any access to CSC data, the production environment, or any functional component thereof, and the verification of this acknowledgement shall be automatically monitored in the processes and automated systems used to grant access rights to employees.”*

A CSP may implement this requirement in many different ways. For instance, a software-as-a-service solution may be used to manage users and the policy acknowledgements. Or the CSP may only use a simple text document to store the acknowledgements. Also, the access control system can be implemented in various ways. So, it is difficult to cover this requirement in a comprehensive manner with one of the tools described in from Section 3.1 to Section 3.5. Therefore, MEDINA provides an additional evidence gathering tool that implements a generic collector which can easily be adapted to any CSP-specific system, i.e., it is not a complete implementation but rather a template that can be adapted to specific systems. In addition, the tool will contain descriptions of techniques in text and/or as pseudo-code form that provide a detailed guide for a CSP to successfully implement the evidence collection.

The *Generic Evidence Collector (GEC)* is based on the *Cloud Evidence Collector*. It presents a self-contained module that can be deployed as a Docker container. It also holds the code for setting up a connection to the *Security Assessment* and implements the MEDINA data model for evidence. It is therefore completely compliant with the MEDINA data model and APIs. Please note that the *GEC* is, at the time of writing, in the design phase and will be implemented in the final iteration of the WP3 components.

⁶ <https://huggingface.co/deepset/roberta-base-squad2>

A CSP who wants to integrate the *GEC* with a specific system only needs to complete the API calls to the CSP-specific system; the response needs to be translated to the MEDINA evidence model. The techniques for achieving these steps are described below.

3.6.1 Descriptions of Techniques

In the following, we provide descriptions of techniques which include explanations of the respective metrics associated to the EUCS requirements [3], certain assumptions as well as the pseudocode for their implementation. Please note that we combine the evidence collection and assessment result creation in the technique description. In some cases, however, it would also be possible to create Rego code instead, to be used in the existing *Security Assessment* component. It is up to the MEDINA user how to put it into practice.

OIS-02.4H: The CSP shall automatically monitor the assignment of responsibilities and tasks to ensure that measures related to segregation of duties are enforced.

Assumptions: We assume that measures for segregation of duties are defined as RBAC constraints. For example, such a constraint may define that no user is allowed to have permissions to deploy software artefacts to a development environment *and* permissions to approve an artefact for release to the production environment.

Also, we assume that user roles and permissions are managed in a respective RBAC system, like Active Directory.

Possible techniques: To check this requirement, existing users and their roles and permissions need to be compared to the segregation of duties constraints, i.e., for any pair of roles given to a certain user, it needs to be checked whether they violate one of the constraints.

Pseudocode

```

users = getUsers()
segregationOfDuties = get SegregationOfDuties() // a map of roles that must not be mixed

for user in users:
    for role in user.roles:
        // for every role the user has, check if it has a constraint in the segregation of
        // duties map; if this constrained role is also in the user's roles, it is a violation
        if segregationOfDuties.get(role) in user.roles:
            evidence = createEvidence(user, segregationOfDuties)
            // create a non-compliant assessmentResult
            createAssessmentResult(evidence, false)
    
```

Metrics

To define a metric related to segregation of duties, we use the approach by Kunz et al. [15]. They propose a metric for the opposite of segregation of duties, i.e., *mixed duties*. Mixed duties calculate the overlap in existing roles. Thus, a metric in this context may define an upper limit for the mixed duties metric:

Requirement ID	Metric ID	Scale	Operator	Target Value	Target Value Type	Resource Type
OIS-02.4H	MixedDuties	[0, ..., 1]	<=	0.1	Float	Identity

ISP-03.5H: The list of exceptions shall be automatically monitored to ensure that the validity of approved exceptions has not expired and that all reviews and approvals are up-to-date.

Assumptions: We assume that the approved exceptions are documented in a table form, e.g., an Excel document, which documents each exception along with its validity period.

Possible techniques: To monitor the list of exceptions, it needs to be retrieved regularly (e.g., daily), and its exceptions and validity periods need to be checked regarding their expiration. If reasonable assumptions can be made about the implementation of the exceptions, their implementation may be checked as well. For example, an exception to the segregation of duties constraints can be checked automatically in the user management system.

Pseudocode

```
exceptionList = getExceptionList()

for exception in exceptionList:
    if exception.validity < Time.now():
        evidence = createEvidence(exception)
        // create a non-compliant assessmentResult
        createAssessmentResult(evidence, false)
```

Metrics

A metric in this context may define an upper limit for existing expired exceptions:

Requirement ID	Metric ID	Scale	Operator	Target Value	Target Value Type	Resource Type
ISP-03.5H	NumberOfExceptions	[0, ...]	<=	0	Integer	Exception

Alternative metrics include a temporal overview, e.g., the average time it takes to fix an expired exception.

HR-03.4H: All employees shall acknowledge in a documented form the information security policies and procedures presented to them before they are granted any access to CSC data, the production environment, or any functional component thereof, and the verification of this acknowledgement shall be automatically monitored in the processes and automated systems used to grant access rights to employees.

Assumptions: Employee acknowledgements of documents such as information security policies, as well as completion of training, can be documented in several ways. We assume that they are either managed in a software-as-a-service solution like SAP or they are managed manually in a simple text document.

Possible techniques: To check this requirement, an *Evidence Collector* should: 1) compare access requests against policy acknowledgements or 2) compare a list of existing user accounts against the list of policy acknowledgements. Option 1) requires the *Evidence Collector* to retrieve a list of access requests to sensitive systems and check whether the requesting party has acknowledged the security policies, while option 2) simply requires retrieving both lists and comparing them as shown below.

Pseudocode

```

acknowledgements = getSecurityPolicyAcknowledgements()
sensitiveRolesList = getSensitiveRolesList()
userList = getUserList()
// only process the users that have a sensitive role
filteredUserList = userList.filter(user.roles in sensitiveRolesList)
for user in filteredUserList::
    if user not in acknowledgements:
        evidence = createEvidence(user)
        // create a non-compliant assessmentResult
        createAssessmentResult(evidence, false)
    
```

Metrics

A metric in this context can define an upper limit for existing users that have access to sensitive systems without having acknowledged policies:

Requirement ID	Metric ID	Scale	Operator	Target Value	Target Value Type	Resource Type
HR-03.4H	NumberOfMissing-PolicyAcknowledgements	[0, ...]	<=	0	Integer	Identity
HR-04.3H	NumberOfMissing-Trainings	[0, ...]	<=	0	Integer	Identity

Alternative metrics include a temporal overview, e.g., of how many users are in this non-compliant state on average. Also, an overview, e.g., of how many users are untrained on average or how long it takes for the average user to complete it once they are registered as new users, are possible metrics.

HR-05.2H: The CSP shall apply a specific procedure to revoke the access rights and process appropriately the accounts and assets of employees when their employment is terminated or changed, defining specific roles and responsibilities and including a documented checklist of all required steps; the CSP shall automatically monitor the application of this procedure.

Assumptions: We assume that a list of current users and their role assignments are available through a user management system, such as Active Directory.

Possible Techniques

- Technique to implement the procedure: The procedure mentioned in HR-05.2H can be implemented as a periodic program which, for instance, runs in a serverless function in the cloud system. This function could retrieve the list of users and a list of active contracts to check whether only active contracts have a respective user in the cloud system.
- Technique to monitor the procedure: To monitor the application of the procedure, the *Evidence Collector* can perform a health check of the underlying Compute resource (the serverless function). Furthermore, it can retrieve the results of the procedure, i.e., a list of currently active users along with an indication of their contract activity.

Pseudocode

```

usersAndContracts = getUsersAndContractsList()
for entry in usersAndContracts::
    if entry.contract.status == "terminated":
        evidence = createEvidence(entry)
        // create a non-compliant assessmentResult
        createAssessmentResult(evidence, false)
    
```

Metrics

A metric in this context may define a grace period for revoking access rights of users with terminated contracts:

Requirement ID	Metric ID	Scale	Operator	Target Value (days)	Target Value Type	Resource Type
HR-05.2H	Revocation-GracePeriod	[0, ...]	<=	5	Integer	Revocation-Period

AM-01.4H The CSP shall automatically monitor the process performing the inventory of assets to guarantee it is up-to-date.

Assumptions: We assume that the process that performs the inventory is a custom program that runs, for example, on a dedicated cloud resource such as a virtual machine. We also assume that the generated inventory is stored in a database, e.g., a SQL database.

Possible techniques

- Technique to implement the process: Different possibilities exist to implement a process that creates a resource inventory (we focus on large cloud providers like Azure and AWS). First, the available service APIs can be used to list all types of resources, like virtual machines, networks, etc. Second, an Infrastructure-as-Code template can be exported which describes the resources in a standardized format. Please note, however, that the responses always depend on the access rights of the requesting client, so it needs *read*-rights on all resources.
- Technique to monitor the process: To guarantee that the process is performed regularly, and the inventory therefore is up-to-date, the CSP may monitor the health of the resource the process runs on. Additionally, tests can be performed which create a new resource and check whether it appears in the inventory.

Pseudocode

```

vm = getInventoryVirtualMachine()

If vm.status != "running"
    evidence = createEvidence(vm)
    // create a non-compliant assessmentResult
    createAssessmentResult(evidence, false)
else
    newVm = createVm()
inventory = database.get(inventoryTable)
if newVM not in inventory
    evidence = createEvidence(vm)
    
```

```
// create a non-compliant assessmentResult
createAssessmentResult(evidence, false)
```

Metrics

A metric in this context may define the uptime of the inventory resource:

Requirement ID	Metric ID	Scale	Operator	Target Value	Target Value Type	Resource Type
AM-01.4H	Inventory-Uptime	[0, ..., 1]	>=	0.99	Float	VirtualMachine

AM-04.1H The CSP shall ensure and document that all employees are committed to the policies and procedures for acceptable use and safe handling of assets in the situations described in AM-02, and this commitment shall be automatically monitored.

Assumptions: We assume that the commitments are documented in a table, e.g., an Excel document. We also assume that a list of current users is available through a user management system, like Active Directory.

Possible techniques: To check this requirement, the commitments to the policies and procedures for acceptable use and safe handling of assets in the given situation simply needs to be checked against an up-to-date list of users.

Pseudocode:

```
commitments = getPolicyCommitments()
userList = getUserList()
for user in userList:
    if user not in commitments:
        evidence = createEvidence(user)
        // create a non-compliant assessmentResult
        createAssessmentResult(evidence, false)
```

Metrics

A metric in this context may define an upper limit for existing users that have not completed the training:

Requirement ID	Metric ID	Scale	Operator	Target Value	Target Value Type	Resource Type
AM-04.1H	NumberOfMissing-Commitments	[0, ...]	<=	0	Integer	Identity

Alternative metrics include a temporal overview, e.g., of how many users have not given the commitment on average or how long it takes for the average user to complete it once they are registered as new users.

PS-02.8H The access control policy shall include logging of all accesses to non-public areas that enables the CSP to check whether only defined personnel have entered these areas, and this logging shall be automatically monitored.

Assumptions: We assume that the physical accesses are logged in a database, e.g., a SQL table. We also assume that a current user list is available through a user management system, like Active Directory.

Possible techniques: To check this requirement, it is necessary to retrieve the accesses, as well as the list of users. All accesses that have been made by a certain user are then filtered out. All roles of the user can then be checked for their inclusion in the access in question.

Pseudocode

```

accesses = getPhysicalAccessesToNonPublicAreas()
userList = getUserList()
for user in userList:
    for role in user.roles:
        for access in accesses.filter(user):
            if access not in role.permissions:
                evidence = createEvidence(user)
                // create a non-compliant assessmentResult
                createAssessmentResult(evidence, false)
    
```

Metrics

A metric in this context may define an upper limit for users that (try to) access sensitive areas without permission, e.g., to trigger an alert:

Requirement ID	Metric ID	Scale	Operator	Target Value	Target Value Type	Resource Type
PS-02.8H	MaximumSensitive-AccessRequests	[0, ...]	<=	0	Integer	Identity

3.7 Summary of the implementation coverage of the requirements of the EUCS draft candidate scheme by the MEDINA Evidence Management Tools

MEDINA focuses primarily on the high assurance level requirements that the draft candidate version of the EUCS scheme [3] lists as “continuous (automated monitoring)”⁷. This results in a list of 34 EUCS requirements that fulfil these conditions (see Table 2).

Table 2. Summary of the identified requirements from the August 2022 draft candidate EUCS [3]

Req.ID	Requirement
OIS-02.4H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the assignment of responsibilities and tasks to ensure that measures related to segregation of duties are enforced.”
ISP-03.5H	“The list of exceptions shall be automatically monitored to ensure that the validity of approved exceptions has not expired and that all reviews and approvals are up-to-date.”

⁷ Please note that the EUCS requirements referred in this deliverable correspond to a draft version of the ENISA catalogue August 2022 and are not intended for being used outside the context of MEDINA.

Req.ID	Requirement
HR-03.4H	“All employees shall acknowledge in a documented form the information security policies and procedures presented to them before they are granted any access to CSC data, the production environment, or any functional component thereof, and the verification of this acknowledgement shall be automatically monitored in the processes and automated systems used to grant access rights to employees.”
HR-04.3H	“The CSP shall ensure that all employees complete the security awareness and training program defined for them on a regular basis, and when changing target group, and shall automatically monitor the completion of the security awareness and training program.”
HR-05.2H	“The CSP shall apply a specific procedure to revoke the access rights and process appropriately the accounts and assets of employees when their employment is terminated or changed, defining specific roles and responsibilities and including a documented checklist of all required steps; the CSP shall automatically monitor the application of this procedure.”
HR-06.2H	“The agreements shall be accepted by external service providers and suppliers when the contract is agreed, and this acceptance shall be automatically monitored.”
HR-06.3H	“The agreements shall be accepted by internal employees of the CSP before authorisation to access CSC data is granted, and this acceptance shall be automatically monitored.”
HR-06.5H	“The CSP shall inform its internal employees, external service providers and suppliers and obtain confirmation of the updated confidentiality or non-disclosure agreement, and this acceptance shall be automatically monitored.”
AM-01.4H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the process performing the inventory of assets to guarantee it is up-to-date.”
AM-03.4H	“The approval of the commissioning and decommissioning of hardware shall be digitally documented and automatically monitored.”
AM-04.1H	“The CSP shall ensure and document that all employees are committed to the policies and procedures for acceptable use and safe handling of assets in the situations described in AM-02, and this commitment shall be automatically monitored.”
PS-02.8H	“The access control policy shall include logging of all accesses to non-public areas that enables the CSP to check whether only defined personnel have entered these areas, and this logging shall be automatically monitored.”
OPS-02.2H	“The provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services shall be automatically monitored to guarantee fulfilment of these safeguards.”
OPS-05.3H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the systems covered by the malware protection and the configuration of the corresponding mechanisms to guarantee fulfilment of above requirements, and the antimalware scans to track detected malware or irregularities.”
OPS-07.2H	“In order to check the proper application of these measures, the CSP shall automatically monitor the execution of data backups, and make available to the CSCs a service portal for monitoring the execution of backups when the CSC uses backup services with the CSP.”
OPS-09.2H	“When the backup data is transmitted to a remote location via a network, the transmission of the data takes place in an encrypted form that corresponds to the state-of-the-art (cf. CKM-02), and shall be automatically monitored by the CSP to verify the execution of the backup.”

Req.ID	Requirement
OPS-12.1H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor log data in order to identify security events that might lead to security incidents, in accordance with the logging and monitoring requirements, and the identified events shall be reported to the appropriate departments for timely assessment and remediation.”
OPS-12.2H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor that event detection processes operate as intended on appropriate assets as identified in the asset classification catalogue (cf AM-05-1H).”
OPS-13.1H	“The CSP shall store all log data in an integrity-protected and aggregated form that allow its centralized evaluation, and shall automatically monitor the aggregation and deletion of logging and monitoring data.”
OPS-18.6H	“The CSP shall provide and promote, where appropriate, automatic update mechanisms for the assets provided by the CSP that the CSCs have to install or operate under their own responsibility, to ease the rollout of patches and updates after an initial approval from the CSC.”
OPS-21.1H	“The CSP shall harden all the system components under its responsibility that are used to provide the cloud service, according to accepted industry standards, and automatically monitor these system components for conformity with hardening requirements.”
IAM-03.1H	“The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to block user accounts after a certain period of inactivity, as defined in the policy of AIM-02, for user accounts, and automatically monitor its application. Such user accounts are: (1) Of employees of the CSP as well as for system components involved in automated authorisation processes; and (2) Associated with identities assigned to persons, identities assigned to non-human entities and identities assigned to multiple persons.”
IAM-03.2H	“The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to block accounts after a certain number of failed authentication attempts, as defined in the policy of AIM-02, based on the risks of the accounts, associated access rights and authentication mechanisms, and automatically monitor its application.”
IAM-03.5H	“The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to revoke accounts that have been blocked by another automatic mechanism after a certain period of inactivity, as defined in the policy of AIM-02 for user accounts, and automatically monitor its application.”
IAM-03.6H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the context of authentication attempts and flag suspicious events to authorized persons, as relevant.”
CCM-04.1H	“The CSP shall approve any change to the cloud service, based on defined criteria and involving CSCs in the approval process according to contractual requirements, before they are made available to CSCs in the production environment, and the approval processes shall be automatically monitored.”
CCM-05.1H	“The CSP shall define roles and rights according to IAM-01 for the authorised personnel or system components who are allowed to make changes to the cloud service in the production environment, and the changes in the production environment shall be automatically monitored to enforce these roles and rights.”
PM-04.7H	“The CSP shall supplement procedures for monitoring compliance with automatic monitoring, by leveraging automatic procedures, when possible, relating to the following aspects: (1) Configuration of system components;

Req.ID	Requirement
	(2) Performance and availability of system components; (3) Response time to malfunctions and security incidents; and (4) Recovery time (time until completion of error handling)."
PM-04.8H	"The CSP shall automatically monitor Identified violations and discrepancies, and these shall be automatically reported to the responsible personnel or system components of the CSP for prompt assessment and action."
IM-02.5H	"The CSP shall automatically monitor the processing of security incidents to verify the application of incident management policies and procedures."
CO-03.5H	"Internal audits shall be supplemented by procedures to automatically monitor compliance with applicable requirements of policies and instructions."
CO-03.6H	"The CSP shall implement automated monitoring to identify vulnerabilities and deviations, which shall be automatically reported to the appropriate CSP's subject matter experts for immediate assessment and action."
INQ-03.4H	"The CSP shall automatically monitor the accesses performed by or on behalf of investigators as determined by the process described in INQ-01."
PSS-04.2H	"An integrity check shall be performed, automatically monitored and reported to the CSC if the integrity check fails."

Table 3 shows the coverage of these 34 EUCS requirements by the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools*. The purpose of this coverage is to show the level of compliance with some of the MEDINA KPIs, in particular KPI 1.1, KPI 1.2 and KPI 4.1. *Appendix D: EUCS Requirements coverage per tool within the MEDINA Evidence Management Tool* details the specific requirements coverage for each of the MEDINA tools (*Clouditor, Codyze, Wazuh, VAT, AMOE* and *GEC*) within the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools*, including the 34 requirements from Table 2 as well as additional ones.

The structure of Table 3 is as follows:

- Each row corresponds to a EUCS requirement [3].
- The "Type" column identifies the type of requirement: technical (*tech*) or organizational (*org*). Please note that the requirement is considered organizational if it implies the monitoring of a static policy document.
- The "Coverage" column shows the level of coverage of the requirement by the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools* described in Section 3. The background colour means:
 - Green The *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools* cover the requirement to some extent (i.e., at least one metric has been implemented).
 - Orange There is a plan or idea to implement the requirement by any of the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools*, but it has not yet been realised.
 - Red It is not possible to cover the requirement due to its nature.

Table 3. Summary of the coverage of the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools* for the 34 high level requirements from the draft candidate EUCS [3]

Category	Req.ID	Type	Coverage
Organizational Information Security	OIS-02.4H	Tech	
Information Security Policies	ISP-03.5H	Tech	
Human Resources	HR-03.4H	Tech & Org	
	HR-04.3H	Tech	
	HR-05.2H	Tech	
	HR-06.2H	Tech	

Category	Req.ID	Type	Coverage
	HR-06.3H	Tech	Orange
	HR-06.5H	Tech & Org	Green
Asset Management	AM-01.4H	Tech	Green
	AM-03.4H	Tech	Orange
	AM-04.1H	Tech & Org	Green
Physical Security	PS-02.8H	Tech & Org	Green
Operational Security	OPS-02.2H	Tech	Green
	OPS-05.3H	Tech	Green
	OPS-07.2H	Tech	Green
	OPS-09.2H	Tech	Green
	OPS-12.1H	Tech	Green
	OPS-12.2H	Tech	Orange
	OPS-13.1H	Tech	Orange
	OPS-18.6H	Tech	Green
Identity, Authentication and Access Control Management	OPS-21.1H	Tech	Green
	IAM-03.1H	Tech	Green
	IAM-03.2H	Tech & Org	Green
	IAM-03.5H	Tech & Org	Orange
Change and Configuration Management	IAM-03.6H	Tech	Orange
	CCM-04.1H	Tech & Org	Orange
Procurement Management	CCM-05.1H	Tech & Org	Orange
	PM-04.7H	Tech	Green
Incident Management	PM-04.8H	Tech	Orange
	IM-02.5H	Tech	Orange
Compliance	CO-03.5H	Tech & Org	Green
	CO-03.6H	Tech	Green
Dealing with Investigation Requests from Government Agencies	INQ-03.4H	Tech	Orange
Product Safety and Security	PSS-04.2H	Tech	Orange

From Table 3, we can conclude that at the time of writing this deliverable the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools* fully cover **21 of the 34 EUCS requirements** identified in Table 2. Furthermore, **there is a plan or idea to cover the remaining 13 requirements** identified in Table 2 in the next release of the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools*. Summarizing, **there is no requirement that is not already covered (green) or for which there is no plan in place (orange)**.

Taking this into consideration, we can calculate the current level of achievement for the following MEDINA KPIs:

- **KPI 1.1**, which was reformulated in July 2022 as follows: *“Provide realizable metrics for at least 70% of the technical measures referenced in EUCS-High assurance requiring ‘continuous (automated)’ monitoring”*.
 - Considering results from Table 3, the 34 identified requirements are considered to be of a technical nature. At the time of writing, *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools* already cover around **61.8% (21/34)** of the technical requirements and have a plan to cover the remaining **38.2% (13/34)**.
 - Summarizing, at the time of writing, **KPI 1.1 has been achieved at 61.8%, which is very close to the 70% coverage target**.

- **KPI 1.2**, which was reformulated in July 2022 as follows: *“Provide a concrete proposal for semi-automated evaluation of metrics related to at least 50% of the organizational measures in EUCS-High assurance requiring ‘continuous (automated)’ monitoring”*.
 - Considering results from Table 3, 9 from the 34 requirements identified are considered to be organizational. At the time of writing, *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools* already cover around **66.7% (6/9)** of the technical requirements and have a plan to cover the remaining **33.3% (3/9)**.
 - Summarizing, at the time of writing, **KPI 1.2 has been achieved at 66.7%, which is above the 50% coverage target.**

The next iteration of the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools* will improve the current planned coverage (orange cells) to achieve a complete coverage (green cells) and 100% coverage for KPI 1.1 and KPI 1.2.

- **KPI 4.1**, which was formulated in the DoA as follows: *“Provide techniques for the continuous gathering of evidence related to the implementation of 100% of the technical measures contributed in KPI 1.1”*.
 - This KPI is measured by considering the number of metrics implemented for covering the 34 EUCS requirements identified in Table 2. Although some coverage of requirements has already been implemented in the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools*, the metrics have not been fully integrated yet with the Ontology and the Catalogue of Controls and Metrics. Table 4 summarises the number of metrics currently implemented for covering the 34 requirements. Other metrics for covering additional requirements have also been implemented. The focus so far has been on the implementation of metrics for OPS requirements; metrics for the remaining categories will be integrated in the next iteration.
 - Considering the results in Table 4, fully integrated metrics exist for 18 of the 34 EUCS requirements. As a result, techniques are provided for **52.9% (18/34)** of the technical requirements.
 - Summarizing, at the time of writing, **KPI 4.1 has been achieved at 52.9%; although this is far from the target, it is expected to be increased to 100% in the next release.**

Table 4. Summary of the number of metrics implemented for covering the 34 EUCS high level requirements in Table 2

Category	Req.ID	Type	# Metrics
Organizational Information Security	OIS-02.4H	Tech	0
Information Security Policies	ISP-03.5H	Tech	0
Human Resources	HR-03.4H	Tech & Org	1
	HR-04.3H	Tech	0
	HR-05.2H	Tech	1
	HR-06.2H	Tech	0
	HR-06.3H	Tech	0
	HR-06.5H	Tech & Org	1
Asset Management	AM-01.4H	Tech	1
	AM-03.4H	Tech	0
	AM-04.1H	Tech & Org	0
Physical Security	PS-02.8H	Tech & Org	1
Operational Security	OPS-02.2H	Tech	4

Category	Req.ID	Type	# Metrics
	OPS-05.3H	Tech	5
	OPS-07.2H	Tech	3
	OPS-09.2H	Tech	10
	OPS-12.1H	Tech	6
	OPS-12.2H	Tech	7
	OPS-13.1H	Tech	4
	OPS-18.6H	Tech	10
	OPS-21.1H	Tech	13
Identity, Authentication and Access Control Management	IAM-03.1H	Tech	1
	IAM-03.2H	Tech & Org	0
	IAM-03.5H	Tech & Org	0
	IAM-03.6H	Tech	0
Change and Configuration Management	CCM-04.1H	Tech & Org	0
	CCM-05.1H	Tech & Org	0
Procurement Management	PM-04.7H	Tech	1
	PM-04.8H	Tech	0
Incident Management	IM-02.5H	Tech	0
Compliance	CO-03.5H	Tech & Org	1
	CO-03.6H	Tech	1
Dealing with Investigation Requests from Government Agencies	INQ-03.4H	Tech	0
Product Safety and Security	PSS-04.2H	Tech	0

4 MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System

This section presents an improved version of the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*, designed, and developed in Task 3.5 and based on the theoretical analysis gathered in D4.2 [7].

The description included in this section contains much information in common with D3.1 [4] with the final aim of providing a self-contained section that facilitates the reader's understanding.

The most relevant improvements that have been implemented in this iteration are the following:

- Updating the architecture to include the two types of users: administrators and authorized *Orchestrators'* owners.
- Although the implemented functionality of *Smart Contracts* is similar to that described in D3.1, some internal improvements have been made to its implementation to: i) optimize gas consumption; ii) define modular, repeatable, and self-contained scripts that facilitate possible re-use in the future; and iii) fix minor bugs.
- Although the implemented functionality of the *Blockchain client* is similar to that described in D3.1, some internal improvements have been made to its implementation: i) the API functionality has been extended with a new authorization request endpoint that allows the *Orchestrators'* owner to automatically ask for authorization; ii) Swagger has been added to the API; iii) error handling has been included for all API endpoints; and iv) minor bug fixes have been made.
- Although the implementation of the *Blockchain viewer* is similar to that described in D3.1, several improvements have been made: i) authentication is required to access graphical dashboards; ii) implementation of role-based access for different users to access different data; iii) different dashboards for different users (administrators and *Orchestrators'* owners); iv) improved usability and appearance; and v) addition of filters.

4.1 Functional description

Blockchain technology has started to be considered as a suitable technology for trustworthy purposes [16], [17], [18], [19] as it promises a transparent, secure, and affordable solution to audit trails. First, Blockchain eliminates the need of a central authority for maintaining data records as it decentralizes the information in a distributed network. Furthermore, Blockchain guarantees immutability of the recorded information as it is "copied" in a distributed network. Another key aspect is that information recorded in a Blockchain is digitally signed by its creator so the origin can always be traced back.

Although Blockchain integrity, decentralization, and non-repudiation inherent features make it a suitable technology for audit trails, its use is still not widespread, and its usability is not user-friendly. Nowadays, a Blockchain client is needed for interacting with a Blockchain. This is usually a limiting requirement as nowadays it is not common for users to have a Blockchain client deployed in their systems. That is why a graphical and web-based tool to access the information recorded in the Blockchain in a user-friendly way is highly recommended, making Blockchain totally transparent for external users (for example, auditors) and providing a graphical mechanism to verify the information records in the Blockchain about evidence and assessment results provided by the *Orchestrators*. This way, anyone with permission (authentication is needed), could check the information recorded in the Blockchain without any kind of Blockchain client (Blockchain will be totally transparent).

The Blockchain based *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*, provides a secure mechanism for MEDINA to maintain an audit trail of evidence and assessment results.

The *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* is implemented in **Smart Contracts** backboneed by a common **Blockchain network** for all the MEDINA framework instances, providing the following **functionalities**:

- It includes the logic for all *Orchestrator* instances in MEDINA to **provide the required information to be audited** (about evidence and assessment results).
- It provides **long-term information recording**, thanks to the inherent advantages of Blockchain (integrity, decentralization, authenticity...).
- It includes the logic for external users to **access MEDINA’s audited information** (about evidence and assessment results) **in a graphical and user-friendly way**.

Related requirements

Below is the collection of requirements (described in D5.2 [6]) related to the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* and a description of how and to what extent these requirements are implemented at this point of development.

Requirement id	ETM.01
Short title	Trustworthiness of evidence
Description	The evidence orchestrator must integrate reasonable safeguards for guaranteeing the trustworthiness of collected evidence.
Status	Implemented

The trustworthiness of evidence is guaranteed thanks to the design of the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*. Two key points: (i) Blockchain is used as trustworthy storage. Information recorded on the Blockchain cannot be tampered, so information integrity is guaranteed; (ii) Instead of recording evidence, evidence hashes/checksums are recorded for avoiding sensitive data disclosure; hashes are considered sufficiently secure (reasonable safeguards) as it is almost impossible to obtain the same hash for two different sets of data (see D4.2 [7] for more details).

Requirement id	ETM.02
Short title	Transmission of evidence checksums
Description	The evidence orchestrator should integrate a Ledger client that stores checksums of evidence in a DLT.
Status	Implemented

A Blockchain client has been provided for the *MEDINA Orchestrator* to interact with the Blockchain and provide a way to be able to register evidence and assessment results hashes/checksums in the Blockchain. The Blockchain client has been integrated with the *Orchestrator*.

Requirement id	ETM.03
Short title	Trustworthiness guaranteeing capabilities
Description	Enable trustworthiness guaranteeing capabilities by extracting checksums from DLT and comparing with current checksums to detect modifications.
Status	Partially implemented

The *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* provides different ways to obtain previously recorded hashes/checksums associated to a specific evidence id or assessment result id: (i) it is possible to directly compare the current checksum with the one previously recorded for a specific evidence/assessment result id through the Blockchain client API; (ii) it is possible to get the information recorded for a specific evidence/assessment result id through the API and obtain the recorded checksum from it to be compared with the current one; (iii) it is possible to

get the information recorded for a specific evidence/assessment result id through the Blockchain monitor (graphical interface) and obtain the recorded hash from it to be compared with the current one; and (iv) it is possible to look for a specific hash/checksum recorded on the Blockchain through the Blockchain monitor. If it exists, the checksum is correct and the information has not been modified; if not, the information has been modified.

These methods require some manual operations. Different automatic ways to extract recorded checksums and compare them with the current ones has been theoretically analysed inside D4.2 [7].

Requirement id	ETM.04
Short title	Tamper-Resistance
Description	The developed tool must provide a tamper-proof way of storing evidence in the considered attacker model.
Status	Implemented

A risk assessment study was carried out inside D4.2 [7] for identifying the main security risks for evidence integrity. Blockchain was considered a suitable technology for providing tamper-proofs of evidence. The *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* records information related to evidence on the Blockchain.

Requirement id	ETM.05
Short title	Tamper-Resistance
Description	The DAT must provide a tamper-proof way of storing audit information in the considered attacker model.
Status	Implemented

A risk assessment study was carried out inside D4.2 [7] for identifying the main security risks for audit information (assessment results) integrity. Blockchain was considered a suitable technology for providing tamper-proofs of assessment results. The *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* records information related to assessment results on the Blockchain.

4.1.1 Fitting into overall MEDINA Architecture

Figure 9 shows how the Blockchain-based *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* fits into the overall MEDINA architecture. It provides a common service of trustworthy records to be able to perform automated inspections if needed while guaranteeing the integrity of information.

Figure 9. Overall MEDINA Architecture (source: D5.2 [6])

On the one hand, taking into account the MEDINA components, only the *Orchestrator(s)* will provide information related to evidence and assessment results. On the other hand, compliance manager auditors will be able to consume information recorded in the Blockchain by means of the web-based interface of the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*.

4.2 Technical description

This section describes the technical details of the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*.

4.2.1 Prototype architecture

Figure 10 shows the Blockchain-based *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* architecture.

Figure 10. MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

The architecture is composed of five main elements:

- **Blockchain network.** A Blockchain network has been configured with three nodes deployed in TECNALIA servers. The Blockchain network is going to be offered as a service by TECNALIA to validate the system solution; however, in real deployments, additional nodes from different companies will be recommended for improving the governance of the Blockchain network. All the information provided by the MEDINA Orchestrator to the MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System will be recorded in all the Blockchain nodes of the Blockchain network; in this way, the integrity of the recorded information is guaranteed.
- **Smart Contracts.** The MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System functionalities have been implemented in Smart Contracts deployed in the Blockchain network (previous element). Smart Contracts are programs typically used to automate the execution of certain actions, guaranteeing that all actors can have immediate certainty of the outcome. Like the information, the Smart Contracts definition is also recorded in all nodes of the Blockchain, ensuring the integrity and security of execution. The MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System functionalities include the registration of data in the Blockchain (evidence and assessment results) to be verified,

as well as the use of this previously registered data for integrity verification. In addition, Blockchain-based events are also generated to feed the Blockchain viewer.

- **Blockchain client.** Every *Orchestrator* using the functionalities of the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* needs a Blockchain client to interact with the Blockchain (wallet management functionalities, transactions generation, etc.). To facilitate integration and deployment, this Blockchain client will be deployed on all the *Orchestrator* instances as a Docker image that exposes an API REST to interact with it.
- **Blockchain viewer.** It listens for Blockchain events from the Smart Contracts and normalises and categorises the details for proper consumption from the Blockchain viewer client. The Blockchain viewer allows to isolate external users from the need to have a Blockchain client to consume information recorded on the Blockchain.
- **Blockchain viewer client:** A client that consumes the normalised and categorised information from the Blockchain viewer.

4.2.2 Description of components

This section describes the five components that appear in the architecture of the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* (see Figure 10).

4.2.2.1 Blockchain network

The Blockchain network considered for the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* is **Quorum** [20]. This selection was based on the comparative study carried out inside WP4, where different Blockchain technologies were analysed, concluding that Quorum is the most suitable one (for more details, please refer to D4.2 [7]).

The Quorum Blockchain network has been deployed at TECNALIA for prototype purposes; three Quorum Blockchain nodes form the test Blockchain network; however, as mentioned in Section 4.2.1, in real deployments, more nodes from different organizations are needed to improve the decentralization and governance of the Blockchain network. These additional nodes need to be permissioned to be part of the Blockchain network, maintaining the network state, executing Smart Contracts, and verifying transactions. Figure 11 shows the architecture of each Quorum node.

Figure 11. Quorum Blockchain node architecture (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

Quorum [20] is a private Blockchain network created by JP Morgan as a fork of the public Ethereum. It stands out for its high maturity level (being a fork of Ethereum means a widely proven background) which reuses existing technology and maintains sync with upcoming versions of Ethereum. Its main advantages are:

- Advanced Smart Contracts. In Quorum, Smart Contracts are based on Solidity language, allowing all the logic of a complete “Turing machine”.
- No cryptocurrency. The *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* does not require any cryptocurrency. For this reason, it is not necessary to complicate the operation of the Blockchain network. In this sense, Quorum stands out because of its high simplicity.
- Voting based consensus. Quorum leverages a faster voting-based consensus algorithm [21] which does not require large processing features in the Blockchain nodes. This consensus algorithm is lighter.
- Private network. Quorum only allows permissioned nodes to participate; it is a private network.
- High scalability level. Quorum is scalable in terms of participants and activities.

The Quorum nodes communicate with Blockchain clients and other Blockchain nodes using the Constellation peer-to-peer system based on secure messages [22]. This module is formed of two components:

- Transaction Manager: it communicates the different Quorum nodes by orchestrating private transactions (sending/receiving encrypted payloads among them). It uses the Enclave for cryptographic operations.
- Enclave: It executes encryption and decryption operations.

Every information provided by the *MEDINA Orchestrators* to the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* (evidence and assessment results) and the Smart Contracts with the specific *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* functionality will be recorded in all the Quorum nodes.

4.2.2.2 Smart Contracts

The Smart Contracts deployed in the Blockchain network include all the intelligence (functionalities) for the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*. The main functionalities are:

User management

There are two kinds of users:

- **Administrators.** These actors are those who can authorize or de-authorize *Orchestrators* to access the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*. Administrators can also define new administrators or remove existing ones. The default administrator in the system for prototype purposes is “TECNALIA”.
- **Authorized *Orchestrators’* owners.** These users shall have been authorized by an existing administrator to use the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* (for example, XLAB, FHG, etc.). Each of these users will own “one” *MEDINA Orchestrator* which can be then registered in the system (there will be just one *Orchestrator* associated to each authorized *Orchestrator* owner because of implemented access control policies in the Smart Contract). The information associated to each *Orchestrator* can only be retrieved by its owner. By this way, although the Blockchain network will be common for several authorized *Orchestrators’* owners (information associated to different *Orchestrators* will be recorded in the same Blockchain network), each authorized *Orchestrator* owner will only have access to the information associated to its own registered *Orchestrator*.

Blockchain addresses are used in the Blockchain based *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* for users' identity purposes (the Blockchain address will be the user identifier).

Administrators' functionalities

Administrators can obtain general information about the current status of the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* (only administrators can execute the following set of functionalities):

- Register a new administrator (the new administrator *id* is needed)
- Remove an existing administrator (the administrator *id* is needed)
- Check if a specific user *id* is an administrator (the administrator *id* is needed)
- Get the number of administrators in the system
- Authorize a new *Orchestrator* owner (the new *Orchestrator* owner *id* is needed)
- De-authorize an existing *Orchestrator* owner (the *Orchestrator* owner *id* is needed)
- Check if a specific *Orchestrator* owner *id* is an authorized *Orchestrator* owner (the *Orchestrator* owner *id* is needed)
- Get the total number of authorized *Orchestrator* owners in the system
- Get the total number of registered *Orchestrators* in the system
- Get all the registered *Orchestrators* *ids* in the system (administrators can only see the registered *Orchestrator id*, but not the information provided during the registering process by the authorized *Orchestrator* owner).

Authorized *Orchestrator* owners' functionalities

Authorized *Orchestrator* owners can register *Orchestrators*. This registration process considers the following data model for each *Orchestrator* identification:

- **id:** This is the internal *id* used to identify the *Orchestrator* inside the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*. It is automatically generated by the Smart Contract considering its Blockchain address (this is unique).
- **owner:** It refers to the authorized *Orchestrator* owner *id* who has registered the *Orchestrator*. As above, it refers to the Blockchain address of the authorized *Orchestrator* owner, as it is considered the user identifier. It is automatically provided by the Smart Contract.
- **timestamp:** It refers to the timestamp in seconds since the epoch of the *Orchestrator* registering process. It is automatically generated by the Smart Contract.

The functionalities related to the *Orchestrators*' owners are:

- Register a new *Orchestrator* (only one *Orchestrator* per authorized *Orchestrator* owner)
- Get the registered *Orchestrator id*
- Get the associated authorized *Orchestrator* owner *id*
- Get the registered *Orchestrator* registration timestamp
- Add new evidence information (details following the trustworthy evidence data model shown in Figure 12 are needed)
- Get a specific evidence information (the specific evidence *id* is needed)
- Get all the added evidence *ids* associated to this *Orchestrator*
- Add new assessment result information (details following the trustworthy assessment result data model shown in Figure 12 are needed)
- Get a specific assessment result information (the specific assessment result *id* is needed)
- Get all the added assessment result *ids* associated to this *Orchestrator*

- Check the validity of the hash for a specific evidence (the specific evidence id and the evidence hash are needed)
- Check the validity of the hash for a specific assessment result (the specific assessment result id and the assessment result hash are needed)
- Check the validity of the hash for a specific assessment compliance result (the specific assessment result id and the assessment compliance result hash are needed).

```

address id;
address owner;
uint256 creationTimestamp;

uint256[] evidencesIds;
struct Evid {
    uint256 id;
    bytes32 valueHash;
    uint256 toolId;
    uint256 resourceId;
    uint256 cspId;
    uint256 timestamp;
}
mapping(uint256 => Evid) public evid;

uint256[] assessmentsIds;
struct Assess {
    uint256 id;
    bytes32 securityAssessmentHash;
    bytes32 complianceHash;
    uint256[] associatedEvidencesId;
    uint256 metricId;
    uint256 timestamp;
}
mapping(uint256 => Assess) public assess;
    
```

Figure 12. MEDINA Trustworthiness Management System data model

If they are not authorized users, they will not be able to use the system as it is restricted by the Smart Contracts design.

Administrators are responsible for authorizing the *Orchestrators'* owners to use the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*. For this purpose, *Orchestrators'* owners need to make a "registration request" to notify the administrators that they want to use the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*. This notification includes the user identifier (Blockchain address) and a contact email to be replied. Once the notification is received by the administrators, they manually analyse whether the *Orchestrator* owner should be authorized or not. If yes, the authorized *Orchestrator* owner will receive feedback by email with the username and password needed to access the Blockchain viewer client.

Events generation

Every time an operation is executed in the Smart Contract, a Blockchain based event is generated to feed the Blockchain monitor. The Blockchain based events to be generated include (but are not limited to):

- A new administrator is registered
- An existing administrator is removed
- A new *Orchestrator* owner is authorized to use the system
- An existing *Orchestrator* owner is de-authorized to use the system
- A new *Orchestrator* is registered by its *Orchestrator* owner
- New evidence information is provided
- New assessment result information is provided

4.2.2.3 Blockchain client

The *Orchestrators* need the Blockchain client to interact with the Blockchain network in general, and with the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* functionalities implemented by means of Smart Contracts, in particular. For this purpose, the main functionalities of the Blockchain client are as follows.

Blockchain account management

Every authorized *Orchestrator* owner interacting with the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* requires a Blockchain account. The account is formed by a Blockchain address, which clearly identifies the user inside the Blockchain network (in fact, it will be considered as the *Orchestrator* owner id in the system because it is unique), and an associated private key, only known by the *Orchestrator* owner (it should be securely kept). The Blockchain account is usually managed by means of a “wallet” included as part of the Blockchain client implemented in MEDINA in order to make users’ interaction with the Blockchain network easier (and transparent of any Blockchain dependency).

In this context, the functionalities available in the Blockchain client related to the Blockchain accounts are:

- Create a new Blockchain account. A new address and its associated private key are automatically generated
- Get the address associated to a specific private key (for validation purposes)
- Add a specific Blockchain account to the Blockchain client wallet (the private key is needed). Only one account can be added to the wallet in MEDINA (this is a limitation defined for MEDINA)
- Get the Blockchain address added to the wallet (for validation purposes). The Blockchain address previously added to the system Blockchain wallet is obtained
- Ask the administrators for authorization of a specific Blockchain address (associated to a specific *Orchestrator* owner) to use the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*.

Blockchain transactions creation

Orchestrators need to generate Blockchain transactions in order to send them to the Blockchain and be understood by the Smart Contracts deployed on the Blockchain. The Blockchain client automatically creates the required Blockchain transaction for executing (calling) all the functionalities available in the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* Smart Contracts. For this purpose, the Blockchain client internally uses the Web3.js library⁸.

API REST for external interaction

The Blockchain component exposes an API REST in order to allow the *MEDINA Orchestrators* to easily interact with the Blockchain client for the functionalities previously described.

Figure 13 shows the different endpoints available on the API through Swagger. For more details on the API, please refer to *Appendix C: MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System API description*.

⁸ <https://web3js.readthedocs.io/en/v1.5.2/>

Figure 13. POSTMAN collection for validating Blockchain client API

4.2.2.4 Blockchain viewer

The Blockchain viewer listens to Blockchain based events generated by the Smart Contracts, notifying about new administrators and *Orchestrators'* owners in the system, as well as new evidence or assessment results recorded in the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*. It provides a mechanism for external users (for example, external auditors, external security engineers, etc.) to verify evidence/assessment results recorded in the Blockchain. Figure 14 shows the internal architecture of the Blockchain viewer.

Figure 14. Blockchain viewer architecture (source: MEDINA’s own contribution)

The Blockchain viewer is composed of four main elements:

- **Eventum** [23]. It is the component which bridges the Smart Contracts deployed in the Blockchain network with the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* functionality and the Blockchain Viewer. As it has been explained before, the Smart Contracts automatically generate Blockchain events that will be listened by Eventum. Eventum will then use Kafka for transmitting them to Logstash. For listening to the events, it is necessary to be subscribed to events from the specific Smart Contract addresses (every Smart Contract has a Blockchain address, which identifies itself in the Blockchain). In addition, the format of the specific events must be also indicated to Eventum (event id, event parameters order, event parameters type).
- **Apache Kafka** [24]. It is the intermediate platform used to distribute Blockchain events between Eventum and Logstash. Kafka uses message queues to provide an

asynchronous communications way; this means that the sender (Eventum) and the receiver (Logstash) of the message do not need to interact with the message queue at the same time.

- **Logstash** [25]. It is a log management tool used in the Blockchain viewer for collecting all the events received from Eventum using Kafka queues and normalising them in a common format before routing them again to Elasticsearch to be processed.
- **Elasticsearch** [26]. It is a distributed search and analysis engine, which allows to store, index and process information. It receives Blockchain events data from the Logstash service and categorize it in four different categories: users, *Orchestrators*, evidence, and assessment results. The information stored in Elasticsearch can be recreated from scratch at any time in case of a security incident resulting in a fully reliable source of information. Elasticsearch exposes an API REST for accessing the information.

4.2.2.5 Blockchain viewer client

There could be several options to consume data from the Blockchain viewer. However, **Kibana** [27] has been considered the best option due to its high compatibility with Elasticsearch as well as the large number of graphical capabilities that it offers, which would highly improve the usability of the system. Kibana is a graphical interface which displays the information from Elasticsearch in real time and through customised dashboards.

Authentication is required for accessing Kibana dashboards; in addition, different roles have been created for accessing different kind of information in the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*: administrators (“TECNALIA” in MEDINA) have access to all the registered evidence and assessment results from different *Orchestrators*. However, each authorized *Orchestrator* has a limited access to just its associated evidence and assessment results in order to avoid information disclosure.

For this purpose, Kibana provides three security features [28]:

- Spaces, allowing the definition of different “tenants” for each user.
- Roles, allowing the definition of different privileges (different spaces access, for example).
- Users, associated to a specific role (and, consequently, a specific space). In MEDINA, there is an administrator user and one user for each *Orchestrator* (or MEDINA deployed instance).

Figure 15 shows the main dashboard for administrators, where a list of the different authorized *Orchestrator* owners appears with a link (shown in blue) to their associated dashboards. Additionally, a summary of the total number of administrators, authorized *Orchestrators’* owners, registered *Orchestrators*, registered evidence, and registered assessment results in the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* is shown. Finally, different filters have been included for improving the usability of the system: filter by role (administrator or *Orchestrator* owner) or filter directly by *Orchestrator* owner id.

Figure 16 shows the main dashboard for each *Orchestrator* owner. Here, the complete list of registered evidence (evidence hashes) and assessment results (assessment result hashes) is shown. Additionally, a summary of the total number of registered evidence and assessment results for the specific *Orchestrator* owner is shown. Finally different filters have been included for improving the usability of the system: filter by id, hash or associated metadata on the evidence and assessment results.

Figure 15. Blockchain viewer graphical interface for administrators

MEDINA Trustworthiness System

Number of evidences

8,724

Number of assessment results

11,608

Look for specific:

Evidence Id

Evidence Hash

Resource id

Tool id

CSP id

Registered evidences

Date per day	timestamp	Evidence id	Resource id	Tool id	CSP id	Hash
2022-06-08	1654671937700244148	656de3e8-e6f9-11ec-b2af-7ad8dc460020	dummyAgent1	evidence-collector-v0.0.16	N/A	%D1UE%7F%17%99%D6%17%B4%B5%95ae7%E...
2022-06-08	1654671886637785398	a0a7e16a-8908-4b22-bd8a-695f6dc53454	/subscriptions/a77071d2-0679-45be-a62e-d3ca3...	Cloudfitor Evidences Collection	N/A	%EE%OD%CE%F50z%D7%C6%AFz%88%F5P3qX%...
2022-06-08	165467188659060307	b615235f-c26a-4365-99a4-df8e9a0199a7	/subscriptions/a77071d2-0679-45be-a62e-d3ca3...	Cloudfitor Evidences Collection	N/A	%2Z%E7%BE%E6%5EB%E4%85%09%83n%B6%92...
2022-06-08	1654671885568955866	ed64ce74-a09b-4dda-809c-9a9828a19e50	/subscriptions/a77071d2-0679-45be-a62e-d3ca3...	Cloudfitor Evidences Collection	N/A	%BC%E2%B3-%5C%E7%BB%A7%AB%ED%85%K7...
2022-06-08	1654671882491620736	6e80c8ba-e01d-4c83-b38c-434a26463b4b	/subscriptions/a77071d2-0679-45be-a62e-d3ca3...	Cloudfitor Evidences Collection	N/A	%2AJZ%A0%8C5%AE%00%03%DF%D6%FDh VT%...
2022-06-08	1654671881466870696	47feb59b-520f-4305-ab02-87fe3ab2ce73	/subscriptions/a77071d2-0679-45be-a62e-d3ca3...	Cloudfitor Evidences Collection	N/A	%D1%16%C4%3B%A5%AA%40f2M%C1%05Bt...

Filter Assessment Results. Look for a specific:

Assessment Result id

Metric id

Assessment Result Hash

Compliance Hash

Registered Assessment Results

Date per day	timestamp	Assessment id	Metric id	Assessment Hash	Compliance Hash	Associated evidences
2022-06-08	1654668891013171204	4d8497fe-f0eb-4cb7-a4c3-fce8335d266b	TransportEncryptionEnabled	%C9%B1%CD3%3F%F4_%F7%8FU%3D%22%DC4I...	%15%ESIY%B6%A0-%402%BF%EB%DO%D3%BA%...	3abcc72-4ee8-4a29-83a0-3030e19766db
2022-06-08	1654668898986093958	cf336530-d113-4866-94de-7e0e3c6c9c75	TLSVersion	kb%E3%27%E7%FA%3D%14u%FA%E2%FDh%C3...	%15%ESIY%B6%A0-%402%BF%EB%DO%D3%BA%...	3abcc72-4ee8-4a29-83a0-3030e19766db

Figure 16. Blockchain viewer graphical interface for Orchestrator owners

4.2.3 Technical specifications

Table 5 shows the main technical specifications about the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*.

Table 5. *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System technical specification*

DEVELOPMENT	
Type	Software
Operating Systems	Windows or Linux
Databases	Blockchain (Quorum) and MongoDB
GUI	Through Kibana
Programming language	Go, Solidity, JavaScript, Scripting
Development Environment	Solidity, Elastic Stack
INSTALLATION AND DEPLOYMENT	
Software Requirements	Docker engine and its supporting packages
Hardware Requirements	Hardware virtualization support
Containerization	Docker
Communications	Secure HTTP (HTTPS)
EXECUTION	
Execution Time	It depends on the network stability
Execution Frequency	Asynchronous

4.3 Delivery and usage

4.3.1 Package information

Only the Blockchain client needs to be provided, as the rest of the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* components are provided as a service from TECNALIA's premises. The Blockchain client is packaged as a docker image.

4.3.2 Installation instructions

Only the Blockchain client needs to be installed, as the rest of the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* components are provided as a service from TECNALIA 's premises.

The installation process (from the *Orchestrator*) is as follows:

- `sudo docker login optima-medina-docker-dev.artifact.tecnalia.com` (and enter your username and password; registration in Orein is needed in advance)
- `sudo docker pull optima-medina-docker-dev.artifact.tecnalia.com/wp3/t35/blockchain:latest`
- `sudo docker run -d -p 8001:8001 -name medina_blockchain optima-medina-docker-dev.artifact.tecnalia.com/wp3/t35/blockchain:latest`

4.3.3 User Manual

The *Orchestrator* is the component which needs to use the Blockchain client to provide evidence and assessment results to the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*. Once

the docker image is running (after following installation steps in section 4.3.2), the *Orchestrator* needs the following:

1. A Blockchain account needs to be generated and added to the Blockchain wallet (inside the Blockchain client) for each *Orchestrator* owner through a POST to the `/client/account` endpoint and a POST to the `/client/wallet` endpoint of the Blockchain client API.
2. Request Authorization of the *Orchestrator* owner in the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* through a POST to the `/client/registration` endpoint of the Blockchain client API. This way, TECNALIA will automatically receive an email with the Blockchain id (account) to be authorized in the system. TECNALIA will manually authorize the Blockchain account (*Orchestrator* owner) and will generate the credentials needed for accessing the Blockchain viewer (user and password).
3. Once the *Orchestrator* owner is authorized, the *Orchestrator*, as technical component, needs to be registered in the system through a POST to the `/client/orchestrator` endpoint. From this moment, all the authorized *Orchestrator* owners' functionalities from the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* can be executed. Refer to *Appendix C: MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System API description* to see the available functionalities: provide evidence or assessment results; get the list of registered evidences or assessment results ids; get the information of a specific evidence or assessment result id; check the hashes of a specific evidence or assessment result.
4. Additionally, the API also includes additional endpoints for admin purposes, as TECNALIA (as administrator) could make *Orchestrator* owners administrators of the system, if needed.

In addition, the correct sequence of steps for testing and validating all the functionalities from the web-based Blockchain viewer client (Kibana) is as follows:

1. Login in the system is required (only authenticated users can access the dashboard) (<https://medina.bclab.dev>; [internal use only - authentication is required])
2. The main dashboard associated to the specific user is automatically displayed. Here, the list of evidence or assessment results can be consulted, or filters can be applied as needed.

4.3.4 Licensing information

Proprietary. Copyright by TECNALIA.

4.3.5 Download

This section is currently not applicable. All the components of the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* are provided as a service from TECNALIA and TECNALIA will own a proprietary license, so no source code will be provided.

5 Checklist for the Self-assessment of EUCS security requirements

In response to Article 54 recital (g) of the EUCSA [29] which states that “A European cybersecurity certification scheme shall include at least the following elements [...] (g) the specific evaluation criteria and methods to be used, including types of evaluation, in order to demonstrate that the security objectives referred to in Article 51 are achieved;” EUCS [30] has defined an evidence-based assessment approach that is to be used solely for the basic level of assurance.

The proposed evidence-based conformity assessment approach states that the evaluation does not require a “full-fledged audit of the cloud service to be certified” [30] but it is more oriented towards “facilitating a controlled environment for providing limited assurance while keeping the associated cost for certification affordable for smaller CSP’s” [30] and follows a checklist-oriented approach.

The process to be followed is similar to the one a CSP would need to follow in order to get certified, in which it would need to create the application request, define the scope of certification, create the audit plan, execute the assessment procedures, analyse the results, issue the assurance report, review the evaluation, and obtain the certification.

The difference here is that in the basic level of assurance, the CSP itself, and not an external or third-party auditor, creates and carries out the audit plan and executes the assessment procedures, also analysing the results, who are sent to the CAB for further analysis and audits. Figure 17 shows a simplified version of this process.

Figure 17. Evidence-based conformity assessment (adapted from [30])

Hence, the challenge here is: how to guide CSPs, especially smaller ones, in this evidence-based conformity assessment methodology? In fact, checklists could be not yet available, or they need to be complemented. (e.g., they do not show examples of evidence that can be delivered and can be considered valid to demonstrate the compliance of a requirement).

The goal of the checklist elaborated in MEDINA (a.k.a. “MEDINA Questionnaires”) is therefore to develop an assessment model for requirements in the basic level of assurance that can be understood by less experienced compliance managers and CSPs in general. However, CABs and auditors could also adopt it as guidance.

MEDINA Questionnaires are based on the experience of the auditors and consultants that have worked in the checklist, with feedback incorporated from the CSPs that participated in MEDINA, as well as from literature. The questions are extracted directly from the EUCS requirements themselves. They have been split for understandability reasons into multiple questions, that is, from one requirement multiple questions have been created. However, the number of overall questions is important as this self-assessment model must not be very heavy and difficult to use.

The first version of the MEDINA Questionnaires was released in D3.1 [4]. The checklists were composed of 532 questions, that were related to the 220 basic assurance level requirements defined in the draft candidate EUCS version published in December 2020 [30].

In this second version of the MEDINA Questionnaires -here reported- the number of questions as well as the formulation have evolved. We have reviewed and updated the questions and evidence with respect to those requirements defined, first in the basic level of assurance of the candidate EUCS November 2021 and second in the basic level of assurance of the draft candidate version of the EUCS scheme August 2022 [3]. Besides, we have also created checklists for the substantial and high level of assurance requirements. Table 6 shows the current number of requirements in the draft candidate version of the EUCS scheme August 2022 and the number questions elicited for each level of assurance (basic, substantial, and high).

Table 6. Coverage of EUCS requirements by the MEDINA Questionnaires

	Number of EUCS requirements [3]	Number of elicited questions in MEDINA Questionnaires
Basic level of assurance	220	497
Substantial level of assurance	129	346
High level of assurance	77	166

In addition to the questions, a very important aspect that needs to be considered in the MEDINA Questionnaires is evidence. ISO 9000 defines evidence as the data supporting the existence or verity of something [31]. In MEDINA, two types of evidence are distinguished:

- **Technical evidence:** data that supports the compliance of a technical requirement or measure. Examples: protocol version, password length.
- **Organizational evidence:** data that supports the compliance of an organizational requirement. Example: existence of a policy and/or procedure document.

Hence, the MEDINA Questionnaires identify some examples of evidence that the CSP shall submit to the CAB for the evaluation assessment. The evidence examples shown are not meant to be an exhaustive list but just a guidance.

The main target users of the MEDINA Questionnaires are small CSPs. However, auditors and CABs could also benefit from it.

Figure 18 shows a summary of the EUCS categories managed by the MEDINA Questionnaires and Figure 19 shows an excerpt of the checklist for the Operational Security category.

MEDINA
MEDINA Questionnaires

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EUCS Controls - SECURITY OBJECTIVES AND REQUIREMENTS FOR CLOUD SERVICES

- ▶ A1. Organizational Information Security
- ▶ A2. Information Security Policies
- ▶ A3. Risk Management
- ▶ A4. Human Resources
- ▶ A5. Asset Management
- ▶ A6. Physical Security
- ▶ A7. Operational Security
- ▶ A8. Identity, Authentication and Access Control Mgmt
- ▶ A9. Cryptography and Key Management
- ▶ A10. Communication Security
- ▶ A11. Portability and Interoperability
- ▶ A12. Change and Configuration Management
- ▶ A13. Development of Information Systems
- ▶ A14. Procurement Management
- ▶ A15. Incident Management
- ▶ A16. Business Continuity
- ▶ A17. Compliance
- ▶ A18. User Documentation
- ▶ A19. Dealing with Investigation Requests from Government Agencies
- ▶ A20. Product Safety and Security

Figure 18. Summary of the EUCS categories in the MEDINA Questionnaires

A7. Operational Security															
Obj	Category	Objective	Control in	Control	Control objective	ReqID	Requirement	Lev	Question	Statement/Questions	Val	Expected Evidence	Guid		
A7	Operational security	Ensure proper and regular operation, including appropriate measures for planning and monitoring capacity, protection against malware, logging and monitoring events, and dealing with vulnerabilities, malfunctions and failures	OPS-01	CAPACITY MANAGEMENT - PLANNING	The capacities of critical resources such as personnel and IT resources are planned in order to avoid possible capacity bottlenecks.	OPS-01.1B	The CSP shall document and implement procedures to plan for capacities and resources (personnel and IT resources), which shall include forecasting future	Basic	Q1-OPS-01.1B	Does the CSP document procedures to plan for capacities and resources (personnel and IT resources)?	50	- Capacity plan - Specific capacity procedures			
								Basic	Q2-OPS-01.1B	Do procedures include forecasting future capacity requirements in order to identify usage trends and manage system overload?	50	- Capacity plan (encompasses future capacity requirements) - Specific capacity procedures			
								Basic	Q3-OPS-01.1B	Does the CSP implement procedures to plan for capacities and resources (personnel and IT resources)?	100	- Capacity plan audit			
								OPS-01.2B	The CSP shall meet the requirements included in contractual agreements with cloud customers regarding the provision of the cloud service in case of capacity bottlenecks or personnel and IT resources	Basic	Q1-OPS-01.2B	Does the CSP meet the requirements included in contractual agreements with cloud customers regarding the provision of the cloud service in case of capacity bottlenecks?	50	- Monitoring reports - contractual agreements - Non-conformities to the contract (if there are non-compliances)	
								Basic	Q2-OPS-01.2B	Does the CSP meet the requirements included in contractual agreements with cloud customers regarding the provision of the cloud service in case of IT resources outages?	NA	- Monitoring reports - Non-conformities to the contract/SLA (if there are non-compliances)			
					OPS-01.3	The capacity projections shall be considered in accordance with the service	High			50					
					OPS-02	CAPACITY MANAGEMENT - MONITORING	The capacities of critical resources such as personnel and IT resources are monitored.	OPS-02.1B	The CSP shall define and implement technical and organizational safeguards for the monitoring of provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services to ensure compliance with the service level agreement	Basic	Q1-OPS-02.1B	Does the CSP define technical safeguards for the monitoring of provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services to ensure compliance with the service level agreement?	50	- Multidimensional QoS prediction methods	
								Basic	Q2-OPS-02.1B	Does the CSP implement technical safeguards for the monitoring of provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services to ensure compliance with the service level agreement?	50	- Service level agreement - SLA compliance report			
								Basic	Q3-OPS-02.1B	Does the CSP define organizational safeguards for the monitoring of provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services to ensure compliance with the service level agreement?	100	- Multi-dimensional QoS measures			
								Basic	Q4-OPS-02.1B	Does the CSP implement organizational safeguards for the monitoring of provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services to ensure compliance with the service level agreement?	50	- Service level agreement - SLA compliance report			
		OPS-02.2	The CSP shall make available to the cloud customer the relevant information regarding	High						50					

Figure 19. Excerpt of the checklist for the Operational Security category

MEDINA Questionnaires also provide some scorecards per category that show the level of assessment of the security controls in that category. To implement scorecards, users are requested to indicate the level of fulfilment for each question between the available options (100%, 50%, 0%, N.A.) (see Figure 19).

Figure 20 shows the scorecards for the self-assessment of the controls in the Operational Security category. We have created scorecards for each assurance level (basic, substantial, and high) and an overall scorecard showing a comparison of achievements at each level.

Figure 20. Scorecards for the Operational Security category in MEDINA Questionnaires

Figure 21 shows an overall scorecard showing the results of the self-assessment for the basic level of assurance for each of the EUCS categories.

Figure 21. Overall scorecard in MEDINA Questionnaires

Checklists with questions for the requirements of the basic, substantial, and high levels of assurance are currently being integrated in the MEDINA Catalogue of Controls and Metrics, and will be reported in D2.2 [32] (due at M27).

Checklist with the questions for basic assurance level requirements is presented in *Appendix E: Self-assessment questionnaires for EUCS basic requirements* under a tabular form with the following structure:

- **ControlID:** id of the EUCS control coming from the draft candidate version of the EUCS scheme August 2022 [3].
- **Control:** description of the control coming from the draft candidate version of the EUCS scheme August 2022 [3].
- **ReqID:** id of the requirement coming from the draft candidate version of the EUCS scheme August 2022 [3].
- **Requirement:** description of the requirement coming from the draft candidate version of the EUCS scheme August 2022 [3].
- **Question ID:** unique identified of each question, related to each requirement.
- **Statement / Question:** question that the CSP should answer in the evaluation to comply with the requirement as requested in the scheme.
- **Evidence:** the document, section of a document, or any kind of information that the CSP is required to provide in order to prove that the requirement is properly implemented in accordance with what it is required. The list provided is not meant to be exhaustive but rather an indication of what kind of information is expected to be provided.

6 Conclusions

This document presents the architecture of the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools* [KR4], which comprises the integration of *Clouditor*, *Codyze*, *Wazuh*, the *Vulnerability Assessment tool (VAT)*, the *Assessment and Management of Organisational Evidence (AMOE)*, the *Generic Evidence Collector (GEC)* and the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*, that aims at ensuring that all evidence and assessment results are secured. This is done by means of smart contracts.

The deliverable starts by introducing the updated architecture, data model and sequence diagrams of the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools*, extending the models and explanations already presented in D5.2 [1].

The document then deepens into the main ideas and motivation for the further development of the tools that comprise the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools*, even if the technical details of the implementation are provided in D3.5 [2]. As a next step, and in order to plan these further developments, the coverage of the requirements of assurance level high coming from the draft candidate version of the EUCS scheme August 2022 [3] has been matched with the different tools comprising the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools*. Please note that the EUCS requirements referred in this deliverable correspond to a draft version of the ENISA catalogue and are not intended for being used outside the context of MEDINA.

Further, the updated functional and technical details of the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*, how it fits into MEDINA, the architecture of the prototype, the description of the prototype and how it is delivered has also been presented. The system is based on smart contracts and is currently deployed on a Blockchain network in TECNALIA.

Finally, and even if MEDINA focuses mostly on the automated monitoring and the high assurance level of the EUCS, CSPs may struggle in the basic level, especially smaller ones. The checklist explained and updated in Section 5 and presented in *Appendix E: Self-assessment questionnaires for EUCS basic requirements* is aimed at these small CSPs so that they are guided in their self – assessment activities and can know which kind of evidence they are to provide to the CABs when doing the third-party assessment.

Future versions of this document will include updated versions of the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* with new functionalities, as well as updates of the MEDINA Questionnaires for EUCS presented in Section 5.

7 References

- [1] MEDINA Consortium, “D5.2-MEDINA Requirements, Detailed architecture, DevOps infrastructure and CI/CD and verification strategy-v2,” 2022.
- [2] MEDINA Consortium, “D3.5 Tools and techniques for collecting evidence of technical and organisational measures - v2,” 2022.
- [3] ENISA, “EUCS – Cloud Services Scheme,” Draft version provided by ENISA (August 2022) - not intended for being used outside the context of MEDINA, 2022.
- [4] MEDINA Consortium, “D3.1 Tools and techniques for the management of trustworthy evidence-v1,” 2021.
- [5] MEDINA Consortium, “D5.1 MEDINA Requirements, Detailed architecture, DevOps infrastructure and CI/CD and verification strategy-v1,” 2021.
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Appendix A: Current state of practice in tools and techniques in management of evidence

1. Assessment of security performance configuration of cloud workloads

Cloud environments are fast-changing and can become vulnerable to attacks if not configured correctly. These configuration changes may be hard to detect and include manual configuration changes as well as configuration changes based on upgrades. According to a study [33] about the top threats to cloud computing by the Cloud Security Alliance (CSA) from 2020, two of the top threats to cloud services are misconfiguration and inadequate change control (Top 2) as well as insecure interfaces and APIs (Top 7).

Cloud configuration checking tools can be used to detect these misconfigurations. According to a further study of the CSA from 2021 regarding the state of cloud security both Cloud Provider tools and third-party tools for configuration checking are used about equally often [34]. Furthermore, the study also states that the dominant public cloud platforms in the market are Microsoft Azure, Amazon Web Services and Google Cloud Platform.

Various approaches, architectures, and implementation for cloud security monitoring have been proposed in the last decade. For example, GMonE [35] was one of the first general-purpose cloud monitoring systems. A more recent approach has been proposed by Torkura et al. [36]. They combine cloud monitoring with state transition analysis to build a continuous threat assessment tool for multi-cloud systems. Similar to *Clouditor* [9], this tool, called CSBAuditor [37], uses Cloud APIs to discover existing resources. The results are then compared to the resources' expected states, i.e., via state transition analysis. It also further analyses the results using a dedicated risk analysis component. In comparison to *Clouditor*, however, it does not implement an ontology-based discovery. While this approach is a compact concept and implementation of a multi-cloud auditing tool, MEDINA rather aims at building a modular framework that automates parts of the certification process, e.g., of the EUCS. Since CSBAuditor implements some of the features that are needed in the MEDINA framework, e.g., cloud resource discovery, it could in parts be adapted to fit the MEDINA design requirements (e.g., APIs).

Cloud-Native Configuration Monitoring

Azure Security Center and Azure Policies

The cloud computing service of Microsoft Azure provides the *Azure Security Center*⁹ allowing to monitor various resources deployed within the cloud. One way to improve the monitoring is to use *Azure Policy*¹⁰ which is a service that lets users create policies. Using these policies helps to comply with the imposed regulations of the company. They can be used to deny the deployment of resources beforehand or give alerts (e.g., in the *Azure Security Center*) about the current state of the deployed resources. There is the option to use pre-built policies or to produce customized policies depending on the specific needs of the respective user.

Although the *Security Center* accompanied with *Azure Policies* provides a good and visualized presentation of the current state of the cloud environment, there are two downsides using this approach. First, the capabilities to monitor resources depend on the expressiveness and scope

⁹ <https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/security-center/security-center-introduction>

¹⁰ <https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/governance/policy/overview>

of the *Azure Policy* language. The main limitation of using Azure’s monitoring services, however, is to be tied to Azure. A multi-cloud monitoring approach is not possible using Azure’s service exclusively.

By exploiting the respective CSP APIs, *Clouditor* leverages the maximum potential to access information about cloud resources and the ability to monitor multiple cloud services simultaneously – based on the ontology used in MEDINA.

AWS Config, Security Hub

Similar to Azure, Amazon Web Services (AWS) provides its own services for monitoring AWS’ resources as well. Two options for checking the state of deployed resources are *AWS Config*¹¹ and the *AWS Security Hub*¹². The same limitations as for *Azure* arise here: being tied to expressiveness of these services and limited to resources of AWS. In addition, the service *AWS Config* cannot be used for free.

As accessing the CSP via its offered APIs is free of charge and the *Clouditor* is offered as an open-source tool under the Apache 2.0 license, the *Clouditor* can be freely used, modified, and distributed under the terms of the license. In addition, the advantages of using *Clouditor* for *Azure* apply.

Commercial tools

There are also commercial tools for monitoring the configurations of one or more cloud computing services. One example is Prisma Cloud [38], a multi-cloud solution for continuous monitoring of cloud configurations. However, such tools are mostly costly and not open source. Since they are not open source, they lack flexibility in use and therefore cannot be easily integrated into a framework like MEDINA.

Secureframe¹³ is a commercial offering that promises continuous compliance with various standards, including ISO 27001 and GDPR (but not the EUCS). It also offers integration to several cloud platforms, such as AWS and Google Cloud. It is, however, unclear to which extent Secureframe automatically covers the standards’ requirements and how its architecture is designed.

Standardized template export

Another way to discover resource configurations is to leverage the APIs for exporting an IaC (Infrastructure-as-Code) template. It allows to retrieve templates for resources deployed in the cloud service. Such a template provides a comprehensive view about the configuration of the respective cloud resource. In addition to the more holistic discovering provided with the general APIs of the respective cloud service providers, we foresee to implement the discovery via these IaC APIs as well, to obtain a quick overview of the cloud resources’ configuration. The export is possible in both Azure and AWS.

Another approach that aims at standardizing evidence gathering from cloud workloads has been proposed by Knoblauch and Banse [39]. They propose a standardized audit API that can be queried by the evidence gathering tool in any system, but which moves the implementation effort

¹¹ <https://aws.amazon.com/es/config/>

¹² https://aws.amazon.com/security-hub/?nc1=h_ls

¹³ <https://secureframe.com/>

to the cloud provider and/or the cloud service provider: either the API responses have to be implemented by the service provider or the cloud provider needs to adopt them. This proposal is therefore better suited in customized systems rather than standard cloud systems.

2. Security assessment of computing infrastructure

This section describes the state of the art of tools used for assessing the security of infrastructural elements such as (virtual) machines and networks. Two types of tools are presented: tools for proactively detecting vulnerabilities (vulnerability assessment) and tools for reactively detecting breaches (intrusion detection). In the scope of MEDINA, these tools are used to obtain evidence about fulfilment of specific requirements by monitoring the state of infrastructure's security, or offered to be used by CSPs to satisfy certain requirements and communicate the fulfilment of these requirements to MEDINA.

Vulnerability assessment

Vulnerability assessment comprises identifying, quantifying, and ranking potential vulnerabilities in computer systems, networks, and applications, and is a critical component of vulnerability and risk management in any company. Vulnerability scanners are automated tools that can aid in the process of identifying vulnerabilities, by checking for security weaknesses or abnormalities in the networks, systems, or applications. Based on the scope of their scanning targets, they are classified as network-based, host-based, wireless, application, and database scanners [40], where a single tool with multiple capabilities (e.g. Nmap [13]) can fall into more than one category. Application vulnerability scanners are further divided into two groups depending on their testing method. Dynamic application security testing (DAST) tools test software in its operational state by using the provided interfaces of running programs to insert specially crafted test inputs, intended to verify the correctness of the program's responses and find error patterns that could indicate security vulnerabilities. DAST scanners do not require application's source code or other data about the software internal operation (black-box testing). On the other hand, static application security testing (SAST) scanners analyse the software's source code and do not require the tested application to be in a running state.

Among the most used DAST tools are web application vulnerability scanners that scan websites for vulnerabilities such as cross-site scripting (XSS), SQL injection, path traversal, and various insecure server configuration errors. Examples of such tools include AppSpider [41], Burp Suite [42], Nessus [43], Qualys [44] (offered as a service), and open-source tools: OpenVAS [45], Arachni [46], OWASP ZAP [12], and w3af [11]. Beside the general web application scanners, other DAST tools focus on specific vulnerabilities: sqlmap [47] (detecting SQL vulnerabilities) and XXSer [48] (cross-site scripting). DAST scanning tools can be used manually in penetration testing or in an automated way, where the results are later examined by an expert. A comprehensive list of DAST scanners is provided by OWASP [49].

Vulnerability Assessment Tools included in MEDINA (described in Section 3.3) combine multiple open-source DAST scanners in a scanning automation framework in order to extend the scope of scanning and enable scheduling of automated scans, alerting, and basic vulnerability management.

Intrusion detection

Intrusion Detection Systems (IDSs) are software applications that can detect and analyse active attacks or threats in the monitored infrastructure. Depending on the scope of monitoring, IDSs can monitor a single machine, its configurations, files, and applications (host-based IDS, HIDS), or analyse traffic on a network to detect anomalous activity or attacks (network-based IDS,

NIDS). Based on the detection technique used, IDSs are grouped into signature-based and anomaly-based. Signature-based IDSs use databases of known attacks or malware patterns and simply look for matches in files or traffic they monitor. Anomaly-based IDSs on the other hand use models, built by monitoring the normal system operation and identify anomalies based on deviations from the normal operation. These are more sophisticated and normally use machine learning methods to train their models and classify application logs, behavioural features, files, or network streams into either normal or potentially harmful (malicious). Because host-based IDSs rely on detecting anomalous behaviour, they can also detect new types of threats, while signature-based IDSs are typically more accurate at detecting known threats, but are incapable of detecting previously unseen malware or new types of attacks (0-days) due to their different fingerprints (patterns).

Recent research in intrusion detection methods focuses on improving the machine learning methods for anomaly based IDSs. Various system-level data is utilized to profile the normal system behaviour and detect abnormalities using supervised or unsupervised machine-learning approaches [50]. Some techniques in research focus on specific attack classification (e.g., denial-of-service attacks) [51] while others are devoted to detection of anomalous traffic without classifying the type of attacks [52].

In order to extend the effectiveness of an intrusion detection system, its detection functionality can be combined or integrated with inspectors and actuators. While the detector is capable of detecting anomalies or threats, inspector software enables review of generated alerts by experts, and actuators can (automatically) perform actions to change the system configuration in order to avoid (further) damage by the detected threat. Multi-module solutions that integrate capabilities of sensors, detectors, inspectors, and actuators exist as well, solutions with the widest capabilities are typically Security Information and Event Management systems (SIEMs) [53].

Two examples of popular IDS tools are Snort [54] and Suricata [55], both signature-based network IDSs. Suricata, the more modern of the pair, supports hardware-accelerated high-bandwidth network captures and decoding of application layer data. Zeek [56] (previously known as Bro-IDS) is a network IDS with prevention capabilities that beside pattern-matching also offers some anomaly detection functionalities with the help of its powerful scripting language. Concerning host-based IDSs, one of the most popular open-source tools is OSSEC [57]. It runs on all major operating systems and consists of a server – agent architecture, where agents (lightweight components installed on monitored hosts) deliver information about detected events to the server that manages the agents. Detection capabilities of OSSEC include file integrity monitoring, collection and analysis of application and system logs, rootkit detection, as well as integration with anti-malware software and APIs (e.g., VirusTotal [58]). *Wazuh*, also used in MEDINA, is another open-source HIDS that is based on OSSEC, but includes additional functionalities, especially regarding possible integrations with other software. *Wazuh* is integrated with the ELK stack (storing logs and events into an Elasticsearch [26] database and providing a user-facing UI through Kibana [27]), includes a restful API for management, as well as improved detection capabilities with added rulesets. Detection rulesets also include basic evaluation of compliance with some controls of specific regulations or standards like GDPR and PCI DSS. *Wazuh* can also retrieve certain data about cloud infrastructure through integrations with Amazon AWS and Microsoft Azure clouds.

3. Information of data flows in cloud applications

The security and compliance of cloud applications depend on the secure configuration of interfaces for data exchange and processing of information. Thereby, the full software and application stack must be examined. The security of a cloud application depends equally on the

security of interactions between components as well as vulnerability free implementations in software. For each granularity, tools are available that support developers and cloud application designers in developing secure applications.

On the highest level, a cloud application consists of a set of services that in its entirety provides the functionality of a cloud application. As a complex system composed of multiple components the secure configuration of each component must be ensured. Tools like Terrascan¹⁴, Chef InSpec¹⁵, Snyk¹⁶ or Anchore¹⁷ can identify security problems in Infrastructure as Code specifications. These includes misconfigurations or violations against best practices that increase the chance of having vulnerable cloud applications. Part of these checks are based on descriptions how a secure configuration should look like. These in turn are mapped in some cases onto policies. As a result, they can validate compliance to standards like HIPAA, PCI DSS, NIST and CIS benchmarks.

A second class of tool can check if used components are up to date and free of vulnerability. This class of tools often provides some form of container or VM scanner. It checks if used programs and libraries in a container/VM contain outdated software or software with vulnerabilities. Tools like these are, for example, Grype¹⁸, Clair¹⁹ and Trivy²⁰.

Finally, source code of developed software that is deployed as a component of a cloud application must be developed using secure coding practices. Part of these practices is the use of static security application testing tools. These tools are often included in CI/CD pipelines and scan source code for vulnerable software patterns. Well known tools include products from SonarSource like SonarQube²¹, Flawfinder²², Semgrep²³ or CodeQL²⁴ by GitHub. They often contain rules that identify when certain software patterns represent vulnerabilities or violate best coding practices. They may also include softer rules from software engineering that try to reduce the complexity of source code and enforce documentation. These tools help developers to identify problems in their code and fix them before the code is deployed as a production application.

Codyze belongs to this last class of tools. It scans code and identifies potential pitfalls in the use of software libraries that cause vulnerabilities. However, where most of the previous tools stop the analysis, *Codyze* tries to map low-level code properties to high-level security requirements from control frameworks like ENISA EUCS [30]. Thus, *Codyze* tries to conclude that the presence of some software properties and absence of vulnerability qualifies a software to comply with control frameworks like ENISA EUCS.

¹⁴ <https://www accurics.com/developers/terrascan/>

¹⁵ <https://community.chef.io/tools/chef-inspec>

¹⁶ <https://snyk.io/>

¹⁷ <https://anchore.com/>

¹⁸ <https://github.com/anchore/grype>

¹⁹ <https://github.com/quay/clair>

²⁰ <https://github.com/aquasecurity/trivy>

²¹ <https://www.sonarqube.org/>

²² <https://dwheeler.com/flawfinder/>

²³ <https://semgrep.dev/>

²⁴ <https://codeql.github.com/>

Appendix B: Assessment of Organizational Measures using NLP

Audits, even those carried out at regular intervals, require many hours of time to find a wide variety of evidence documents. According to the knowledge of MEDINA partners, this is particularly noticeable in the area of organisational requirements. These are various types of evidence documents that have to be found by CSPs. This evidence can consist of screenshots, pictures, log files, configurations, or others. Thus, an extensive manual analysis is currently necessary. Because of the wide variety of different problems, there exists almost no automation as far as MEDINA partners know. Moreover, it is difficult to automate the analysis due to the large variety of evidence types.

To fulfil MEDINA's goal of the assessment of organisational measures, the AMOE tool will be used to extract evidence based on metrics from certain documents linked to the organisational measures and process them in a pipeline to prepare them for assessment. The evidence information is to be retrieved from a wide variety of document types. This can be done by separating certain types of documents and then processing them accordingly, for example through natural language processing (NLP) for natural language-based text documents, or through differential analysis, which uses a golden standard, for other documents.

1. Document types and methods

The process involves a wide variety of document types. Such documents can be images, .xlsx, .docx, .md, .txt or even .pdf files. This makes a standardised methodology for the extraction of evidence correspondingly difficult. Different document forms can also occur within these file formats. For example, a Word document can contain tabular text as well as full text. This makes this task even more complex as this structure and context is lost when only the text is considered. Therefore, in order to find a way to extract the evidence, the files must first be divided into categories that can be handled in different ways. Furthermore, document sections need to be handled separately if the structure varies (e.g., text, table, figure, diagrams...).

A selection of requirements from the EUCS marked as organisational within the MEDINA project, can be used as a basis for this task's experiments. For this, it is necessary to create metrics and map them to these organisational requirements. These metrics can be used to design specific queries to extract the audit-relevant information from evidence documents. Some metrics might need specific input from the CSP to make the query complete, which could allow to transform an organisational measure to a technical, assessable measure.

Dataset

Building a dataset to fulfil all requirements of a security scheme is difficult, as every CSP and every service can produce different types of accepted (=compliant) evidence. At the moment of writing this document, this data set is not yet available. Therefore, one of the main first steps of this task is to gather all evidence documents that could be relevant for successfully reaching the compliance status to a security scheme. To get a generic dataset, the documents should reflect the real-world evidence of CSPs. In a joint effort, exemplary documents and the evidence could be provided by Bosch, Fabasoft and Nixu.

Natural language text documents

Text-based evidence will often be provided in the form of .docx documents or .pdf documents containing human-readable text. Here, however, it is often difficult to obtain the required information with classical information extraction and is usually connected with manual searching for the corresponding sentence passages, automated, predefined queries, and queries with a predefined structure. For this reason, it is necessary to try NLP approaches to solve this problem. One such NLP option is a *question answering* [59] system.

A question-answering system is an intelligent system that can answer questions asked on the basis of a natural language text document. There are question-answering systems for the extraction of word phrases (e.g.: BERT-SQUAD [60] [61]) as well as for the prediction of yes/no questions. This system can be tested on the official BERT-SQUAD site of huggingface [62]. Such a system is built, for example, on top of a neural network like Bert [63]. Bert is a neural network that can understand human-readable documents by pre-training large amounts of data. This network was retrained with questions and answers in order to be able to answer questions from a given document.

A question answering system can be used, for example, to investigate the current approach for monitoring the security of office buildings. For this, we need to query the document containing the information that includes how the floors are currently secured. The result would be a corresponding extracted text phrase from the given document. This extraction includes a certain degree of confidence. If the confidence is high enough, the result can be compared with a list of possible results. If the result is present in the list, the metric is fulfilled.

The disadvantage of such a system is that it always tries to find a corresponding answer to a question. For example, to the question: "Where is the Eiffel Tower located?" it would also try to find the most likely answer. If the following input text is used: "Fabasoft has its headquarters in Linz", the network will probably give Linz as the answer.

As it can be seen from this example, the correctness of a neural network cannot be guaranteed. Also, model answers to yes/no questions might not be accurate enough, so further research has to be considered here to determine whether such systems provide high quality output usable for this task. However, the model provides a confidence level, which can be considered before using the output for assessment. The extracted evidence with the respective confidence is passed on to Cluditor for further processing and assessment. Thus, it can be decided there whether a manual check is necessary, or the confidence is sufficient. In this case, the result of the network can be used to speed up the manual testing process.

2. Information extraction from log files

Classical information extraction methods can be used to query for information from log files. Depending on the structure of the log file this can be done using regular expressions (RegEx) or XPath queries or extraction from JSON files. As this is straight forward process, we do not intend to use NLP methods for this type of documents.

3. Difference analysis

One way of checking documents can also be a simple difference comparison. Here, it is necessary that an existing checked and already audited document is available. This checked document can now be compared with a more recent version. If there is no change, or only an irrelevant change, this document does not have to be further approved. Furthermore, the manual review of documents can be facilitated with the help of a difference analysis.

However, in order to be able to carry out such a difference analysis, a distinction must again be made between document types. Furthermore, thresholds have to be researched that determine whether the change is irrelevant and how manual reviews can influence the assessment.

Difference analysis on images

A simple approach here would be to compare the image to predefined (e.g., accepted in a previous audit) evidence image. The difference on pixel level can be calculated. If the difference is 0, the second image is identical to the first and does not have to be checked manually.

However, if a change has been made, a manual check must now be carried out. To simplify this check, the difference analysis can be used to display the change more easily. This can be found by subtracting the first image from the second image. The difference can then be presented to the user as additional information or be highlighted in the original images.

The described approaches will be probably too simple, as different ratios, contrast etc. of images are not considered. Hence, further research should be conducted. However, we do not expect to have a large quantity of evidence images (despite some screenshots). Screenshots or other images could be checked in other ways, as the source document will be some form of a text document, or the image can be OCRed (OCR: Optical Character Recognition) and then treated as such.

Difference analysis on textual documents

If the text content is identical to a document that has already been checked, the document to be compared is automatically compliant. However, if this is not the case, a sentence-level differential analysis could be performed to facilitate a manual review. This will highlight new sentences.

Bytewise Comparison

To compare two generic files, one can resort to a bytewise comparison. Before comparing the two files, the header must not be considered, as this information is usually changed when the file is saved. A bytewise comparison can now be carried out on the remaining data. The difference analysis for manual difference inspection (by human) only makes limited sense, as the difference cannot always be displayed visually in a meaningful way. As this would be a rather low-level approach, we do not expect to provide much to a working prototype, still it is considered here for completeness.

Difference analysis using document features

For this purpose, it is necessary to extract features from these already audited documents that allow similarity comparisons on the document corpus. In order to compare text, it is necessary that an algorithm can remotely “understand” the text. For this, a vectorisation of the text is necessary. Word embeddings or sentence embeddings can be used. Such embeddings can also be generated by neural networks. Semantic similarities are also considered here.

One of the easiest ways to compare images is to use the pixel values as a feature vector. However, it is important to note that the pixels must be contained in the exact same points on the image (resolution, contrast, etc.).

With the extracted features it is now possible to calculate similarity metrics. For example, cosine similarity can be used for this purpose. Cosine Similarity outputs a score between 0 and 1. If the result is 1 both documents are very likely identical. Closer to 0 means that both documents are not very similar.

A limitation can be seen, for example, if a sentence in a bigger original document is changed just slightly. For example: "The floor is alarmed" to "The floor is not alarmed". Semantically, there is a big difference, but the similarity score only changes slightly. To address this problem, one can combine the similarity score with querying.

Appendix C: MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System API description

The Blockchain client to be deployed on the MEDINA *Orchestrator* exposes the following API:

1. Blockchain account Management

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/account>
 - Description: Create a new Blockchain account.
 - Method: POST.
 - Parameters: None.
 - Responses: 200 (OK), 403 (Application error).
 - Output (example):

```
{
  "ad"ress": "0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae"a72"825",
  "pr"va"eKey": "0x4a2ac221aef1a96c7dc13b2e5f552fc55939054a451e2e25131d079b"885b81a"
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/account?privatekey=0x4a2ac221aef1a96c7dc13b2e5f552fc55939054a451e2e25131d079bc885b81a>
 - Description: Get address associated to a private key.
 - Method: GET.
 - Parameters: privatekey.
 - Responses: 200 (OK), 400 (parameter error), 403 (Application error).
 - Output (example):

```
{
  "ad"ress": "0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae"a72"825",
  "pr"va"eKey": "0x4a2ac221aef1a96c7dc13b2e5f552fc55939054a451e2e25131d079bc"885b81a "
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/wallet?privatekey=0x4a2ac221aef1a96c7dc13b2e5f552fc55939054a451e2e25131d079bc885b81a>
 - Description: Add account to wallet.
 - Method: POST.
 - Parameters: privatekey.
 - Responses: 200 (OK), 400 (parameter error), 403 (Application error).
 - Output (example):

```
{
  "s"at"s": "OK",
  "walle"ad"ress": "0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae"a72c825"
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/wallet>
 - Description: Get account added to the wallet.
 - Method: GET.
 - Parameters: None.
 - Responses: 200 (OK), 403 (Application error).
 - Output (example):

```
{
  "s"at"s": "OK",
  "walle"ad"ress": "0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae"a72c825"
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/registration>
 - Description: Authorization request.
 - Method: POST.
 - Parameters: address.
 - Responses: 200 (OK), 400 (parameter error), 403 (Application error).
 - Output (example):

```
{
```

```
    "s"at"s": "OK",  
    "ad"ress": "0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae"a72c825"  
  }  
}
```

2. Blockchain transactions generation: General system management

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/admin?address=0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae3a72c825>
 - Description: Add a new administrator.
 - Method: POST.
 - Parameters: address.
 - Responses: 200 (OK), 400 (parameter error), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
 - Output (example):

```
{  
  "s"at"s": "OK",  
  "walle"ad"ress": "0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae"a72c825"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/admin?address=0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae3a72c825>
 - Description: Remove an existing administrator.
 - Method: DEL.
 - Parameters: address.
 - Responses: 200 (OK), 400 (parameter error), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
 - Output (example):

```
{  
  "s"at"s": "OK",  
  "walle"ad"ress": "0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae"a72c825"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/admin?address=0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae3a72c825>
 - Description: Check if an id is administrator.
 - Method: GET.
 - Parameters: address.
 - Responses: 200 (OK), 400 (parameter error), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
 - Output (example):

```
{  
  "s"at"s": "OK",  
  "is"dmin": "true"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/authorizedowner?address=0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae3a72c825>
 - Description: Authorize an owner to use the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*.
 - Method: POST.
 - Parameters: address.
 - Responses: 200 (OK), 400 (parameter error), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
 - Output (example):

```
{  
  "s"at"s": "OK",  
  "authorizedowne"ad"ress": "0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae"a72c825"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/authorizedowner?address=0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae3a72c825>

- Description: Deauthorize an owner to use the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*.
- Parameters: address.
- Responses: 200 (OK), 400 (parameter error), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
- Output (example):

```
{
  "s"at"s": "OK",
  "authorizedowne"ad"ress": "0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae"a72c825"
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/authorizedowner?address=0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae3a72c825>

- Description: Check if an id is an authorized owner.
- Method: GET.
- Parameters: address.
- Responses: 200 (OK), 400 (parameter error), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
- Output (example):

```
{
  "s"at"s": "OK",
  "isauthori"ed"wner": "true"
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/adminnum>

- Description: Get the number of administrators in the system.
- Method: GET.
- Parameters: None.
- Responses: 200 (OK), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
- Output (example):

```
{
  "s"at"s": "OK",
  "dm"n"um": "3"
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/authorizedownersnum>

- Description: Get the number of authorized owners in the system.
- Method: GET.
- Parameters: None.
- Responses: 200 (OK), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
- Output (example):

```
{
  "s"at"s": "OK",
  "authorizedow"er"n"m ": "4"
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestratorsnum>

- Description: Get the number of *Orchestrators* registered in the system.
- Method: GET.
- Parameters: None.
- Responses: 200 (OK), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
- Output (example):

```
{
  "s"at"s": "OK",
  "orchestr"to"s"um": "5"
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrators>

- Description: Get the *Orchestrators* ids (addresses) registered in the system.
- Method: GET.
- Parameters: None.

- Responses: 200 (OK), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
- Output (example):

```
{  
  "s"at"s": "OK",  
  "orchestrators"dr"sse":  
  "0x55456e0Bd0E46Ec4276Eac51cfC281D39e2cD449,0xF2c6cF607dCbF1Bf4E885ae6099eC7cF1Cc0ac51,0  
x2B09939744d8c8Be9e23d05C1D04552F203B06D3,0xA3929a5dC7B0DAdB25004443F77bd9C47b56F4A4,0x0  
dE4b77C6683Bd29fAa3fa8FCDdCEf1b" F3aef8b"  
}
```

3. Blockchain transactions generation: *Orchestrator's* functionalities

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator>
 - Description: Register an *Orchestrator* in the trustworthy management system.
 - Method: POST.
 - Parameters: None.
 - Responses: 200 (OK), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
 - Output (example):

```
{  
  "s"at"s": "OK",  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator/id>
 - Description: Get the *Orchestrator* id (address).
 - Method: GET.
 - Parameters: None.
 - Responses: 200 (OK), 401 (registration error), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
 - Output (example):

```
{  
  "s"at"s": "OK", "id": "0x0dE4b77C6683Bd29fAa3fa8FCDdCEf1b" F3aef8b"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator/owner>
 - Description: Get the *Orchestrator* owner.
 - Method: GET.
 - Parameters: None.
 - Responses: 200 (OK), 401 (registration error), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
 - Output (example):

```
{  
  "s"at"s": "OK", "owner": "0x45a224EF8e9f8350eaf0fE123CbAb5ae" a72c825"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator/creationtime>
 - Description: Get the *Orchestrator* creation time.
 - Method: GET.
 - Parameters: None.
 - Responses: 200 (OK), 401 (registration error), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
 - Output (example):

```
{  
  "s"at"s": "OK",  
  "crea"io"Time": " 16335876551"1352261"  
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator/evidence?id=1&hash=0x7465737400&tool=1&resource=2&csp=3>
 - Description: Record a new evidence from the *Orchestrator*.

- Method: POST.
- Parameters: id, hash, tool, resource and csp.
- Responses: 200 (OK), 400 (parameter error), 401 (registration error), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
- Output (example):

```
{
  "status": "OK",
  "evidenceId": "1",
  "evidenceHash": "0x746573740000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000",
  "evidenceTool": "1",
  "evidenceUsage": "2",
  "evidenceStep": "3"
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator/evidence/{id}>
 - Description: Get the evidence information of the provided evidence id.
 - Method: GET.
 - Parameters: None.
 - Responses: 200 (OK), 400 (parameter error), 401 (registration error), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
 - Output (example):

```
{
  "status": "OK",
  "evidence": "1,0x746573740000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000,1,2,3,163358709970812276"
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator/evidences>
 - Description: Get the evidences ids registered from the *Orchestrator*.
 - Method: GET.
 - Parameters: None.
 - Responses: 200 (OK), 401 (registration error), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
 - Output (example):

```
{
  "status": "OK",
  "evidence": "0,1"
}
```

- [https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator/assessment?id=123&hashvalue=0x7465737400&hashcompliance=0x7465737400&evidences=\[1,2\]&metric=2](https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator/assessment?id=123&hashvalue=0x7465737400&hashcompliance=0x7465737400&evidences=[1,2]&metric=2)
 - Description: Record a new assessment result from the *Orchestrator*.
 - Method: POST.
 - Parameters: id, result hash, compliance hash, associated evidences and metric.
 - Responses: 200 (OK), 400 (parameter error), 401 (registration error), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
 - Output (example):

```
{
  "status": "OK",
  "assessmentId": "123",
  "assessmentHash": "0x746573740000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000",
  "assessmentHashCompliance": "0x746573740000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000",
  "assessmentIdences": "[1,2]",
  "evidenceMetric": "2"
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator/assessment/{id}>
 - Description: Get the assessment result information of the provided assessment result id.
 - Method: GET.
 - Parameters: None.
 - Responses: 200 (OK), 400 (parameter error), 401 (registration error), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
 - Output (example):

```
{
  "status": "OK",
  "assessment": "123,0x74657374000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000,0x74657374000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000,1,2,2,16335893984"1147759"
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator/assessments>
 - Description: Get the assessment results ids registered from the *Orchestrator*.
 - Method: GET.
 - Parameters: None.
 - Responses: 200 (OK), 401 (registration error), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
 - Output (example):

```
{
  "status": "OK",
  "assessments": "123,456"
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator/evidence/check>
 - Description: Check the recorded hash value for a specific evidence id.
 - Method: GET.
 - Parameters: id and hash.
 - Responses: 200 (OK), 400 (parameter error), 401 (registration error), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
 - Output (example):

```
{
  "status": "OK",
  "correctevidencash": "true"
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator/assessment/checkhash>
 - Description: Check the recorded result hash value for a specific assessment id.
 - Method: GET.
 - Parameters: id and result hash.
 - Responses: 200 (OK), 400 (parameter error), 401 (registration error), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
 - Output (example):

```
{
  "status": "OK",
  "correctassessmenthash": "true"
}
```

- <https://medina.bclab.dev/client/orchestrator/assessment/checkcompliance>
 - Description: Check the recorded compliance hash value for a specific assessment id.
 - Method: GET.
 - Parameters: id and compliance hash.

- Responses: 200 (OK), 400 (parameter error), 401 (registration error), 403 (Application error), 409 (account error).
- Output (example):

```
{  
  "status": "OK",  
  "correctcompliance": "true"  
}
```

Draft

Appendix D: EUCS Requirements coverage per tool within the MEDINA Evidence Management Tools

This section shows the current coverage of the 34 EUCS requirements identified in Table 2 for each of the tools within the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools*. Please note that the EUCS requirements referred in this deliverable correspond to a draft version of the ENISA catalogue [3] and are not intended for being used outside the context of MEDINA.

The background colour means:

- Green** *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools* cover the requirement to some extent (i.e., at least one metric has been implemented).
- Orange** There is a plan or idea to implement the requirement by any of the *MEDINA Evidence Management Tools*, but it has not yet been realised.
- Red** It is not possible to cover the requirement due to its nature.

1. Cloudfitor

As shown in Table 7, *Cloudfitor* covers 8/34 and has a plan to cover other 15/34 EUCS requirements. 11/34 requirements are not possible to cover with *Cloudfitor's Cloud Evidence Collector*. This is because some requirements are not related to cloud resources.

Table 7. Summary of *Cloudfitor's* coverage of the 34 EUCS high level requirements in Table 2

Req.ID	Requirement	Type	Coverage	Comments
OIS-02.4H	"The CSP shall automatically monitor the assignment of responsibilities and tasks to ensure that measures related to segregation of duties are enforced."	Tech	Green	
ISP-03.5H	"The list of exceptions shall be automatically monitored to ensure that the validity of approved exceptions has not expired and that all reviews and approvals are up-to-date."	Tech	Orange	Possible checks include checking for recent document modifications.
HR-03.4H	"All employees shall acknowledge in a documented form the information security policies and procedures presented to them before they are granted any access to CSC data, the production environment, or any functional component thereof, and the verification of this acknowledgement shall be automatically monitored in the processes and automated systems used to grant access rights to employees."	Tech & Org	Red	
HR-04.3H	"The CSP shall ensure that all employees complete the security awareness and training program defined for them on a regular basis, and when changing target group, and shall automatically monitor the completion of the security awareness and training program."	Tech	Red	

HR-05.2H	“The CSP shall apply a specific procedure to revoke the access rights and process appropriately the accounts and assets of employees when their employment is terminated or changed, defining specific roles and responsibilities and including a documented checklist of all required steps; the CSP shall automatically monitor the application of this procedure.”	Tech		Under certain assumptions <i>Clouditor</i> can be extended with basic checks, e.g., for asset ownership of (non-) existing accounts.
HR-06.2H	“The agreements shall be accepted by external service providers and suppliers when the contract is agreed, and this acceptance shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech		
HR-06.3H	“The agreements shall be accepted by internal employees of the CSP before authorisation to access CSC data is granted, and this acceptance shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech		
HR-06.5H	“The CSP shall inform its internal employees, external service providers and suppliers and obtain confirmation of the updated confidentiality or non-disclosure agreement, and this acceptance shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		
AM-01.4H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the process performing the inventory of assets to guarantee it is up-to-date.”	Tech		We plan to add an Infrastructure-as-Code-based resource discovery to monitor existing resources; in a public cloud, however, the cloud provider has to be trusted with the up-to-dateness with the provided information
AM-03.4H	“The approval of the commissioning and decommissioning of hardware shall be digitally documented and automatically monitored.”	Tech		
AM-04.1H	“The CSP shall ensure and document that all employees are committed to the policies and procedures for acceptable use and safe handling of assets in the situations described in AM-02, and this commitment shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		
PS-02.8H	“The access control policy shall include logging of all accesses to non-public areas that enables the CSP to check whether only defined personnel have entered these areas, and this logging shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		
OPS-02.2H	“The provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services shall be automatically monitored to guarantee fulfilment of these safeguards.”	Tech		While the (de-) provisioning of services can be monitored, it has to be evaluated if this can be

				mapped to a pre-configured list of SLAs, e.g., regarding uptime.
OPS-05.3H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the systems covered by the malware protection and the configuration of the corresponding mechanisms to guarantee fulfilment of above requirements, and the antimalware scans to track detected malware or irregularities.”	Tech		
OPS-07.2H	“In order to check the proper application of these measures, the CSP shall automatically monitor the execution of data backups, and make available to the CSCs a service portal for monitoring the execution of backups when the CSC uses backup services with the CSP.”	Tech		
OPS-09.2H	“When the backup data is transmitted to a remote location via a network, the transmission of the data takes place in an encrypted form that corresponds to the state-of-the-art (cf. CKM-02), and shall be automatically monitored by the CSP to verify the execution of the backup.”	Tech		One possibility is to check for the existence of the backup in the target location.
OPS-12.1H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor log data in order to identify security events that might lead to security incidents, in accordance with the logging and monitoring requirements, and the identified events shall be reported to the appropriate departments for timely assessment and remediation.”	Tech		
OPS-12.2H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor that event detection processes operate as intended on appropriate assets as identified in the asset classification catalogue (cf AM-05-1H).”	Tech		
OPS-13.1H	“The CSP shall store all log data in an integrity-protected and aggregated form that allow its centralized evaluation, and shall automatically monitor the aggregation and deletion of logging and monitoring data.”	Tech		
OPS-18.6H	“The CSP shall provide and promote, where appropriate, automatic update mechanisms for the assets provided by the CSP that the CSCs have to install or operate under their own responsibility, to ease the rollout of patches and updates after an initial approval from the CSC.”	Tech		
OPS-21.1H	“The CSP shall harden all the system components under its responsibility that are used to provide the cloud service, according to accepted industry standards, and	Tech		

	automatically monitor these system components for conformity with hardening requirements.”			
IAM-03.1H	“The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to block user accounts after a certain period of inactivity, as defined in the policy of AIM-02, for user accounts, and automatically monitor its application. Such user accounts are: (1) Of employees of the CSP as well as for system components involved in automated authorisation processes; and (2) Associated with identities assigned to persons, identities assigned to non-human entities and identities assigned to multiple persons.”	Tech		
IAM-03.2H	“The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to block accounts after a certain number of failed authentication attempts, as defined in the policy of AIM-02, based on the risks of the accounts, associated access rights and authentication mechanisms, and automatically monitor its application.”	Tech & Org		
IAM-03.5H	“The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to revoke accounts that have been blocked by another automatic mechanism after a certain period of inactivity, as defined in the policy of AIM-02 for user accounts, and automatically monitor its application.”	Tech & Org		
IAM-03.6H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the context of authentication attempts and flag suspicious events to authorized persons, as relevant.”	Tech		
CCM-04.1H	“The CSP shall approve any change to the cloud service, based on defined criteria and involving CSCs in the approval process according to contractual requirements, before they are made available to CSCs in the production environment, and the approval processes shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		
CCM-05.1H	“The CSP shall define roles and rights according to IAM-01 for the authorised personnel or system components who are allowed to make changes to the cloud service in the production environment, and the changes in the production environment shall be automatically monitored to enforce these roles and rights.”	Tech & Org		<i>Clouditor</i> will be extended with an infrastructure-as-code-based discovery mechanisms that can easily detect changes in a cloud system. An open issue, however, is how this information can be compared to the existing roles concept.

PM-04.7H	“The CSP shall supplement procedures for monitoring compliance with automatic monitoring, by leveraging automatic procedures, when possible, relating to the following aspects: (1) Configuration of system components; (2) Performance and availability of system components; (3) Response time to malfunctions and security incidents; and (4) Recovery time (time until completion of error handling).”	Tech		This requirement targets an extension of the monitoring of EUCS requirements to third parties. We will evaluate if the development of a dedicated API for third parties can be integrated regarding the required features.
PM-04.8H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor Identified violations and discrepancies, and these shall be automatically reported to the responsible personnel or system components of the CSP for prompt assessment and action.”	Tech		Automatic identification of violations is an inherent feature of the MEDINA framework, while automatic reports are an open task for future iterations. We will evaluate if this can be extended to third parties (similar to PM-04.7H).
IM-02.5H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the processing of security incidents to verify the application of incident management policies and procedures.”	Tech		
CO-03.5H	“Internal audits shall be supplemented by procedures to automatically monitor compliance with applicable requirements of policies and instructions.”	Tech & Org		
CO-03.6H	“The CSP shall implement automated monitoring to identify vulnerabilities and deviations, which shall be automatically reported to the appropriate CSP’s subject matter experts for immediate assessment and action.”	Tech		
INQ-03.4H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the accesses performed by or on behalf of investigators as determined by the process described in INQ-01.”	Tech		This can be partly covered, by logging accesses; a mapping to specific users, however, cannot be covered by <i>Clouditor</i> .
PSS-04.2H	“An integrity check shall be performed, automatically monitored and reported to the CSC if the integrity check fails.”	Tech		In public clouds, images are normally obtained from a cloud vendor-owned marketplace and cannot easily be checked for integrity. For integrity checks of container images, we plan to implement checks for Docker Content Trust.

In addition, *Clouditor* also covers or has a plan to cover additional EUCS requirements beyond the 34 identified in Table 2. These additional requirements are listed in Table 8.

Table 8. Summary of additional requirements coverage of Cloudfitor

Req.ID	Requirement	Coverage
OPS-05.1B	“The CSP shall deploy malware protection, if technically feasible, on all systems that support delivery of the cloud service in the production environment, according to policies and procedures.”	
OPS-06.1S	“The CSP shall define and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 for data backup and recovery, covering at least the following aspects: (1)The extent and frequency of data backups and the duration of data retention are consistent with the contractual agreements with the CSCs and the CSP’s operational continuity requirements for recovery time objective (RTO) and recovery point objective (RPO); (2) How data is backed up in encrypted, state-of-the-art form; (3) How backup data is stored, moved, managed, and disposed of; (4) How a CSC-initiated recovery or recovery test is performed; (5) Restricted access to the backed-up data and the execution of restores only by authorised persons; and (6) Tests of recovery procedures (cf. OPS-08).”	
OPS-13.1B	“The CSP shall store all log data in an integrity-protected and aggregated form that allow its evaluation.”	
OPS-13.2S	“The communication between the assets to be logged and the logging servers shall be authenticated, encrypted using state-of-the-art encryption and, when encryption is not feasible, shall be accessible only by authorised personnel.”	
OPS-13.2H	“The communication between the assets to be logged and the logging servers shall be authenticated, encrypted using state-of-the-art encryption and, when encryption is not feasible, shall be accessible only by authorised personnel.”	
OPS-13.3B	“Log data shall be deleted when no longer required for the purpose for which it was collected.”	
OPS-13.4S	“The CSP shall implement technically supported procedures to fulfil requirements for log data access, storage and deletion restrictions, including access only for authorized users and systems and the enforcement of data retention periods.”	
IAM-01.1B	“The CSP shall define role and rights policies and procedures for controlling access to information resources, according to ISP-02 and based on the business and security requirements of the CSP, in which at least the following aspects are covered: (1) Parameters to be considered for making access control decisions; (2) Granting and modifying access rights based on the “least-privilege” principle and on the “need to-know” principle; (3) Segregation of duties between managing, approving and assigning access rights; (4) Dedicated rules for users with privileged access; (5) Requirements for the approval and documentation of the management of access rights.”	
IAM-06.5S	“The CSP shall require strong authentication (for example: multi-factor authentication) for accessing the administration interfaces used by the CSP.”	
IAM-06.5H	“The CSP shall require strong authentication (for example: multi-factor authentication) for accessing the administration interfaces used by the CSP and those offered to the CSCs.”	
IAM-07.1B	“The CSP shall define and implement according to ISP-02 policies and procedures about authentication mechanisms, covering at least the following aspects: (1) The selection of mechanisms suitable for every type of account and each level of risk; (2)The protection of credentials used by the authentication mechanism; (3) The generation and distribution of credentials for new accounts; (4) Rules for the renewal of credentials, including periodic renewals, renewals in case of loss or compromise; and (5) Rules on the	

	required strength of credentials, together with mechanisms to communicate and enforce the rules.”	
CKM-01.1S	“The CSP shall define and implement policies with technical and organizational safeguards for cryptography and key management, according to ISP-02, in which at least the following aspects are described: (1) Usage of strong cryptographic mechanisms and secure network protocols, corresponding to the state of the art; (2) Requirements for the secure generation, storage, archiving, retrieval, distribution, withdrawal and deletion of the keys; (3) Consideration of relevant legal and regulatory obligations and requirements; (4) Risk-based provisions for the use of encryption aligned with the data classification schemes and considering the communication channel, type, strength and quality of the encryption.”	
CKM-02.1B	“The CSP shall define and implement strong cryptographic mechanisms for the transmission of CSC data over public networks, in order to protect the confidentiality, integrity and authenticity of data.”	
CKM-02.1S	“The CSP shall define and implement strong cryptographic mechanisms for the transmission of CSC data over public networks, in order to protect the confidentiality, integrity and authenticity of data.”	
CKM-03.1B	“The CSP shall define and implement procedures and technical safeguards to protect the confidentiality of CSC data during storage, according to ISP-02.”	
CKM-03.3S	“The procedures for the use of private and secret keys, including a specific procedure for any exceptions, shall be established in accordance with applicable legal and regulatory obligations and requirements and contractually agreed with the CSC.”	

2. Codyze

As shown in Table 9, *Codyze* does not currently cover any of the EUCS requirements identified in Table 2; however, it has a plan to cover 6/34 requirements. 28/34 requirements are not possible to cover with *Codyze* because they do not correspond to specific implementations in source code, but example, to runtime operations (e.g., ISP-03.5H, OPS-12.1H).

Table 9. Summary of *Codyze*'s coverage of the 34 EUCS high level requirements in Table 2

ReqID	Requirement	Type	Coverage	Comments
OIS-02.4H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the assignment of responsibilities and tasks to ensure that measures related to segregation of duties are enforced.”	Tech		It may be possible to check if an application uses mechanisms to segregate duties and if assignments are monitored.
ISP-03.5H	“The list of exceptions shall be automatically monitored to ensure that the validity of approved exceptions has not expired and that all reviews and approvals are up-to-date.”	Tech		
HR-03.4H	“All employees shall acknowledge in a documented form the information security policies and procedures presented to them before they are granted any access to CSC data, the production environment, or any functional component thereof, and the verification of this acknowledgement shall be automatically monitored in	Tech & Org		

	the processes and automated systems used to grant access rights to employees.”			
HR-04.3H	“The CSP shall ensure that all employees complete the security awareness and training program defined for them on a regular basis, and when changing target group, and shall automatically monitor the completion of the security awareness and training program.”	Tech		
HR-05.2H	“The CSP shall apply a specific procedure to revoke the access rights and process appropriately the accounts and assets of employees when their employment is terminated or changed, defining specific roles and responsibilities and including a documented checklist of all required steps; the CSP shall automatically monitor the application of this procedure.”	Tech		
HR-06.2H	“The agreements shall be accepted by external service providers and suppliers when the contract is agreed, and this acceptance shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech		
HR-06.3H	“The agreements shall be accepted by internal employees of the CSP before authorisation to access CSC data is granted, and this acceptance shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech		
HR-06.5H	“The CSP shall inform its internal employees, external service providers and suppliers and obtain confirmation of the updated confidentiality or non-disclosure agreement, and this acceptance shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		
AM-01.4H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the process performing the inventory of assets to guarantee it is up-to-date.”	Tech		
AM-03.4H	“The approval of the commissioning and de-commissioning of hardware shall be digitally documented and automatically monitored.”	Tech		
AM-04.1H	“The CSP shall ensure and document that all employees are committed to the policies and procedures for acceptable use and safe handling of assets in the situations described in AM-02, and this commitment shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		
PS-02.8H	“The access control policy shall include logging of all accesses to non-public areas that enables the CSP to check whether only defined personnel have entered these areas, and this logging shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		
OPS-02.2H	“The provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services shall be automatically monitored to guarantee fulfilment of these safeguards.”	Tech		
OPS-05.3H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the systems covered by the malware protection and the configuration of the corresponding mechanisms to guarantee fulfilment of above requirements, and the antimalware scans to track detected malware or irregularities.”	Tech		

OPS-07.2H	“In order to check the proper application of these measures, the CSP shall automatically monitor the execution of data backups, and make available to the CSCs a service portal for monitoring the execution of backups when the CSC uses backup services with the CSP.”	Tech		
OPS-09.2H	“When the backup data is transmitted to a remote location via a network, the transmission of the data takes place in an encrypted form that corresponds to the state-of-the-art (cf. CKM-02), and shall be automatically monitored by the CSP to verify the execution of the backup.”	Tech		
OPS-12.1H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor log data in order to identify security events that might lead to security incidents, in accordance with the logging and monitoring requirements, and the identified events shall be reported to the appropriate departments for timely assessment and remediation.”	Tech		
OPS-12.2H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor that event detection processes operate as intended on appropriate assets as identified in the asset classification catalogue (cf AM-05-1H).”	Tech		
OPS-13.1H	“The CSP shall store all log data in an integrity-protected and aggregated form that allow its centralized evaluation, and shall automatically monitor the aggregation and deletion of logging and monitoring data.”	Tech		
OPS-18.6H	“The CSP shall provide and promote, where appropriate, automatic update mechanisms for the assets provided by the CSP that the CSCs have to install or operate under their own responsibility, to ease the rollout of patches and updates after an initial approval from the CSC.”	Tech		
OPS-21.1H	“The CSP shall harden all the system components under its responsibility that are used to provide the cloud service, according to accepted industry standards, and automatically monitor these system components for conformity with hardening requirements.”	Tech		
IAM-03.1H	“The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to block user accounts after a certain period of inactivity, as defined in the policy of AIM-02, for user accounts, and automatically monitor its application. Such user accounts are: (1) Of employees of the CSP as well as for system components involved in automated authorisation processes; and (2) Associated with identities assigned to persons, identities assigned to non-human entities and identities assigned to multiple persons.”	Tech		

IAM-03.2H	“The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to block accounts after a certain number of failed authentication attempts, as defined in the policy of AIM-02, based on the risks of the accounts, associated access rights and authentication mechanisms, and automatically monitor its application.”	Tech & Org		
IAM-03.5H	“The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to revoke accounts that have been blocked by another automatic mechanism after a certain period of inactivity, as defined in the policy of AIM-02 for user accounts, and automatically monitor its application.”	Tech & Org		
IAM-03.6H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the context of authentication attempts and flag suspicious events to authorized persons, as relevant.”	Tech		<i>Codyze</i> could check if authentication attempts are logged in source code.
CCM-04.1H	“The CSP shall approve any change to the cloud service, based on defined criteria and involving CSCs in the approval process according to contractual requirements, before they are made available to CSCs in the production environment, and the approval processes shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		<i>Codyze</i> can partly cover this requirement, e.g., by checking git commit sign-offs.
CCM-05.1H	“The CSP shall define roles and rights according to IAM-01 for the authorised personnel or system components who are allowed to make changes to the cloud service in the production environment, and the changes in the production environment shall be automatically monitored to enforce these roles and rights.”	Tech & Org		<i>Codyze</i> may check for changes in the software environment used to develop applications. Changes can be flagged as no longer meeting specified requirements.
PM-04.7H	“The CSP shall supplement procedures for monitoring compliance with automatic monitoring, by leveraging automatic procedures, when possible, relating to the following aspects: (1) Configuration of system components; (2) Performance and availability of system components; (3) Response time to malfunctions and security incidents; and (4) Recovery time (time until completion of error handling).”	Tech		
PM-04.8H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor Identified violations and discrepancies, and these shall be automatically reported to the responsible personnel or system components of the CSP for prompt assessment and action.”	Tech		
IM-02.5H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the processing of security incidents to verify the application of incident management policies and procedures.”	Tech		

CO-03.5H	“Internal audits shall be supplemented by procedures to automatically monitor compliance with applicable requirements of policies and instructions.”	Tech & Org		
CO-03.6H	“The CSP shall implement automated monitoring to identify vulnerabilities and deviations, which shall be automatically reported to the appropriate CSP’s subject matter experts for immediate assessment and action.”	Tech		<i>Codyze</i> checks for certain classes of vulnerabilities and deviations from requirements. These are currently related to usage of cryptographic libraries. The process is automated as part of a CI/CD pipeline.
INQ-03.4H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the accesses performed by or on behalf of investigators as determined by the process described in INQ-01.”	Tech		
PSS-04.2H	“An integrity check shall be performed, automatically monitored and reported to the CSC if the integrity check fails.”	Tech		

3. VAT

As shown in Table 10, VAT does not currently cover any of the 34 requirements identified in Table 2; however, it has a plan to cover 4/34 requirements. 30/34 requirements are not possible to cover with this tool. VAT can provide monitoring of the requirements related to vulnerability scanning and (limited) management of incidents, coverage of other requirements is not in scope of VAT. Using user-provided custom scripts, VAT can also cover some other technical requirements and thus act similarly to the GEC.

Table 10. Summary of VAT’s coverage of the 34 EUCS high level requirements in Table 2

Req.ID	Requirement	Type	Coverage	Comments
OIS-02.4H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the assignment of responsibilities and tasks to ensure that measures related to segregation of duties are enforced.”	Tech		
ISP-03.5H	“The list of exceptions shall be automatically monitored to ensure that the validity of approved exceptions has not expired and that all reviews and approvals are up-to-date.”	Tech		
HR-03.4H	“All employees shall acknowledge in a documented form the information security policies and procedures presented to them before they are granted any access to CSC data, the production environment, or any functional component thereof, and the verification of this acknowledgement shall be automatically monitored in the processes and automated systems used to grant access rights to employees.”	Tech & Org		

HR-04.3H	“The CSP shall ensure that all employees complete the security awareness and training program defined for them on a regular basis, and when changing target group, and shall automatically monitor the completion of the security awareness and training program.”	Tech		
HR-05.2H	“The CSP shall apply a specific procedure to revoke the access rights and process appropriately the accounts and assets of employees when their employment is terminated or changed, defining specific roles and responsibilities and including a documented checklist of all required steps; the CSP shall automatically monitor the application of this procedure.”	Tech		
HR-06.2H	“The agreements shall be accepted by external service providers and suppliers when the contract is agreed, and this acceptance shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech		
HR-06.3H	“The agreements shall be accepted by internal employees of the CSP before authorisation to access CSC data is granted, and this acceptance shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech		
HR-06.5H	“The CSP shall inform its internal employees, external service providers and suppliers and obtain confirmation of the updated confidentiality or non-disclosure agreement, and this acceptance shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		
AM-01.4H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the process performing the inventory of assets to guarantee it is up-to-date.”	Tech		
AM-03.4H	“The approval of the commissioning and decommissioning of hardware shall be digitally documented and automatically monitored.”	Tech		
AM-04.1H	“The CSP shall ensure and document that all employees are committed to the policies and procedures for acceptable use and safe handling of assets in the situations described in AM-02, and this commitment shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		
PS-02.8H	“The access control policy shall include logging of all accesses to non-public areas that enables the CSP to check whether only defined personnel have entered these areas, and this logging shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		
OPS-02.2H	“The provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services shall be automatically monitored to guarantee fulfilment of these safeguards.”	Tech		
OPS-05.3H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the systems covered by the malware protection and the configuration of the corresponding mechanisms to guarantee fulfilment of above requirements, and the antimalware scans to track detected malware or irregularities.”	Tech		Although VAT’s primary role are vulnerability scans, some malware checks could be done as well.

OPS-07.2H	“In order to check the proper application of these measures, the CSP shall automatically monitor the execution of data backups, and make available to the CSCs a service portal for monitoring the execution of backups when the CSC uses backup services with the CSP.”	Tech		
OPS-09.2H	“When the backup data is transmitted to a remote location via a network, the transmission of the data takes place in an encrypted form that corresponds to the state-of-the-art (cf. CKM-02), and shall be automatically monitored by the CSP to verify the execution of the backup.”	Tech		
OPS-12.1H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor log data in order to identify security events that might lead to security incidents, in accordance with the logging and monitoring requirements, and the identified events shall be reported to the appropriate departments for timely assessment and remediation.”	Tech		
OPS-12.2H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor that event detection processes operate as intended on appropriate assets as identified in the asset classification catalogue (cf AM-05-1H).”	Tech		
OPS-13.1H	“The CSP shall store all log data in an integrity-protected and aggregated form that allow its centralized evaluation, and shall automatically monitor the aggregation and deletion of logging and monitoring data.”	Tech		
OPS-18.6H	“The CSP shall provide and promote, where appropriate, automatic update mechanisms for the assets provided by the CSP that the CSCs have to install or operate under their own responsibility, to ease the rollout of patches and updates after an initial approval from the CSC.”	Tech		
OPS-21.1H	“The CSP shall harden all the system components under its responsibility that are used to provide the cloud service, according to accepted industry standards, and automatically monitor these system components for conformity with hardening requirements.”	Tech		Specific checks for individual hardening specifications can be implemented (CSP-specific).
IAM-03.1H	“The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to block user accounts after a certain period of inactivity, as defined in the policy of AIM-02, for user accounts, and automatically monitor its application. Such user accounts are: (1) Of employees of the CSP as well as for system components involved in automated authorisation processes; and (2) Associated with identities assigned to persons, identities assigned to non-human entities and identities assigned to multiple persons.”	Tech		

IAM-03.2H	“The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to block accounts after a certain number of failed authentication attempts, as defined in the policy of AIM-02, based on the risks of the accounts, associated access rights and authentication mechanisms, and automatically monitor its application.”	Tech & Org		
IAM-03.5H	“The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to revoke accounts that have been blocked by another automatic mechanism after a certain period of inactivity, as defined in the policy of AIM-02 for user accounts, and automatically monitor its application.”	Tech & Org		
IAM-03.6H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the context of authentication attempts and flag suspicious events to authorized persons, as relevant.”	Tech		
CCM-04.1H	“The CSP shall approve any change to the cloud service, based on defined criteria and involving CSCs in the approval process according to contractual requirements, before they are made available to CSCs in the production environment, and the approval processes shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		
CCM-05.1H	“The CSP shall define roles and rights according to IAM-01 for the authorised personnel or system components who are allowed to make changes to the cloud service in the production environment, and the changes in the production environment shall be automatically monitored to enforce these roles and rights.”	Tech & Org		
PM-04.7H	“The CSP shall supplement procedures for monitoring compliance with automatic monitoring, by leveraging automatic procedures, when possible, relating to the following aspects: (1) Configuration of system components; (2) Performance and availability of system components; (3) Response time to malfunctions and security incidents; and (4) Recovery time (time until completion of error handling).”	Tech		
PM-04.8H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor Identified violations and discrepancies, and these shall be automatically reported to the responsible personnel or system components of the CSP for prompt assessment and action.”	Tech		
IM-02.5H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the processing of security incidents to verify the application of incident management policies and procedures.”	Tech		Processing of security incidents is possible for incidents detected by VAT.
CO-03.5H	“Internal audits shall be supplemented by procedures to automatically monitor compliance with applicable requirements of policies and instructions.”	Tech & Org		

CO-03.6H	“The CSP shall implement automated monitoring to identify vulnerabilities and deviations, which shall be automatically reported to the appropriate CSP’s subject matter experts for immediate assessment and action.”	Tech		VAT implements vulnerability monitoring by itself and can report this as evidence. If the CSP uses another solution for vulnerability detection, VAT cannot monitor its operation.
INQ-03.4H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the accesses performed by or on behalf of investigators as determined by the process described in INQ-01.”	Tech		
PSS-04.2H	“An integrity check shall be performed, automatically monitored and reported to the CSC if the integrity check fails.”	Tech		

4. Wazuh

As shown in Table 11, *Wazuh* covers 2/34 and has a plan or idea to cover other 7/34 EUCS requirements identified in Table 2. 25/34 requirements are not possible to cover with this tool. The requirements in scope of *Wazuh* are those related to malware and vulnerability detection, incident handling, collection of logs, and alerting based on detected events. Other requirements cannot be covered with *Wazuh*.

Table 11. Summary of *Wazuh*’s coverage of the 34 EUCS high level requirements in Table 2

Req.ID	Requirement	Type	Coverage	Comments
OIS-02.4H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the assignment of responsibilities and tasks to ensure that measures related to segregation of duties are enforced.”	Tech		
ISP-03.5H	“The list of exceptions shall be automatically monitored to ensure that the validity of approved exceptions has not expired and that all reviews and approvals are up-to-date.”	Tech		
HR-03.4H	“All employees shall acknowledge in a documented form the information security policies and procedures presented to them before they are granted any access to CSC data, the production environment, or any functional component thereof, and the verification of this acknowledgement shall be automatically monitored in the processes and automated systems used to grant access rights to employees.”	Tech & Org		
HR-04.3H	“The CSP shall ensure that all employees complete the security awareness and training program defined for them on a regular basis, and when changing target group, and shall automatically monitor the completion of the security awareness and training program.”	Tech		

HR-05.2H	“The CSP shall apply a specific procedure to revoke the access rights and process appropriately the accounts and assets of employees when their employment is terminated or changed, defining specific roles and responsibilities and including a documented checklist of all required steps; the CSP shall automatically monitor the application of this procedure.”	Tech		
HR-06.2H	“The agreements shall be accepted by external service providers and suppliers when the contract is agreed, and this acceptance shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech		
HR-06.3H	“The agreements shall be accepted by internal employees of the CSP before authorisation to access CSC data is granted, and this acceptance shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech		
HR-06.5H	“The CSP shall inform its internal employees, external service providers and suppliers and obtain confirmation of the updated confidentiality or non-disclosure agreement, and this acceptance shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		
AM-01.4H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the process performing the inventory of assets to guarantee it is up-to-date.”	Tech		
AM-03.4H	“The approval of the commissioning and de-commissioning of hardware shall be digitally documented and automatically monitored.”	Tech		
AM-04.1H	“The CSP shall ensure and document that all employees are committed to the policies and procedures for acceptable use and safe handling of assets in the situations described in AM-02, and this commitment shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		
PS-02.8H	“The access control policy shall include logging of all accesses to non-public areas that enables the CSP to check whether only defined personnel have entered these areas, and this logging shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		
OPS-02.2H	“The provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services shall be automatically monitored to guarantee fulfilment of these safeguards.”	Tech		
OPS-05.3H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the systems covered by the malware protection and the configuration of the corresponding mechanisms to guarantee fulfilment of above requirements, and the antimalware scans to track detected malware or irregularities.”	Tech		
OPS-07.2H	“In order to check the proper application of these measures, the CSP shall automatically monitor the execution of data backups, and make available to the CSCs a service portal for monitoring the execution of backups when the CSC uses backup services with the CSP.”	Tech		

OPS-09.2H	“When the backup data is transmitted to a remote location via a network, the transmission of the data takes place in an encrypted form that corresponds to the state-of-the-art (cf. CKM-02), and shall be automatically monitored by the CSP to verify the execution of the backup.”	Tech		
OPS-12.1H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor log data in order to identify security events that might lead to security incidents, in accordance with the logging and monitoring requirements, and the identified events shall be reported to the appropriate departments for timely assessment and remediation.”	Tech		<i>Wazuh</i> is a log collection / aggregation tool with event detection and alerting capabilities. It thus provides the implementation of this requirement.
OPS-12.2H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor that event detection processes operate as intended on appropriate assets as identified in the asset classification catalogue (cf AM-05-1H).”	Tech		<i>Wazuh</i> can monitor the operation of <i>Wazuh</i> agents. The integration with an asset classification catalogue is not implemented by <i>Wazuh</i> , but could be done on the MEDINA Orchestrator level.
OPS-13.1H	“The CSP shall store all log data in an integrity-protected and aggregated form that allow its centralized evaluation, and shall automatically monitor the aggregation and deletion of logging and monitoring data.”	Tech		For logs that are collected with <i>Wazuh</i> (forwarded to its collector), deletion of logs could be easily checked by querying for the oldest logs.
OPS-18.6H	“The CSP shall provide and promote, where appropriate, automatic update mechanisms for the assets provided by the CSP that the CSCs have to install or operate under their own responsibility, to ease the rollout of patches and updates after an initial approval from the CSC.”	Tech		Specific checks can be implemented in <i>Wazuh</i> Agents to monitor e.g., update mechanism access logs. This is highly CSP-specific and thus needs to be implemented separately for each specific service being evaluated.
OPS-21.1H	“The CSP shall harden all the system components under its responsibility that are used to provide the cloud service, according to accepted industry standards, and automatically monitor these system components for conformity with hardening requirements.”	Tech		

IAM-03.1H	<p>“The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to block user accounts after a certain period of inactivity, as defined in the policy of AIM-02, for user accounts, and automatically monitor its application. Such user accounts are:</p> <p>(1) Of employees of the CSP as well as for system components involved in automated authorisation processes; and</p> <p>(2) Associated with identities assigned to persons, identities assigned to non-human entities and identities assigned to multiple persons.”</p>	Tech		
IAM-03.2H	<p>“The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to block accounts after a certain number of failed authentication attempts, as defined in the policy of AIM-02, based on the risks of the accounts, associated access rights and authentication mechanisms, and automatically monitor its application.”</p>	Tech & Org		
IAM-03.5H	<p>“The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to revoke accounts that have been blocked by another automatic mechanism after a certain period of inactivity, as defined in the policy of AIM-02 for user accounts, and automatically monitor its application.”</p>	Tech & Org		
IAM-03.6H	<p>“The CSP shall automatically monitor the context of authentication attempts and flag suspicious events to authorized persons, as relevant.”</p>	Tech		Alerting of authorized persons can be implemented if such logging exists.
CCM-04.1H	<p>“The CSP shall approve any change to the cloud service, based on defined criteria and involving CSCs in the approval process according to contractual requirements, before they are made available to CSCs in the production environment, and the approval processes shall be automatically monitored.”</p>	Tech & Org		
CCM-05.1H	<p>“The CSP shall define roles and rights according to IAM-01 for the authorised personnel or system components who are allowed to make changes to the cloud service in the production environment, and the changes in the production environment shall be automatically monitored to enforce these roles and rights.”</p>	Tech & Org		
PM-04.7H	<p>“The CSP shall supplement procedures for monitoring compliance with automatic monitoring, by leveraging automatic procedures, when possible, relating to the following aspects:</p> <p>(1) Configuration of system components;</p> <p>(2) Performance and availability of system components;</p> <p>(3) Response time to malfunctions and security incidents; and</p>	Tech		

	(4) Recovery time (time until completion of error handling)."			
PM-04.8H	"The CSP shall automatically monitor Identified violations and discrepancies, and these shall be automatically reported to the responsible personnel or system components of the CSP for prompt assessment and action."	Tech		
IM-02.5H	"The CSP shall automatically monitor the processing of security incidents to verify the application of incident management policies and procedures."	Tech		This is possible for incidents detected by <i>Wazuh</i> or forwarded to <i>Wazuh</i> through logs of another system.
CO-03.5H	"Internal audits shall be supplemented by procedures to automatically monitor compliance with applicable requirements of policies and instructions."	Tech & Org		
CO-03.6H	"The CSP shall implement automated monitoring to identify vulnerabilities and deviations, which shall be automatically reported to the appropriate CSP's subject matter experts for immediate assessment and action."	Tech		<i>Wazuh</i> agents can identify particular vulnerabilities or malware appearing on the monitored machines.
INQ-03.4H	"The CSP shall automatically monitor the accesses performed by or on behalf of investigators as determined by the process described in INQ-01."	Tech		
PSS-04.2H	"An integrity check shall be performed, automatically monitored and reported to the CSC if the integrity check fails."	Tech		

5. AMOE

As shown in Table 12, *AMOE* covers 17/34 EUCS requirements. Other 17/34 requirements are not possible to cover with *AMOE* as they are not organisational, nor do they imply that monitoring a respective static policy document is necessary, i.e., they are focused on automatic monitoring that requires technical implementation.

Table 12. Summary of *AMOE*'s coverage of the 34 EUCS high level requirements in Table 2

Req.ID	Requirement	Type	Coverage	Comments
OIS-02.4H	"The CSP shall automatically monitor the assignment of responsibilities and tasks to ensure that measures related to segregation of duties are enforced."	Tech		
ISP-03.5H	"The list of exceptions shall be automatically monitored to ensure that the validity of approved exceptions has not	Tech		

	expired and that all reviews and approvals are up-to-date.”			
HR-03.4H	“All employees shall acknowledge in a documented form the information security policies and procedures presented to them before they are granted any access to CSC data, the production environment, or any functional component thereof, and the verification of this acknowledgement shall be automatically monitored in the processes and automated systems used to grant access rights to employees.”	Tech & Org		
HR-04.3H	“The CSP shall ensure that all employees complete the security awareness and training program defined for them on a regular basis, and when changing target group, and shall automatically monitor the completion of the security awareness and training program.”	Tech		
HR-05.2H	“The CSP shall apply a specific procedure to revoke the access rights and process appropriately the accounts and assets of employees when their employment is terminated or changed, defining specific roles and responsibilities and including a documented checklist of all required steps; the CSP shall automatically monitor the application of this procedure.”	Tech		
HR-06.2H	“The agreements shall be accepted by external service providers and suppliers when the contract is agreed, and this acceptance shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech		
HR-06.3H	“The agreements shall be accepted by internal employees of the CSP before authorisation to access CSC data is granted, and this acceptance shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech		
HR-06.5H	“The CSP shall inform its internal employees, external service providers and suppliers and obtain confirmation of the updated confidentiality or non-disclosure agreement, and this acceptance shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		
AM-01.4H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the process performing the inventory of assets to guarantee it is up-to-date.”	Tech		
AM-03.4H	“The approval of the commissioning and decommissioning of hardware shall be digitally documented and automatically monitored.”	Tech		
AM-04.1H	“The CSP shall ensure and document that all employees are committed to the policies and procedures for acceptable use and safe handling of assets in the situations described in AM-02, and this commitment shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		
PS-02.8H	“The access control policy shall include logging of all accesses to non-public areas that enables the CSP to check whether only defined personnel have entered these areas, and this logging shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		
OPS-02.2H	“The provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services shall be automatically monitored to guarantee fulfilment of these safeguards.”	Tech		

OPS-05.3H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the systems covered by the malware protection and the configuration of the corresponding mechanisms to guarantee fulfilment of above requirements, and the antimalware scans to track detected malware or irregularities.”	Tech		
OPS-07.2H	“In order to check the proper application of these measures, the CSP shall automatically monitor the execution of data backups, and make available to the CSCs a service portal for monitoring the execution of backups when the CSC uses backup services with the CSP.”	Tech		
OPS-09.2H	“When the backup data is transmitted to a remote location via a network, the transmission of the data takes place in an encrypted form that corresponds to the state-of-the-art (cf. CKM-02), and shall be automatically monitored by the CSP to verify the execution of the backup.”	Tech		
OPS-12.1H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor log data in order to identify security events that might lead to security incidents, in accordance with the logging and monitoring requirements, and the identified events shall be reported to the appropriate departments for timely assessment and remediation.”	Tech		
OPS-12.2H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor that event detection processes operate as intended on appropriate assets as identified in the asset classification catalogue (cf AM-05-1H).”	Tech		
OPS-13.1H	“The CSP shall store all log data in an integrity-protected and aggregated form that allow its centralized evaluation, and shall automatically monitor the aggregation and deletion of logging and monitoring data.”	Tech		
OPS-18.6H	“The CSP shall provide and promote, where appropriate, automatic update mechanisms for the assets provided by the CSP that the CSCs have to install or operate under their own responsibility, to ease the rollout of patches and updates after an initial approval from the CSC.”	Tech		
OPS-21.1H	“The CSP shall harden all the system components under its responsibility that are used to provide the cloud service, according to accepted industry standards, and automatically monitor these system components for conformity with hardening requirements.”	Tech		
IAM-03.1H	“The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to block user accounts after a certain period of inactivity, as defined in the policy of AIM-02, for user accounts, and automatically monitor its application. Such user accounts are: (1) Of employees of the CSP as well as for system components involved in automated authorisation processes; and (2) Associated with identities assigned to persons, identities assigned to non-human entities and identities assigned to multiple persons.”	Tech		

IAM-03.2H	“The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to block accounts after a certain number of failed authentication attempts, as defined in the policy of AIM-02, based on the risks of the accounts, associated access rights and authentication mechanisms, and automatically monitor its application.”	Tech & Org		
IAM-03.5H	“The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to revoke accounts that have been blocked by another automatic mechanism after a certain period of inactivity, as defined in the policy of AIM-02 for user accounts, and automatically monitor its application.”	Tech & Org		
IAM-03.6H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the context of authentication attempts and flag suspicious events to authorized persons, as relevant.”	Tech		
CCM-04.1H	“The CSP shall approve any change to the cloud service, based on defined criteria and involving CSCs in the approval process according to contractual requirements, before they are made available to CSCs in the production environment, and the approval processes shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		
CCM-05.1H	“The CSP shall define roles and rights according to IAM-01 for the authorised personnel or system components who are allowed to make changes to the cloud service in the production environment, and the changes in the production environment shall be automatically monitored to enforce these roles and rights.”	Tech & Org		
PM-04.7H	“The CSP shall supplement procedures for monitoring compliance with automatic monitoring, by leveraging automatic procedures, when possible, relating to the following aspects: (1) Configuration of system components; (2) Performance and availability of system components; (3) Response time to malfunctions and security incidents; and (4) Recovery time (time until completion of error handling).”	Tech		
PM-04.8H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor Identified violations and discrepancies, and these shall be automatically reported to the responsible personnel or system components of the CSP for prompt assessment and action.”	Tech		
IM-02.5H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the processing of security incidents to verify the application of incident management policies and procedures.”	Tech		
CO-03.5H	“Internal audits shall be supplemented by procedures to automatically monitor compliance with applicable requirements of policies and instructions.”	Tech & Org		
CO-03.6H	“The CSP shall implement automated monitoring to identify vulnerabilities and deviations, which shall be automatically reported to the appropriate CSP’s subject matter experts for immediate assessment and action.”	Tech		
INQ-03.4H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the accesses performed by or on behalf of investigators as determined by the process described in INQ-01.”	Tech		

PSS-04.2H	“An integrity check shall be performed, automatically monitored and reported to the CSC if the integrity check fails.”	Tech		
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In addition, AMOE also covers additional EUCS requirements beyond the 34 identified in Table 2. These additional requirements are listed in Table 13.

Table 13. Summary of additional requirements coverage of AMOE

Req.ID	Requirement	Coverage
ISP-02.1H	“The CSP shall derive policies and procedures from the global information security policy for all relevant subject matters, and document them according to a uniform structure, including at least the following aspects: (1) Objectives; (2) Scope; (3) Roles and responsibilities within the organization, including staff competence requirements and the establishment of substitution rules; (4) Roles and dependencies on other organisations (especially CSCs and subservice providers); (5) Steps for the execution of the security strategy; (6) Applicable legal and regulatory requirements.”	
AM-01.1H	“The CSP shall define and implement policies and procedures for maintaining an inventory of assets, which shall be performed automatically and/or by the people or teams responsible for the assets to ensure complete, accurate, valid and consistent inventory throughout the asset life cycle.”	
OPS-04.1H	“The CSP shall define and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 to protect its systems and its customers from malware, covering at least the following aspects: (1) Use of system-specific protection mechanisms; (2) Operating protection programs on system components under the responsibility of the CSP that are used to provide the cloud service in the production environment; and (3) Operation of protection programs for employees’ terminal equipment.”	
OPS-06.1H	“The CSP shall define and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 for data backup and recovery, covering at least the following aspects: (1)The extent and frequency of data backups and the duration of data retention are consistent with the contractual agreements with the CSCs and the CSP’s operational continuity requirements for recovery time objective (RTO) and recovery point objective (RPO); (2) How data is backed up in encrypted, state-of-the-art form; (3) How backup data is stored, moved, managed, and disposed of; (4) How a CSC-initiated recovery or recovery test is performed; (5) Restricted access to the backed-up data and the execution of restores only by authorised persons; and (6) Tests of recovery procedures (cf. OPS-08).”	
OPS-07.1H	“The CSP shall document and implement technical and organizational measures to monitor the execution of data backups in accordance to the policies and procedures defined in OPS-06.”	
OPS-08.1H	“The CSP shall test the restore procedures at least annually, embedded in the CSP’s business continuity management, including tests assessing if the specifications for the RTO and RPO agreed with the customers are met.”	
OPS-08.3H	“The CSP shall thoroughly document restore tests, including the safe disposal of restored data.”	
OPS-09.1H	“The CSP shall transfer backup data to a remote location or transport them on backup media to a remote location, selected upon criteria of distance, recovery times and impact of disasters on backup and main sites.”	

OPS-10.1H	<p>“The CSP shall define and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 that govern the logging and monitoring of events on system components under its responsibility, covering at least the following aspects: (1) Definition of events that could lead to a violation of the protection goals; (2) Specifications for activating, stopping and pausing the various logs; (3) Information regarding the purpose and retention period of the logs; (4) Definition of roles and responsibilities for setting up and monitoring logging; (5) Definition of log data that may be transferred to CSCs and technical requirements of such log forwarding; (6) Information about timestamps in event creation; (7) Time synchronisation of system components; and (8) Compliance with legal and regulatory frameworks.”</p>	
OPS-13.3H	<p>“Log data shall be deleted when it is no longer required for the purpose for which they were collected.”</p>	
OPS-17.1H	<p>“The CSP shall define and implement, in accordance with ISP-02, policies and procedures, including technical and organisational measures to ensure the timely identification and addressing of vulnerabilities in the system components used to provide the cloud service, covering at least the following aspects: (1) Regular identification of vulnerabilities; (2) Assessment of the severity of identified vulnerabilities; (3) Prioritisation and implementation of actions to promptly remediate or mitigate identified vulnerabilities based on severity and according to defined case specific timelines; and (4) Handling of system components for which no measures are initiated for the timely remediation or mitigation of vulnerabilities.”</p>	
OPS-19.1H	<p>“The CSP shall perform at least monthly tests to detect publicly known vulnerabilities on the system components used to provide the cloud service, in accordance with policies for handling vulnerabilities (cf. OPS-17).”</p>	
IAM-01.1H	<p>“The CSP shall define role and rights policies and procedures for controlling access to information resources, according to ISP-02 and based on role-based access control and based on the business and security requirements of the CSP, in which at least the following aspects are covered: (1) Parameters to be considered for making access control decisions; (2) Granting and modifying access rights based on the “least-privilege” principle and on the “need to-know” principle; (3) Use of a role-based mechanism for the assignment of access rights; (4) Segregation of duties between managing, approving and assigning access rights; (5) Dedicated rules for users with privileged access; (6) Requirements for the approval and documentation of the management of access rights.”</p>	
IAM-08.1H	<p>“The CSP shall document, communicate and make available to all users under its responsibility rules and recommendations for the management of credentials, including at least: (1) Non-reuse of credentials; (2) Trade-offs between entropy and ability to memorize; (3) Recommendations for renewal of passwords; (4) Rules on storage of passwords. (5) Recommendations on password managers (6) Recommendation to specifically address classical attacks, including phishing, social attacks, and whaling.”</p>	
CKM-01.1H	<p>“The CSP shall define and implement policies with technical and organizational safeguards for cryptography and key management, according to ISP-02, in which at least the following aspects are described: (1) Usage of strong cryptographic mechanisms and secure network protocols, corresponding to the state of the art; (2) Requirements for the secure generation, storage, archiving, retrieval, distribution, withdrawal and deletion of the keys; (3) Consideration of relevant legal and regulatory obligations and requirements; (4) Risk-based provisions for the use of encryption aligned with the data classification schemes and considering the communication channel, type, strength and quality of the encryption.”</p>	

CKM-02.1H	“The CSP shall define and implement strong cryptographic mechanisms for the transmission of all data over public networks, in order to protect the confidentiality, integrity and authenticity of data.”	
CKM-02.2H	“The CSP shall use strong cryptographic mechanisms to protect the communication during remote access to the production environment, including employee authentication.”	
CKM-03.1H	“The CSP shall define and implement procedures and technical safeguards to protect the confidentiality of CSC data during storage, according to ISP-02.”	
CKM-04.1H	“Procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management in the area of responsibility of the CSP shall include at least the following aspects: (1) Generation of keys for different cryptographic systems and applications; (2) Issuing and obtaining public-key certificates; (3) Provisioning and activation of the keys; (4) Secure storage of keys including description of how authorised users get access; (5) Changing or updating cryptographic keys including policies defining under which conditions and in which manner the changes and/or updates are to be realised; (6) Handling of compromised keys; and (7) Withdrawal and deletion of keys.”	
CS-01.1H	“The CSP shall document, communicate and implement technical safeguards that are suitable to promptly detect and respond to network-based attacks and to ensure the protection of information and information processing systems, in accordance with ISP-02, and based on the results of a risk analysis carried out according to RM-01.”	
CS-02.1H	“The CSP shall define and implement according to ISP-02 specific security requirements to connect within its network, including at least: (1) When the security zones are to be separated and when the CSCs are to be logically or physically segregated; (2) What communication relationships and what network and application protocols are permitted in each case; (3) How the data traffic for administration and monitoring are segregated from each other at the network level; (4) What internal, cross-location communication is permitted; and (5) what cross-network communication is allowed.”	
CS-03.1H	“The CSP shall distinguish between trusted and untrusted networks, based on a risk assessment.”	
CS-05.1H	“The CSP shall document and implement separation mechanisms at network level for the data traffic of different CSCs.”	
PI-01.2B	“The interfaces shall be clearly documented for subject matter experts to understand how they can be used to retrieve the data.”	
CCM-01.1H	“The CSP shall define and implement policies and procedures for change management of the IT systems supporting the cloud service according to ISP-02, covering at least the following aspects: (1) Criteria for risk assessment, categorization and prioritization of changes and related requirements for the type and scope of testing to be performed, and necessary approvals; (2) Requirements for the performance and documentation of tests; (3) Requirements for segregation of duties during planning, testing, and release of changes; (4) Requirements for the proper information of CSCs about the type and scope of the change as well as the resulting obligations to cooperate in accordance with the contractual agreements; (5) Requirements for the documentation of changes in the system, operational and user documentation; and (6) Requirements for the implementation and documentation of emergency changes, which must comply with the same level of security as normal changes. (7) Requirements for the handling of a change’s unexpected effects, including corrective actions.”	
IM-01.2H	“The CSP shall establish a Cyber Security Incident Response Team (CSIRT), which contributes to the coordinated resolution of security incidents.”	
IM-02.1H	“The CSP shall classify and prioritize security events that could constitute a security incident, and perform root-cause analyses for these events, using their subject matter experts and external security providers where appropriate.”	

IM-02.4H	“The CSP shall simulate the identification, analysis, and defence of security incidents and attacks at least once a year through appropriate tests and exercises.”	
IM-04.1H	“The CSP shall inform employees and external business partners of their contractual obligations to report all security events that become known to them and are directly related to the cloud service.”	
IM-04.3H	“The CSP shall define, publish and implement a single point of contact to report security events and vulnerabilities.”	
IM-05.1H	“The CSP shall periodically inform its CSCs on the status of the security incidents affecting the CSC, or, where appropriate and necessary, involve them in the resolution, according to the contractual agreements.”	
IM-05.2H	“As soon as a security incident has been closed, the CSP shall inform the affected CSCs about the actions taken, according to the contractual agreements.”	
IM-07.1H	“The CSP shall document and implement a procedure to archive all documents and evidence that provide details on security incidents, in a way that could be used as evidence in court.”	
IM-07.4H	“The CSP shall establish an integrated team of forensic/incident responder employees specifically trained on evidence preservation and chain of custody management.”	
BC-01.1B	“The CSP shall define policies and procedures according to ISP-02 establishing the strategy and guidelines to ensure business continuity and contingency management.”	
BC-02.1H	“The policies and procedures for business continuity and contingency management shall include the need to perform a business impact analysis to determine the impact of any malfunction to the cloud service or enterprise, considering at least the following aspects: (1) Possible scenarios based on a risk assessment; (2) Identification of critical products and services; (3) Identification of dependencies, including processes (including resources required), applications, business partners and third-parties; (4) Identification of threats to critical products and services; (5) Identification of effects resulting from planned and unplanned malfunctions and changes over time; (6) Determination of the maximum acceptable duration of malfunctions; (7) Identification of restoration priorities; (8) Determination of time targets for the resumption of critical products and services within the maximum acceptable time period (RTO); (9) Determination of time targets for the maximum reasonable period during which data can be lost and not recovered (RPO); and (10) Estimation of the resources needed for resumption.”	
BC-03.1H	“The CSP shall document and implement a business continuity plan and contingency plans to ensure continuity of the services, taking into account information security constraints and the results of the business impact analysis, based on industry accepted standards, and covering at least the following aspects: (1) Defined purpose and scope, including relevant business processes and dependencies; (2) Accessibility and comprehensibility of the plans for persons who are to act accordingly; (3) Ownership by at least one designated person responsible for review and approval; (4) Defined communication channels, roles and responsibilities including notification of the customers; (5) Recovery procedures, manual interim solutions and reference information (taking into account prioritisation in the recovery of cloud infrastructure components and services and alignment with customers); (6) List of standards being used; (7) Methods for putting the plans into effect; (8) Continuous process improvement; and (9) Interfaces to Security Incident Management.”	
CO-01.1H	“The CSP shall document the legal, regulatory, self-imposed and contractual requirements relevant to the information security of the cloud service.”	

CO-01.4H	The CSP shall document and implement a proactive approach for receiving up-to-date legal, regulatory and contractual requirements that affect the cloud service.”	
CO-02.1H	“The CSP shall define and implement policies and procedures for planning and conducting audits, made in accordance with ISP-02 and that would not interfere with the operation of the cloud service, addressing at least the following aspects: (1) Restriction to read-only access to system components in accordance with the agreed audit plan and as necessary to perform the audit activities; (2) Activities that may result in malfunctions to the cloud service or breaches of contractual requirements are performed during scheduled maintenance windows or outside peak periods; and (3) Logging and monitoring of activities.”	
DOC-01.1H	“The CSP shall make publicly available guidelines and recommendations to assist the cloud service users with the secure configuration, installation, deployment, operation and maintenance of the cloud service provided, covering at least the following aspects, where applicable to the cloud service: (1) Instructions for secure configuration; (2) Information sources on known vulnerabilities and update mechanisms; (3) Error handling and logging mechanisms; (4) Authentication mechanisms; (5) Roles and rights policies including combinations that result in an elevated risk; (6) Services and functions for administration of the cloud service by privileged users, and (7) Complementary User Entity Controls (CUECs).”	
DOC-02.1H	“The CSP shall provide comprehensible and transparent information on: (1) Its jurisdiction; and (2) System component locations, including its subservice providers, where CSC data , meta-data, cloud service derived data and CSC account data is processed, stored and backed up; (3) System component locations, including for its subservice providers, where any CSP data is processed, stored, and backed up; (4) The locations from which administration and supervision may be carried out on the cloud service. (5) The locations from which the CSP conducts support operations for CSCs, including the list of operations that can be carried by support teams in each location.”	

6. Generic Evidence Collector (GEC)

As shown in Table 14, GEC covers 8/34 EUCS requirements and has a plan or idea to cover other 26/34 requirements.

Table 14. Summary of GEC’s coverage of the 34 EUCS high level requirements in Table 2

Req.ID	Requirement	Type	Coverage	Comments
OIS-02.4H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the assignment of responsibilities and tasks to ensure that measures related to segregation of duties are enforced.”	Tech		
ISP-03.5H	“The list of exceptions shall be automatically monitored to ensure that the validity of approved exceptions has not expired and that all reviews and approvals are up-to-date.”	Tech		
HR-03.4H	“All employees shall acknowledge in a documented form the information security policies and procedures presented to them before they are granted any access to CSC data, the production environment, or any functional component thereof, and the verification of this acknowledgement shall be automatically monitored in the processes and automated systems used to grant access rights to employees.”	Tech & Org		

HR-04.3H	“The CSP shall ensure that all employees complete the security awareness and training program defined for them on a regular basis, and when changing target group, and shall automatically monitor the completion of the security awareness and training program.”	Tech		
HR-05.2H	“The CSP shall apply a specific procedure to revoke the access rights and process appropriately the accounts and assets of employees when their employment is terminated or changed, defining specific roles and responsibilities and including a documented checklist of all required steps; the CSP shall automatically monitor the application of this procedure.”	Tech		
HR-06.2H	“The agreements shall be accepted by external service providers and suppliers when the contract is agreed, and this acceptance shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
HR-06.3H	“The agreements shall be accepted by internal employees of the CSP before authorisation to access CSC data is granted, and this acceptance shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
HR-06.5H	“The CSP shall inform its internal employees, external service providers and suppliers and obtain confirmation of the updated confidentiality or non-disclosure agreement, and this acceptance shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
AM-01.4H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the process performing the inventory of assets to guarantee it is up-to-date.”	Tech		
AM-03.4H	“The approval of the commissioning and decommissioning of hardware shall be digitally documented and automatically monitored.”	Tech		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
AM-04.1H	“The CSP shall ensure and document that all employees are committed to the policies and procedures for acceptable use and safe handling of assets in the situations described in AM-02, and this commitment shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		
PS-02.8H	“The access control policy shall include logging of all accesses to non-public areas that enables the CSP to check whether only defined personnel have entered these areas, and this logging shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		
OPS-02.2H	“The provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services shall be automatically monitored to guarantee fulfilment of these safeguards.”	Tech		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided

OPS-05.3H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the systems covered by the malware protection and the configuration of the corresponding mechanisms to guarantee fulfilment of above requirements, and the antimalware scans to track detected malware or irregularities.”	Tech		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
OPS-07.2H	“In order to check the proper application of these measures, the CSP shall automatically monitor the execution of data backups, and make available to the CSCs a service portal for monitoring the execution of backups when the CSC uses backup services with the CSP.”	Tech		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
OPS-09.2H	“When the backup data is transmitted to a remote location via a network, the transmission of the data takes place in an encrypted form that corresponds to the state-of-the-art (cf. CKM-02), and shall be automatically monitored by the CSP to verify the execution of the backup.”	Tech		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
OPS-12.1H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor log data in order to identify security events that might lead to security incidents, in accordance with the logging and monitoring requirements, and the identified events shall be reported to the appropriate departments for timely assessment and remediation.”	Tech		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
OPS-12.2H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor that event detection processes operate as intended on appropriate assets as identified in the asset classification catalogue (cf AM-05-1H).”	Tech		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
OPS-13.1H	“The CSP shall store all log data in an integrity-protected and aggregated form that allow its centralized evaluation, and shall automatically monitor the aggregation and deletion of logging and monitoring data.”	Tech		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
OPS-18.6H	“The CSP shall provide and promote, where appropriate, automatic update mechanisms for the assets provided by the CSP that the CSCs have to install or operate under their own responsibility, to ease the rollout of patches and updates after an initial approval from the CSC.”	Tech		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
OPS-21.1H	“The CSP shall harden all the system components under its responsibility that are used to provide the cloud service, according to accepted industry standards, and automatically monitor these system components for conformity with hardening requirements.”	Tech		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided

IAM-03.1H	“The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to block user accounts after a certain period of inactivity, as defined in the policy of AIM-02, for user accounts, and automatically monitor its application. Such user accounts are: (1) Of employees of the CSP as well as for system components involved in automated authorisation processes; and (2) Associated with identities assigned to persons, identities assigned to non-human entities and identities assigned to multiple persons.”	Tech		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
IAM-03.2H	“The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to block accounts after a certain number of failed authentication attempts, as defined in the policy of AIM-02, based on the risks of the accounts, associated access rights and authentication mechanisms, and automatically monitor its application.”	Tech & Org		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
IAM-03.5H	“The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to revoke accounts that have been blocked by another automatic mechanism after a certain period of inactivity, as defined in the policy of AIM-02 for user accounts, and automatically monitor its application.”	Tech & Org		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
IAM-03.6H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the context of authentication attempts and flag suspicious events to authorized persons, as relevant.”	Tech		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
CCM-04.1H	“The CSP shall approve any change to the cloud service, based on defined criteria and involving CSCs in the approval process according to contractual requirements, before they are made available to CSCs in the production environment, and the approval processes shall be automatically monitored.”	Tech & Org		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
CCM-05.1H	“The CSP shall define roles and rights according to IAM-01 for the authorised personnel or system components who are allowed to make changes to the cloud service in the production environment, and the changes in the production environment shall be automatically monitored to enforce these roles and rights.”	Tech & Org		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
PM-04.7H	“The CSP shall supplement procedures for monitoring compliance with automatic monitoring, by leveraging automatic procedures, when possible, relating to the following aspects: (1) Configuration of system components; (2) Performance and availability of system components; (3) Response time to malfunctions and security incidents; and (4) Recovery time (time until completion of error handling).”	Tech		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided

PM-04.8H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor Identified violations and discrepancies, and these shall be automatically reported to the responsible personnel or system components of the CSP for prompt assessment and action.”	Tech		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
IM-02.5H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the processing of security incidents to verify the application of incident management policies and procedures.”	Tech		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
CO-03.5H	“Internal audits shall be supplemented by procedures to automatically monitor compliance with applicable requirements of policies and instructions.”	Tech & Org		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
CO-03.6H	“The CSP shall implement automated monitoring to identify vulnerabilities and deviations, which shall be automatically reported to the appropriate CSP’s subject matter experts for immediate assessment and action.”	Tech		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
INQ-03.4H	“The CSP shall automatically monitor the accesses performed by or on behalf of investigators as determined by the process described in INQ-01.”	Tech		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided
PSS-04.2H	“An integrity check shall be performed, automatically monitored and reported to the CSC if the integrity check fails.”	Tech		Technique description either in textual form and/or as pseudo-code will be provided

Appendix E: Self-assessment questionnaires for EUCS basic requirements

1. Organization of Information Security

Table 15. Checklist for OIS basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

Control ID	Control	ReqID	Requirement	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
OIS-01	INFORMATION SECURITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM	OIS-01.1B	The CSP shall have an information security management system (ISMS), covering at least the operational units, locations, people and processes for providing the cloud service.	Q1-OIS-01.1B	Does the CSP have an information security management system (ISMS) documented?	- Documented Information Security Management System (ISMS)
				Q2-OIS-01.1B	Does the information security management system cover the operational units?	- ISMS scope (operational units)
				Q3-OIS-01.1B	Does the information security management system (ISMS), cover locations?	- ISMS scope (locations)
				Q4-OIS-01.1B	Does the CSP cover processes for providing the cloud service?	- ISMS scope (processes for providing the cloud service)
		OIS-01.2B	The CSP shall provide documented information of the ISMS applied to the cloud service.	Q1-OIS-01.2B	Does the CSP provide documented information of the ISMS applied to the cloud service?	- Documented information of the ISMS applied to the cloud service
OIS-02	SEGREGATION OF DUTIES	OIS-02.1B	The CSP shall perform a risk assessment as defined in RM-01 about the accumulation of responsibilities or tasks on roles or individuals, regarding the provision of the CSC, covering at least the following areas, insofar as these are applicable to the provision of the cloud service and are in the area of responsibility of the CSP: (1) Administration of rights profiles, approval and assignment of access and access authorisations (cf. IAM-01); (2) Development, testing and release of changes (cf. DEV-01, CCM-01); and	Q1-OIS-02.1B	Does the CSP perform a risk assessment as defined in RM-01?	- Documented risk assessment

			(3) Operation of the system components.			
				Q2-OIS-02.1B	Does the risk assessment address the accumulation of responsibilities or tasks in roles or individuals, with respect to the provision of the cloud service?	- Documented risk assessment (information related with the accumulation of responsibilities or tasks in roles or individuals, with respect to the provision of the cloud service)
				Q3-OIS-02.1B	Does the risk assessment cover administration of rights profiles, approval and assignment of access and access authorisations (cf. IAM-01)?	- Documented risk assessment (information related with the administration of rights profiles, approval and assignment of access and access authorisations) - Documented risk assessment review record
				Q4-OIS-02.1B	Does the risk assessment cover development, testing and release of changes (cf. DEV-01, CCM-01)?	- Documented risk assessment (information related with development, testing and release of changes) - Documented risk assessment review record
				Q5-OIS-02.1B	Does the risk assessment cover the operation of the system components / assets?	- Documented risk assessment (information related with operation of the system components) - Documented risk assessment review record
		OIS-02.2B	The CSP shall implement the mitigating measures defined in the risk treatment plan, privileging separation of duties, unless impossible for organisational or technical reasons, in which case the measures shall include the monitoring of activities in order to detect unauthorised or unintended changes as well as misuse and the subsequent appropriate actions.	Q1-OIS-02.2B	Does the CSP implement the mitigating measures defined in the risk treatment plan?	- Quality records derived from the implementation of the defined Risk Assessment. The records shall include at least the following information: mitigation measure applied, linked requirement id and by whom.

OIS-03	CONTACT WITH AUTHORITIES AND INTEREST GROUPS	OIS-03.1B	The CSP shall stay informed about current threats and vulnerabilities	Q1-OIS-03.1B	Does the CSP stay informed about current threats and vulnerabilities?	- Subscriptions to Industry Reports & Storm Casts - Online Threat Intelligence investigation records
OIS-04	INFORMATION SECURITY IN PROJECT MANAGEMENT	OIS-04.1B	The CSP shall include information security in the project management of all projects that may affect the service, regardless of the nature of the project.	Q1-OIS-04.1B	Does the CSP include information security in the project management of all projects that may affect the service, regardless of the nature of the project?	- Project management documentation (information related with the information security)

2. Information Security Policies

Table 16. Checklist for ISP basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

Control ID	Control	ReqID	Requirement	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
ISP-01	GLOBAL INFORMATION SECURITY POLICY	ISP-01.1B	The CSP shall document a global information security policy covering at least the following aspects: (1) the importance of information security, based on the requirements of CSCs in relation to information security, as well as on the need to ensure the security of the information processed and stored by the CSP and the assets that support the services provided (2) the security objectives and the desired security level, based on the business goals and tasks of the CSP (3) the commitment of the CSP to implement the security measures required to achieve the established security objectives; (4) the most important aspects of the security strategy to achieve the security objectives	Q1-ISP-01.1B	Is there a document describing the global information security policy?	- Global information security policy document

			(5) the organisational structure for information security in the ISMS application area.		
				Q2-ISP-01.1.B	Does the policy cover the importance of information security, as well as on the need to ensure the security of the information processed and stored by the CSP and the assets that support the services provided? - Global information security policy document (includes the importance of information security, as well as on the need to ensure the security of the information processed and stored by the CSP and the assets that support the services provided)
				Q3-ISP-01.1.B	Does the policy cover the security objectives and the desired assurance and security level, based on the business goals of the Cloud Service Provider? - Global information security policy document (includes the security objectives and the desired security level, based on the business goals and tasks of the Cloud Service Provider)
				Q4-ISP-01.1.B	Does the policy cover the commitment of the CSP to implement the security measures required to achieve the established security objectives? - Global information security policy document (includes the commitment of the CSP to implement the security measures required to achieve the established security objectives)
				Q5-ISP-01.1.B	Does the policy cover the most important aspects of the security strategy to achieve the security objectives set? - Global information security policy document (includes the most important aspects of the security strategy to achieve the security objectives set)
				Q6-ISP-01.1.B	Does the policy cover the organisational structure for information security in the cloud service application area? - Global information security policy document (includes the organisational structure for information security in the ISMS application area)

		ISP-01.2B	The CSP's top management shall approve and endorse the global information security policy.	Q1-ISP-01.2B	Does the global information security policy or the organizational structure document establish who is the top management responsible for?	- Global information security policy document (establishes who is the top management responsible for) - Organizational structure
				Q2-ISP-01.2B	Does the top management approve and endorse the global information security policy?	- Top management signature of the global information security policy document
		ISP-01.3B	The CSP shall communicate and make available the global information security policy to employees and to CSCs.	Q1-ISP-01.3B	Does the CSP communicate and make available the global information security policy to all employees and CSCs?	- Intranet - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
				Q2-ISP-01.3B	Does the CSP communicate and make available the global information security policy to all external employees?	- Web - email -Etc.
				Q3-ISP-01.3B	Does the CSP communicate and make available the global information security policy to all cloud service customers?	- Service contract - Web - email -Etc.
ISP-02	SECURITY POLICIES AND PROCEDURES	ISP-02.1B	The CSP shall derive policies and procedures from the global information security policy for all relevant subject matters, and document them according to a uniform structure, including at least the following aspects: (1) Objectives (2) Scope (3) Roles and responsibilities within the organization (4) Roles and dependencies on other organisations (especially CSCs and subservice providers) (5) Steps for the execution of the security strategy (6) Applicable legal and regulatory requirements.	Q1-ISP-02.1B	Has the CSP identified all the relevant subject matters within the scheme?	- Specific document that includes information about the relevant subject matters within the scheme - Global information security policy - Etc.

				Q2-ISP-02.1B	Does the CSP derive policies and procedures from the global information security policy for all relevant subject matters?	- Policies and procedures for each subject matter
				Q3-ISP-02.1B	Does the CSP document the policies and procedures derived from the global one following a uniform structure, including at least the following aspects? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objectives; • Scope; • Roles and responsibilities within the organization; • Roles and dependencies on other organisations (especially cloud customers and subservice organisations); • Steps for the execution of the security strategy; and • Applicable legal and regulatory requirements. 	- Policies and procedures template - Policies and procedures for each subject matter
		ISP-02.2B	The CSP shall communicate and make available the policies and procedures to all employees.	Q1-ISP-02.2B	Does the CSP communicate and make available the policies and procedures to all internal employees?	- Intranet - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
				Q2-ISP-02.2B	Does the CSP communicate and make available the policies and procedures to all external employees?	- Web - email - Etc.
		ISP-02.3B	The CSP's top management shall approve the security policies and procedures or delegate this responsibility to authorized bodies.	Q1-ISP-02.3B	Has the CSP defined the authorized bodies and its composition?	- Specific document that includes information about the authorized bodies and its composition

				Q2-ISP-02.3B	Are the security policies and procedures approved by the CSP's top management or by the authorized bodies?	- Top management or authorized bodies signature of the security policies and procedures
		ISP-02.4B	The CSP's subject matter experts shall review the policies and procedures for adequacy at least annually, when the global information security policy is modified, and when major changes may affect the security of the cloud service.	Q1-ISP-02.4B	Does every subject matter have an expert identified?	- Global information security policy document - Organizational structure - Another specific document
				Q2-ISP-02.4B	Every policy and procedure have been reviewed by the related expert at least annually, or when the global information security policy is updated, or when major changes may affect the security of the cloud service?	- Policies and procedures version control and change history
		ISP-02.5B	After a modification of procedures and policies, they shall be approved before they become effective, and then communicated and made available to employees.	Q1-ISP-02.5B	After an update of procedures and policies, have they been approved before they become effective?	- Signature of the new procedures and policies version
				Q2-ISP-02.5B	After an update of procedures and policies, have they been communicated and made available to internal and external employees?	- Intranet/WEB - email - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
ISP-03	EXCEPTIONS	ISP-03.1B	The CSP shall maintain a list of exceptions, limited in time, to the security policies and procedures, including associated controls.	Q1-ISP-03.1B	Does the CSP maintain a list of exceptions to the security policies and procedures?	- List of exceptions to the security policies and procedures - Records of updates of the list of exceptions
				Q2-ISP-03.1B	Does the list of exceptions include associated controls?	- Associated controls in the list of exceptions
				Q3-ISP-03.1B	Are the exceptions defined limited in time?	- Time limitation for each exception

		ISP-03.2B	The list of exceptions shall be reviewed at least annually.	Q1-ISP-03.2B	Is the list of exceptions being reviewed at least annually?	- List of exceptions document version control and change history - List of exceptions document review record
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3. Risk Management

Table 17. Checklist for RM basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

Control ID	Control	ReqID	Requirement	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
RM-01	RISK MANAGEMENT POLICY	RM-01.1B	The CSP shall define policies and procedures for the cloud service in accordance with ISP-02 and OIS-01.1B for the following aspects: (1) Identification of risks associated with the loss of confidentiality, integrity, availability and authenticity of information within the scope of the ISMS and assigning risk owners (2) Analysis of the probability and impact of occurrence and determination of the level of (3) Evaluation of the risk analysis based on defined criteria for risk acceptance and prioritisation of handling (4) Handling of risks through measures, including approval of authorisation and acceptance of residual risks by risk owners (5) Retain documented information of the activities to enable consistent, valid and comparable results.	Q1-RM-01.1B	Does the CSP define the policies and procedures for Risk management?	- Risk policy document - Risk management procedures

				Q2-RM-01.1B	Does the CSP define policies and procedures cover the identification of risks associated with the loss of confidentiality within the scope of the ISMS?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk policy document (it includes the identification of risks associated with the loss of confidentiality within the scope of the ISMS) - Risk management procedures (includes the identification of risks associated with the loss of confidentiality within the scope of the ISMS)
				Q3-RM-01.1B	Does the CSP define policies and procedures cover the identification of risks associated with the loss of integrity within the scope of the ISMS?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk policy document (includes the identification of risks associated with the loss of integrity within the scope of the ISMS) - Risk management procedures (includes the identification of risks associated with the loss of integrity within the scope of the ISMS)
				Q4-RM-01.1B	Does the CSP define policies and procedures cover the identification of risks associated with the loss of availability of information within the scope of the ISMS?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk policy document (includes the identification of risks associated with the loss of availability of information within the scope of the ISMS) - Risk management procedures (includes the identification of risks associated with the loss of availability of information within the scope of the ISMS)
				Q5-RM-01.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures cover the identification of risks associated with the loss of authenticity of information within the scope of the ISMS?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk policy document (includes the identification of risks associated with the loss of authenticity of information within the scope of the ISMS) - Risk management procedures

					(includes the identification of risks associated with the loss of authenticity of information within the scope of the ISMS)
				Q6-RM-01.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures cover the assignation of risk owners? - Risk policy document (includes the assignation of risk owners) - Risk management procedures (includes the assignation of risk owners)
				Q7-RM-01.1B	Does the CSP define policies and procedures cover the analysis of the probability and impact of occurrence and determination of the level of risk? - Risk policy document (includes the analysis of the probability and impact of occurrence and determination of the level of risk) - Risk management procedures (includes the analysis of the probability and impact of occurrence and determination of the level of risk)
				Q8-RM-01.1B	Does the CSP define policies and procedures cover the evaluation of the risk analysis based on defined criteria for risk acceptance and prioritisation of handling? - Risk policy document (includes the evaluation of the risk analysis based on defined criteria for risk acceptance and prioritisation of handling) - Risk management procedures (includes the evaluation of the risk analysis based on defined criteria for risk acceptance and prioritisation of handling)
				Q9-RM-01.1B	Does the CSP define policies and procedures covers the handling of risks through measures? - Risk policy document (includes the handling of risks through measures) - Risk management procedures
				Q10-RM-01.1B	Does the handling of risks through measures, includes the approval of - Risk policy document - Risk management procedures

					authorisation and acceptance of residual risks by risk owners?	(includes the handling of risks through measures)
RM-02	RISK ASSESSMENT IMPLEMENTATION	RM-02.1B	The CSP shall implement the policies and procedures covering risk assessment on the entire cloud service.	Q11-RM-01.1B	Does the CSP define policies and procedures cover the documentation of the activities implemented to enable consistent, valid and comparable results?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk policy document (includes the documentation of the activities implemented to enable consistent, valid and comparable results) - Risk management procedures (includes the documentation of the activities implemented to enable consistent, valid and comparable results)
		RM-02.2B	The CSP shall make the results of the risk assessment available to relevant internal parties and relevant information shall be made available to defined external parties.	Q1-RM-02.2B	Does the CSP make the results of the risk assessment available to relevant stakeholders?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk assessment results - Intranet/WEB - email - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		RM-02.3B	The CSP shall review and revise the risk assessment at least annually, and after each major change that may affect the security of the cloud service.	Q1-RM-02.3B	Does the CSP review and revise the risk assessment at least annually?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Top management or authorized bodies signature of the risk assessment at least annually - records of this review in logs with dates
				Q2-RM-02.3B	Does the CSP review and revise the risk assessment after each major change that may affect the security of the cloud service?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - List of major changes - Top management or authorized bodies signature of the risk assessment after major changes
RM-03	RISK TREATMENT IMPLEMENTATION	RM-03.1B	The CSP shall prioritize risks according to their criticality.	Q1-RM-03.1B	Does the CSP shall prioritize risks according to their criticality?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - List of prioritized risks according to their criticality

		RM-03.2B	The CSP shall document and implement a plan to treat risks according to their priority level by reducing or avoiding them through security controls, by sharing them, or by retaining them.	Q1-RM-03.2B	Does the CSP document a risk treatment plan to treat risks according to their priority level?	- Risk treatment plan according to their priority level
				Q2-RM-03.2B	Does the risk treatment plan contemplate the reducing or avoiding the risks through security controls, by sharing them, or by retaining them?	- Risk treatment plan (contemplates the reducing or avoiding the risks through security controls, by sharing them, or by retaining them)
				Q3-RM-03.2B	Does the CSP implement the defined risk treatment plan?	Evidence of actions defined in the risk treatment plan
		RM-03.3B	The risk treatment plan shall reduce the risk level to a threshold that the risk owners deem acceptable (Residual Risk).	Q1-RM-03.3B	Does the risk treatment plan reduce the risk level to a threshold that the risk owners deem acceptable (Residual Risk)?	- Risk threshold evolution through time.
				Q2-RM-03.3B	Is it defined what a residual risk is?	- Formal and documented definition of "Residual Risk"
		RM-03.4B	The CSP shall make the risk treatment plan available to relevant internal parties with appropriately summarised and abstracted versions made available both internally and to authorized external parties.	Q1-RM-03.4B	Does the CSP make the risk treatment plan available to relevant internal parties with appropriately summarised and abstracted versions?	- Risk treatment plan - Intranet/WEB - email - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
				Q2-RM-03.4B	Are abstracted versions made available both internally and to authorized external parties?	
		RM-03.5B	If the CSP shares risks with the CSC, the shared risks shall be associated to Complementary User Entity Controls (CUECs) and described in the user documentation.	Q1-RM-03.5B	If the CSP shares risks with the CSC, are the shared risks associated to Complementary User Entity Controls (CUECs)?	- List of Complementary User Entity Controls for the risks shared with the CSC - Trazability between risks shared by CSP and Complementary User Entity Controls (CUECs)
				Q1-RM-03.5B	If the CSP shares risks with the CSC, are the shared risks described in the user documentation?	- User documentation including the description of the shared risks

		RM-03.6B	The CSP shall revise the risk treatment plan every time the risk assessment is modified.	Q1-RM-03.6B	Does the CSP review the risk treatment plan every time the risk assessment is revised?	- Risk treatment plan version control and change history - Risk treatment plan review record
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4. Human Resources

Table 18. Checklist for HR basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

Control ID	Control	ReqID	Requirement	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
HR-01	HUMAN RESOURCE POLICIES	HR-01.1B	The CSP shall classify information security-sensitive positions according to their level of risk, including positions related to IT administration and to the provisioning of the cloud service in the production environment, and all positions with access to CSC data or system components.	Q1-HR-01.1B	Are the security-sensitive positions classified according to their level of risk?	- Competence Position Document or similar - Policy document (roles section)
				Q2-HR-01.1B	Are the IT administration positions included in that classification?	- Competence Position Document or similar (includes the administration positions)
				Q3-HR-01.1B	Are the cloud service provisioning positions included in that classification?	- Competence Position Document or similar (includes the cloud service provisioning positions)
				Q4-HR-01.1B	Are all the positions with access to cloud customer data included in that classification?	- Competence Position Document or similar (includes all the positions with access to cloud customer data)
				Q5-HR-01.1B	Are all the positions with access to system components / assets included in that classification?	- Competence Position Document or similar (includes all the positions with access to system components)

		HR-01.2B	The CSP shall include in its employment contracts or on a dedicated code of conduct or ethics an overarching agreement by employees to act ethically in their professional duties.	Q1-HR-01.2B	- Does there exist an overarching agreement containing rules to act ethically in professionals' duties?	Overarching agreement with rules to act ethically
				Q2-HR-01.2B	- Is this overarching agreement included in the internal employees' contract or in a dedicated code of conduct or ethics?	Internal employees' contracts or dedicated Code of Conduct/Ethics document
				Q3-HR-01.2B	- Is this overarching agreement included in the external employees' contract or in a dedicated code of conduct or ethics?	Internal employees' contracts or dedicated Code of Conduct/Ethics document
		HR-01.3B	The CSP shall define and implement a policy that describes actions to take in the event of violations of policies and procedures or applicable legal and regulatory requirements, including at least the following aspects: (1) Verifying whether a violation has occurred; and (2) Consideration of the nature and severity of the violation and its impact	Q1-HR-01.3B	- Has the CSP documented a policy that describes actions to take in the event of violations of policies and procedures or applicable legal and regulatory requirements?	- Documented Policy, section dedicated to violations, instructions, applicable legal and regulatory requirements
				Q2-HR-01.3B	- Does the documented policy include at least the following aspects? • Verifying whether a violation has occurred; and • Consideration of the nature and severity of the violation and its impact	- Documented Policy (includes verifying whether a violation has occurred & Consideration of the nature and severity of the violation and its impact)
				Q3-HR-01.3B	Has the CSP communicated the policy that describes actions to take in the event of violations of policies and instructions or applicable legal and regulatory requirements?	- Evidence related to the policy communication: - Intranet/WEB - email - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.

				Q4-HR-01.3B	Are there evidence that the policy that describes actions to take in the event of violations of policies and instructions or applicable legal and regulatory requirements has been implemented?	-Records related to the policy implementation such as warnings and signed documents in accordance with what it is defined in the policy for the different levels of violations
		HR-01.4B	If disciplinary measures are defined in this policy, then the employees of the CSP shall be informed about possible disciplinary measures and the use of these disciplinary measures shall be appropriately documented.	Q1-HR-01.4B	Does the policy that describes actions to take in the event of violations of policies and instructions or applicable legal and regulatory requirements contain disciplinary measures?	- HR-03 Policy document
				Q2-HR-01.4B	Have the internal employees been informed about possible disciplinary measures?	Mechanisms used to inform internal employees about disciplinary methods: - Intranet/WEB - email - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
				Q3-HR01.4B	Have the external employees been informed about possible disciplinary measure?	- Mechanisms used to inform external employees about disciplinary methods - email - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
				Q4-HR01.4	Have the use of the disciplinary measures been appropriately documented?	- Documented disciplinary measures way of use

HR-02	VERIFICATION OF QUALIFICATION AND TRUSTWORTHINESS	HR-02.1B	The CSP shall assess the competence and integrity of all its employees with access to CSC data or system components under the CSP's responsibility, or who are responsible to provide the cloud service in the production environment before commencement of employment in a position classified in objective HR-01.	Q1-HR-02.1B	Does the CSP assess the competence and integrity of all its employees with access to CSC data or system components under the CSP's responsibility, or who are responsible to provide the cloud service in the production environment before commencement of employment in a position classified in objective HR-01?	- Documented assess results
		HR-02.2B	The CSP shall assess the competence and integrity of its employees of the CSP before commencement of employment in a position with a higher risk classification that their previous position within the company.	Q1-HR-03.2B	Does the CSP assess the competence and integrity of its employees of the CSP before commencement of employment in a position with a higher risk classification that their previous position within the company?	- Documented assess results
		HR-02.3B	The extent of the assessment shall be proportional to the business context, the sensitivity of the information that will be accessed by the employee, and the associated risks.	Q1-HR-02.2B	Is the extent of the assessment proportional to the business context, the sensitivity of the information that will be accessed by the employee, and the associated risks?	- Assessment compliance review record
HR-03	EMPLOYEE TERMS AND CONDITIONS	HR-03.1B	The CSP shall ensure that all employees are required by their employment terms and conditions to comply with all applicable information security policies and procedures.	Q1-HR-03.1B	Does the CSP ensure that all employees comply with all applicable information security policies and procedures?	- Employment terms and conditions - Audit results of internal employees
		HR-03.2B	The CSP shall ensure that the employment terms for all employees include a non-disclosure provision, which shall cover any information that has been obtained or generated as part of the cloud service, even if anonymised and decontextualized.	Q1-HR-03.2B	Does the employment terms for all internal employees include a non-disclosure provision?	- Non-disclosure provision document included in the employment terms and conditions for internal employees

				Q2-HR-03.2B	Does the employment terms for all external employees include a non-disclosure provision?	- Non-disclosure provision document included in the employment terms and conditions for external employees
				Q3-HR-03.2	Does the non-disclosure provision cover any information that has been obtained or generated as part of the cloud service, even if anonymised and decontextualized?	- Non-disclosure provision document included in the employment terms and conditions
		HR-03.3B	The CSP shall give a presentation of all applicable information security policies and procedures to employees before granting them any access to CSC data, the production environment, or any functional component thereof.	Q1-HR-03.3B	Has the CSP given a presentation of all applicable information security policies and procedures to internal employees before granting them any access to customer data, the production environment, or any component thereof?	- Information security policies and procedure presentation + delivery evidence
				Q2-HR-03.3B	Has the CSP given a presentation of all applicable information security policies and procedures to external employees before granting them any access to customer data, the production environment, or any component thereof?	- Information security policies and procedure presentation + delivery evidence
HR-04	SECURITY AWARENESS AND TRAINING	HR-04.1B	The CSP shall define a security awareness and training program that covers the following aspects: (1) Handling system components used to provide the cloud service in the production environment in accordance with applicable policies and procedures; (2) Handling CSC data in accordance with applicable policies and instructions and applicable legal and regulatory requirements; (3) Information about the current threat situation; and	Q1-HR-04.1B	Has the CSP defined a security awareness and training program?	- Documented security awareness and training program

			(4) Correct behaviour in the event of security incidents.			
				Q2-HR-04.1B	Does the defined security awareness and training program contain at least the following topics? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Handling system components used to provide the cloud service in the production environment in accordance with applicable policies and procedures; • Handling cloud customer data in accordance with applicable policies and instructions and applicable legal and regulatory requirements; • Information about the current threat situation; and • Correct behaviour in the event of security incidents. 	- Security awareness and training program (includes Handling system components, Handling cloud customer data, Information about the current threat situation and Correct behaviour in the event of security incidents)
		HR-04.2B	The CSP shall review their security awareness and training program based on changes to policies and procedures and the current threat situation.	Q1-HR-04.2B	Is the security awareness and training program kept updated according to the changes to policies and instructions and the current threat situation?	- Documented history of the security and awareness training program with references to policies/instructions/threat situation
		HR-04.3B	The CSP shall ensure that all employees complete the security awareness and training program defined for them.	Q1-HR-04.3B	Have all the CSP employees received the defined security awareness and training program?	- Training delivery records
HR-05	TERMINATION OR CHANGE IN EMPLOYMENT	HR-05.1B	The CSP shall communicate to employees their ongoing responsibilities relating to information security when their employment is terminated or changed.	Q1-HR-05.1B	Does the CSP communicate to employees their ongoing responsibilities relating to information security when their employment is terminated or changed?	- Employee termination/position change document

		HR-05.2B	The CSP shall apply a specific procedure to revoke the access rights and process appropriately the accounts and assets of employees when their employment is terminated or changed.	Q1-HR-05.2B	Have the CSP defined a specific procedure to revoke the access rights and process appropriately the accounts and assets of employees when their employment is terminated or changed?	- Documented specific procedure to revoke the access rights and process appropriately the accounts and assets of employees when their employment is terminated or changed
				Q2-HR-05.2B	Is this procedure applied to internal employees?	- Evidence of the new access rights and process appropriately the accounts and assets to internal employees
				Q3-HR-05.2B	Is this procedure applied to external employees?	- Evidence of the new access rights and process appropriately the accounts and assets to external employees
HR-06	CONFIDENTIALITY AGREEMENTS	HR-06.1B	The CSP shall ensure that non-disclosure or confidentiality agreements are agreed with internal employees, external service providers and suppliers.	Q1-HR-06.1B	Does the CSP have non-disclosure or confidentiality agreements to rule the relationship between internal employees and external service providers and suppliers	- Documented Non-disclosure or confidentiality agreements to rule the relationship between internal employees and external service providers and suppliers
				Q2-HR-06.1B	Does the CSP ensure the agreement between internal employees and external service providers and suppliers based on the defined non-disclosure agreement?	- Signed non-disclosure or confidentiality agreements to rule the relationship between internal employees and external service providers and suppliers

5. Asset management

Table 19. Checklist for AM basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

Control ID	Control	ReqID	Requirement	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
AM-01	ASSET INVENTORY	AM-01.1B	The CSP shall define and implement policies and procedures for maintaining an inventory of assets.	Q1-AM-01.1B	Does the CSP define policies and procedures for maintaining an inventory of assets?	- Documented policies and procedures
				Q2-AM-01.1B	Does the CSP implement the defined policies and procedures for maintaining an inventory of assets?	- Documented Inventory of assets
		AM-01.2B	The CSP shall record for each asset the information needed to apply the risk management procedure defined in RM-01.	Q1-AM-01.2B	Does the CSP record for each asset the information needed to apply the risk management procedure defined in RM-01?	- Documented Information needed for each asset to apply risk management in the inventory of assets
AM-02	ACCEPTABLE USE AND SAFE HANDLING OF ASSETS POLICY	AM-02.1B	The CSP shall define and implement policies and procedures as defined in ISP-02 for acceptable use and safe handling of assets. When removable media is used in the technical infrastructure or for IT administration tasks, this media shall be dedicated to a single use.	Q1-AM-02.1B	Does the CSP define policies and procedures for acceptable use and safe handling of assets?	- Policies and procedures document - Global security policies
				Q2-AM-02.1B	When removable media is used in the technical infrastructure or for IT administration tasks, is this media dedicated to a single use?	
AM-03	COMMISSIONING AND DECOMMISSIONING	AM-03.1B	The CSP shall define and implement a procedure for the commissioning of hardware that is used to provide the cloud service in the production environment, based on applicable policies and procedures.	Q1-AM-03.1B	Does the CSP define a procedure for the commissioning of hardware that is used to provide the cloud service in the production environment, based on applicable policies and procedures?	- Documented Hardware commissioning procedure

				Q2-AM-03.1B	Does CSP implement a procedure for the commissioning of hardware that is used to provide the cloud service in the production environment, based on applicable policies and procedures?	- Evidence related to procedure for the commissioning of hardware implementation: - HW commissioning records / Implementation checklist or equivalent
		AM-03.2B	The CSP shall define and implement a procedure for the decommissioning of hardware that is used to provide the cloud service in the production environment, including the complete and permanent deletion of the data or the proper destruction of the media and requiring approval based on applicable policies.	Q1-AM-03.2B	Does the CSP define a procedure for the decommissioning of hardware that is used to provide the cloud service in the production environment, based on applicable policies and procedures?	- Documented Hardware decommissioning procedure
				Q2-AM-03.2B	Does CSP implement a procedure for the decommissioning of hardware that is used to provide the cloud service in the production environment, based on applicable policies and procedures?	- Evidence related to procedure for the decommissioning of hardware implementation: - HW decommissioning records / Implementation checklist or equivalent
				Q3-AM-03.2B	Does the decommissioning procedure include the complete and permanent deletion of the data or the proper destruction of the media and requiring approval based on applicable policies?	- Decommissioning Procedure -Evidence of procedure application in real cases
AM-04	ACCEPTABLE USE, SAFE HANDLING AND RETURN OF ASSETS	AM-04.1B	The CSP shall ensure and document that all employees are committed to the policies and procedures for acceptable use and safe handling of assets in the situations described in AM-02.	Q1-AM-04.1B	Does the CSP ensure that internal and external employees are committed to the established policy and procedures related to assets commissioning and decommissioning?	-Evidence of actions to ensure employees commitment
AM-05	ASSET CLASSIFICATION AND LABELLING	AM-05.1B	The CSP shall document an asset classification schema that reflects for each asset the protection needs of the categories of information it may process, store, or transmit.	Q1-AM-05.1B	For every asset included in the Asset Inventory, has the CSP documented an asset classification scheme that reflects the protection needs of the	- Asset classification scheme in the Assets Inventory or in a separate document

					information it processes, stores, or transmits?	
		AM-05.2B	When applicable, the CSP shall label all assets according to their classification in the asset classification schema.	Q1-AM-05.2B	Has the CSP labelled (when applicable) each asset according to the asset classification scheme?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - List of assets linked to their labels / tags and other configuration information - Photograph (or other recording means) of the labelled assets - Asset classification Scheme

6. Physical security

Table 20. Checklist for PS basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

Control ID	Control	ReqID	Requirement	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
PS-01	PHYSICAL SECURITY PERIMETERS	PS-01.1B	The CSP shall define security perimeters in the buildings and premises related to the cloud service provided.	Q1-PS-01.1B	Does the CSP define security perimeters in the buildings related to the cloud service provided?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Building plans - Security perimeter plans - A CSP shall establish secure areas to protect valuable information and assets that only authorized people can access
				Q2-PS-01.1B	Does the CSP define security perimeters in the premises related to the cloud service provided?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Building plans - Security perimeter plans, identifying which are the ones concerning the cloud service
		PS-01.2B	The CSP shall define at least two security areas, with at least one sensitive area covering sensitive activities such as the buildings and premises hosting the information system for the provision of the cloud service, and at least	Q1-PS-01.2B	Does the CSP define a security area covering sensitive activities such as the buildings and premises hosting the information system for the provision of the cloud service?	- Documented security area plan, establishing the two security areas, as per the requirement and who has access to them and per which terms

			one public area covering at least all remaining buildings and premises.			
				Q2-PS-01.2B	Does the CSP define a security public area covering at least all remaining buildings and premises?	-Documented security area plan
		PS-01.3B	The CSP shall define and implement a set of security requirements for each security area in a policy and procedures according to ISP-02.	Q1-PS-01.3B	Does the CSP define a set of security requirements for each security area in a policy according to ISP-02 (Information Security Policy)?	- Documented security requirements for each security area - Documented physical policy
				Q2-PS-01.3B	Does the CSP communicate the set of security requirements?	- Evidence related to the set of security requirements communication: - Intranet - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
PS-02	PHYSICAL SITE ACCESS CONTROL	PS-02.1B	The CSP shall define and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 related to the physical access control to the security areas matching the requirements defined in PS-01 and based on the principles defined in IAM-01.	Q1-PS-02.1B	Does the CSP define policies and procedures related to the physical access control to the security areas?	-Documented policies and procedures
				Q2-PS-02.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures related to the physical access control to the security areas?	-Access control systems to prevent unauthorised access (i.e., EACS, intercoms, videophones, CCTV cameras, mechanical locking devices operated by keys or codes, etc.)
		PS-02.2B	The access control policy shall require at least one authentication factor for accessing any non-public area.	Q1-PS-02.2B	Does the access control policy require at least one authentication factor for accessing any non-public area?	- Authentication factors (i.e., Fingerprint, PIN, etc.)
		PS-02.3B	The access control policy shall describe the physical access control derogations in case of emergency.	Q1-PS-02.3B	Does the access control policy describe the physical access control derogations in case of emergency?	- Documented description of the physical access control derogations in case of emergency

		PS-02.4B	The CSP shall display at the entrance of all non-public perimeters a warning concerning the limits and access conditions to the corresponding areas.	Q1-PS-02.4B	Does the CSP display at the entrance of all non-public perimeters a warning concerning the limits and access conditions to the corresponding areas?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wall chats - Specific warning signals - Etc.
		PS-02.5B	The CSP shall protect security perimeters with security measures to detect and prevent unauthorised access in a timely manner so that it does not compromise the information security of the cloud service.	Q1-PS-02.5B	Does the CSP protect security perimeters with security measures to detect and prevent unauthorised access in a timely manner so that it does not compromise the information security of the cloud service?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CCTV (closed circuit television) Security System. - Access control systems. Access control systems serve to restrict entry only to authorized personnel. - Motion sensors. - Fibre optic detection systems. - Ground Radar Systems. - Microwave barriers. - Electrified fences. - Microphone cable fence disturbance sensors. - Etc.
PS-03	WORKING IN NON-PUBLIC AREAS	PS-03.1B	The CSP shall define and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 concerning work in non-public areas.	Q1-PS-03.1B	Does the CSP define policies and procedures concerning work in non-public areas?	-Documented policies and procedures
				Q2-PS-03.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures concerning work in non-public areas?	-Access control systems to prevent unauthorised access (i.e., EACS, intercoms, videophones, CCTV cameras, mechanical locking devices operated by keys or codes, etc.)
PS-04	EQUIPMENT PROTECTION	PS-04.1B	The CSP shall define and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 concerning the protection of equipment and including at least the following aspects: (1) Protecting power and communications cabling from interception, interference or damage;	Q1-PS-04.1B	Does the CSP define policies and procedures concerning the protection of equipment including protecting power and communications cabling from interception, interference or damage?	-Documented policies and procedures

			(2) Protecting equipment during maintenance operations; (3) Protecting equipment holding CSC data during transport.		
				Q2-PS-04.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures concerning the protection of equipment including protecting power and communications cabling from interception, interference or damage? - Power and telecommunications lines undergrounded - Power cables isolated - Installation of reinforced ducts and locked rooms or boxes at inspection and termination points - Electromagnetic shielding for cable protection - Access controlled to cable rooms and patch panels - Etc.
				Q3-PS-04.1B	Does the CSP define policies and procedures concerning the protection of equipment including protecting equipment during maintenance operations? - Documented policies and procedures
				Q4-PS-04.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures concerning the protection of equipment including protecting equipment during maintenance operations? - Service interval recommendations and supplier specifications - List of authorized maintenance personnel - Records of all failures, real or suspected, as well as all preventive and corrective maintenance - Maintenance requirements required by insurance policies

				Q5-PS-04.1B	Does the CSP define policies and procedures concerning the protection of equipment including protecting equipment holding CSC data during transport.	-Documented policies and procedures
				Q6-PS-04.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures concerning the protection of equipment including protecting equipment holding CSC data during transport.	- Reliable transport or courier. It can also be an approved transport or courier, in agreement with the policies and procedures (see below) - List of authorized couriers - Procedures to verify the identity of couriers; - Packaging protect specifications - Records identifying the content of the media, the protection applied, as well as reflecting the moments of transfer to custodians and reception at destination.
		PS-04.2B	The CSP shall use encryption on the removable media and the backup media intended to move between security areas according to the sensitivity of the data stored on the media	Q1-PS-04.2B	Does the CSP use encryption on the removable media intended to move between security areas?	- Compliant encryption algorithms and tools (i.e., Self-Encrypting USB Drives, Media Encryption Software, File Encryption Software) - Secure password management tool
				Q2-PS-04.2B	Does the CSP shall use encryption on the backup media intended to move between security areas?	- Backup software
				Q3-PS-04.2B	Is the level of encryption according to the sensitivity of the data stored on the media?	- Encrypted logs

PS-05	PROTECTION AGAINST EXTERNAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL THREATS	PS-05.1B	The CSP shall define and implement a set of requirements related to external and environmental threats in a policy according to ISP-02, addressing the following risks in accordance with the applicable legal and contractual requirements: (1) Faults in planning; (2) Unauthorised access; (3) Force majeure, including epidemiological risks; (4) Insufficient surveillance; (5) Insufficient air-conditioning; (6) Fire and smoke; (7) Water; (8) Power failure; and (9) Air ventilation and filtration.	Q1-PS-05.1B	Does the CSP define a set of security requirements related to external and environmental threats in a policy according to Information Security Policies (SP-02)?	- Documented policy
				Q2-PS-05.1B	Does the policy address fault in planning?	- Documented Policy & security requirements encompasses (faults in planning)
				Q3-PS-05.1B	Does the policy address unauthorised access?	- Documented Policy & security requirements encompasses (unauthorised access)
				Q4-PS-05.1B	Does the policy address insufficient surveillance?	- Documented Policy & security requirements encompasses (insufficient surveillance)
				Q5-PS-05.1B	Does the policy address insufficient air-conditioning?	- Documented Policy & security requirements encompasses (what to do when there is a lack of insufficient air-conditioning - e.g., high temperature)
				Q6-PS-05.1B	Does the policy address fire and smoke?	- Documented Policy & security requirements encompasses (fire and smoke)

				Q7-PS-05.1B	Does the policy address water?	- Documented Policy & security requirements encompasses (water)
				Q8-PS-05.1B	Does the policy address power failure?	- Documented Policy & security requirements encompasses (power failure)
				Q9-PS-05.1B	Does the policy address air ventilation and filtration?	- Documented Policy & security requirements encompasses (air ventilation and filtration)

7. Operational security

Table 21. Checklist for OPS basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

Control ID	Control	ReqID	Requirement	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
OPS-01	CAPACITY MANAGEMENT – PLANNING	OPS-01.1B	The CSP shall define and implement procedures to plan for capacities and resources (personnel and IT resources), which shall include forecasting future capacity requirements in order to identify usage trends and manage system overload.	Q1-OPS-01.1B	Does the CSP define procedures to plan for capacities and resources (personnel and IT resources)?	- Capacity plan - Specific capacity procedures
				Q2-OPS-01.1B	Do procedures include forecasting future capacity requirements in order to identify usage trends and manage system overload?	- Capacity plan (encompasses future capacity requirements) - Specific capacity procedures
				Q3-OPS-01.1B	Does the CSP implement procedures to plan for capacities and resources (personnel and IT resources)?	- Capacity plan audit
		OPS-01.2B	The CSP shall meet the requirements included in contractual agreements with CSCs regarding the provision of the cloud service in case of capacity bottlenecks or personnel and IT resources outages.	Q1-OPS-01.2B	Does the CSP meet the requirements included in contractual agreements with cloud customers regarding the provision of the cloud service in case of capacity bottlenecks?	- Monitoring reports - Contractual agreements - Non-conformities to the contract (if there are non-compliances)

				Q2-OPS-01.2B	Does the CSP meet the requirements included in contractual agreements with cloud customers regarding the provision of the cloud service in case of IT resources outages?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring reports - Non-conformities to the contract/SLA (if there are non-compliances) - Contractual agreements
OPS-02	CAPACITY MANAGEMENT – MONITORING	OPS-02.1B	The CSP shall document and implement technical and organizational safeguards for the monitoring of provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services to ensure compliance with the service level agreement.	Q1-OPS-02.1B	Does the CSP document technical safeguards for the monitoring of provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services to ensure compliance with the service level agreement?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multidimensional QoS prediction methods
				Q2-OPS-02.1B	Does the CSP implement technical safeguards for the monitoring of provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services to ensure compliance with the service level agreement?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Service level agreement - SLA compliance report
				Q3-OPS-02.1B	Does the CSP define organizational safeguards for the monitoring of provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services to ensure compliance with the service level agreement?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multi-dimensional QoS measures
				Q4-OPS-02.1B	Does the CSP implement organizational safeguards for the monitoring of provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services to ensure compliance with the service level agreement?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Service level agreement - SLA compliance report
OPS-03	CAPACITY MANAGEMENT – CONTROLLING OF RESOURCES	OPS-03.1B	The CSP shall enable CSCs to control and monitor the allocation of the system resources assigned to them, if the corresponding cloud capabilities are exposed to the CSCs.	Q1-OPS-03.1B	Does the CSP enable CSCs to control and monitor the allocation of the system resources assigned to them, if the corresponding cloud capabilities are exposed to the CSCs?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contractual agreement - SLA - Privileges to use the monitoring and control tools

OPS-04	PROTECTION AGAINST MALWARE – POLICIES	OPS-04.1B	The CSP shall define and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 to protect its systems and its customers from malware, covering at least the following aspects: (1) Use of system-specific protection mechanisms; (2) Operating protection programs on system components under the responsibility of the CSP that are used to provide the cloud service in the production environment; and (3) Operation of protection programs for employees' terminal equipment	Q1-OPS-04.1B	Does the CSP define policies and procedures according to ISP-02 to protect its systems and its customers from malware, covering the use of system-specific protection mechanisms?	-Documented policies and procedures
				Q2-OPS-04.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 to protect its systems and its customers from malware, covering the use of system-specific protection mechanisms?	- System-specific protection mechanisms - System-specific protection mechanism deployment report - Audit report - policies and procedures
				Q3-OPS-04.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures according to ISP-02 to protect its systems and its customers from malware, covering operating protection programs on system components under the responsibility of the CSP that are used to provide the cloud service in the production environment?	-Documented policies and procedures
				Q4-OPS-04.1B	Does the CSP communicate policies and procedures according to ISP-02 to protect its systems and its customers from malware, covering operating protection programs on system components under the responsibility of the CSP that are used to provide the cloud service in the production environment?	-Intranet/WEB - email - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.

				Q5-OPS-04.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 to protect its systems and its customers from malware, covering operating protection programs on system components under the responsibility of the CSP that are used to provide the cloud service in the production environment?	- Operating protection programs on system components under the responsibility of the CSP - Operating protection programs deployment report - Audit report
				Q6-OPS-04.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures according to ISP-02 to protect its systems and its customers from malware, covering operation of protection programs for employees' terminal equipment.	- Documented policies and procedures
				Q7-OPS-04.1B	Does the CSP document, communicate and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 to protect its systems and its customers from malware, covering operation of protection programs for employees' terminal equipment.	- Intranet/WEB - email - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
				Q8-OPS-04.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 to protect its systems and its customers from malware, covering the operation of protection programs for employees' terminal equipment.	- Operation of protection programs for employees' terminal equipment - Operation of protection programs for employees' terminal equipment deployment report - Audit report
OPS-05	PROTECTION AGAINST MALWARE – IMPLEMENTATION	OPS-05.1B	The CSP shall deploy malware protection, if technically feasible, on all systems that support delivery of the cloud service in the production environment, according to policies and procedures.	Q1-OPS-05.1B	Does the CSP deploy malware protection, if technically feasible, on all systems that support delivery of the cloud service in the production environment?	- Malware protection programs deployed

				Q2-OPS-05.1B	Is the deploy of malware protection according to policies and procedures?	-Documented policies and procedures for malware protection - Malware deployment report
OPS-06	DATA BACKUP AND RECOVERY – POLICIES	OPS-06.1B	The CSP shall document, communicate and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 for data backup and recovery.	Q1-OPS-06.1B	Does the CSP define policies and procedures according to ISP-02 for data backup and recovery?	-Documented policies and procedures
				Q2-OPS-06.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 for data backup and recovery?	- A filled form or screenshot identifying which information was requested to be backed up, the requester, the date of request, the date when the backup was performed, the result of the backup procedure (successful / fail) and where the backup was stored. - A general schedule of the backup to be performed, identifying which information is planned to be backed up, the requester, the dates planned for backup, and where the backup must be stored
OPS-07	DATA BACKUP AND RECOVERY – MONITORING	OPS-07.1B	The CSP shall document and implement technical and organizational measures to monitor the execution of data backups in accordance to the policies and procedures defined in OPS-06.	Q1-OPS-07.1B	Does the CSP document technical and organizational measures to monitor the execution of data backups?	- Documented technical and organizational measures
				Q2-OPS-07.1B	Does the CSP implement technical and organizational measures to monitor the execution of data backups?	- Documented technical and organizational measures report
				Q3-OPS-07.1B	Are the technical and organizational measures to monitor the execution of data backups in accordance with	- Documented conformity report

					the policies and procedures defined in OPS- 06?	
OPS-08	DATA BACKUP AND RECOVERY – REGULAR TESTING	OPS-08.1B	The CSP shall test the restore procedures at least annually.	Q1-OPS-08.1B	Does the CSP test the restore procedures at least annually?	- A filled form or screenshot identifying which information was requested to be restored, the requester, the date of request, the date when the restore was performed, and the result of the restore procedure (successful / fail)
		OPS-08.2B	The CSP shall not use CSC data, but only data in test accounts controlled by CSP staff for testing purposes.	Q1-OPS-08.1B	Does the CSP use CSC data, except for data in test accounts controlled by CSP staff for testing purposes? --> NO	
OPS-09	DATA BACKUP AND RECOVERY – STORAGE	OPS-09.1B	The CSP shall transfer backup data to a remote location or transport them on backup media to a remote location.	Q1-OPS-09.1B	Does the CSP transfer backup data to a remote location or transport them on backup media to a remote location?	- Data transport report
		OPS-09.2B	When the backup data is transmitted to a remote location via a network, the transmission of the data takes place in an encrypted form that corresponds to the state-of-the-art (cf. CKM-02).	Q1-OPS-09.2B	When the backup data is transmitted to a remote location via a network, do the transmission of the data takes place in an encrypted form that corresponds to the state-of-the-art (cf. CKM- 02)?	- Data transport report (encompasses an encrypted form that corresponds to the state-of-the-art (cf. CKM- 02))
OPS-10	LOGGING AND MONITORING – POLICIES	OPS-10.1B	The CSP shall define and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 that govern the logging and monitoring of events on system components under its responsibility.	Q1-OPS-10.1B	Does the CSP define policies and procedures according to ISP-02 that govern the logging of events on system components under its responsibility?	- Documented policies and procedures
				Q2-OPS-10.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 that govern the logging of events on system components under its responsibility?	- Documented Reports - Logs

				Q2-OPS-10.2S	Do policies and procedures cover the specifications for activating, stopping, and pausing the various logs?	- Documented policies and procedures - Policies and procedures compliance report
				Q3-OPS-10.2S	Do policies and procedures cover the Information regarding the purpose and retention period of the logs?	- Documented policies and procedures - Policies and procedures compliance report
				Q4-OPS-10.2S	Do policies and procedures cover the definition of roles and responsibilities for setting up and monitoring logging?	- Documented policies and procedures - Policies and procedures compliance report
				Q5-OPS-10.2S	Do policies and procedures cover the definition of log data that may be transferred to CSCs and technical requirements of such log forwarding?	- Documented policies and procedures - Policies and procedures compliance report
				Q6-OPS-10.2S	Do policies and procedures cover the Information about timestamps in event creation?	- Documented policies and procedures - Policies and procedures compliance report
				Q7-OPS-10.2S	Do policies and procedures cover the time synchronisation of system components?	- Documented policies and procedures - Policies and procedures compliance report
				Q8-OPS-10.2S	Do policies and procedures cover the compliance with legal and regulatory frameworks?	- Documented policies and procedures - Policies and procedures compliance report
OPS-11	LOGGING AND MONITORING – DERIVED DATA MANAGEMENT	OPS-11.1B	The CSP shall define and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 that govern the secure handling of cloud service derived data.	Q1-OPS-11.1B	Does the CSP define policies and procedures according to ISP-02 that govern the secure handling of derived data?	- Documented policies and procedures

				Q1-OPS-11.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 that govern the secure handling of derived data?	- Records derived from the implementation of the policies and procedures covering the governance of the secure handling of derived data - Logs
OPS-12	LOGGING AND MONITORING – IDENTIFICATION OF EVENTS	OPS-12.1B	The CSP shall monitor log data in order to identify security events that might lead to security incidents, in accordance with the logging and monitoring requirements, and the identified events shall be reported to the appropriate departments for timely assessment and remediation.	Q1-OPS-12.1B	Does the CSP monitor log data in order to identify events that might lead to security incidents, in accordance with the logging and monitoring requirements?	- Documented monitoring of log data (Logs) - Documented security incidents
				Q2-OPS-12.1B	Are identified events reported to the appropriate departments for timely assessment and remediation?	- Security incidents notification event report
OPS-13	LOGGING AND MONITORING – ACCESS, STORAGE AND DELETION	OPS-13.1B	The CSP shall store all log data in an integrity-protected and aggregated form that allow its evaluation.	Q1-OPS-13.1B	Does the CSP store all log data in an integrity-protected and aggregated form that allow its centralized evaluation?	- Log data Database
		OPS-13.2B	The communication between the assets to be logged and the logging servers shall be authenticated and protected in integrity and confidentiality whenever possible.	Q1-OPS-13.2B	Is the communication between the assets to be logged and the logging servers authenticated in integrity?	Logs
				Q2-OPS-13.2B	Is the communication between the assets to be logged and the logging servers authenticated in confidentiality?	Logs
				Q3-OPS-13.2B	Is the communication between the assets to be logged and the logging servers protected in integrity?	Logs
				Q4-OPS-13.2B	Is the communication between the assets to be logged and the logging servers protected in confidentiality?	Logs

		OPS-13.3B	Log data shall be deleted when no longer required for the purpose for which it was collected.	Q1-OPS-13.3B	Are log data deleted when it is no longer required for the purpose for which they were collected?	- Log data deletion record
OPS-14	LOGGING AND MONITORING – ATTRIBUTION	OPS-14.1B	The log data generated allows an unambiguous identification of user accesses at the CSC level to support analysis during and following a security incident.	Q1-OPS-14.1B	Does the log data generated allows an unambiguous identification of user accesses at the CSC level to support analysis in the event of an incident?	- Logs
OPS-15	LOGGING AND MONITORING – CONFIGURATION	OPS-15.1B	The CSP shall restrict access to system components under its responsibility, that are used for logging and monitoring, with strong authentication (for example multi-factor authentication).	Q1-OPS-15.1B	Does the CSP restrict access to system components under its responsibility, that are used for logging and monitoring with strong authentication?	- Documented authorized access users list
		OPS-15.2B	Changes to the logging and monitoring configuration are made in accordance with applicable policies (cf. CCM-01).	Q1-OPS-15.2B	Are changes to the logging and monitoring configuration made in accordance with applicable policies (cf. CCM-01)?	- Cross References between changes to the logging and monitoring configuration and policies for changes to information systems
OPS-16	LOGGING AND MONITORING – AVAILABILITY	OPS-16.1B	The CSP shall monitor the system components for logging and monitoring under its responsibility, and shall automatically report failures to the responsible departments for assessment and remediation.	Q1-OPS-16.1B	Does the CSP monitor the system components for logging and monitoring under its responsibility?	- Documented system components monitor report
				Q2-OPS-16.1B	Does the CSP automatically report failures to the responsible departments for assessment and remediation?	- Automatized failures report
OPS-17	MANAGING VULNERABILITIES, MALFUNCTIONS AND ERRORS – POLICIES	OPS-17.1B	The CSP shall define and implement, in accordance with ISP-02, policies and procedures, including technical and organisational measures to ensure the timely identification and addressing of vulnerabilities in the system components used to provide the cloud service.	Q1-OPS-17.1B	Does the CSP define in accordance with ISP-02 policies and procedures with technical and organisational measures to ensure the timely identification and addressing of vulnerabilities in the system components used to provide the cloud service?	- Documented policies and procedures

				Q2-OPS-17.1B	Does the CSP implement in accordance with ISP-02 policies and procedures with technical and organisational measures to ensure the timely identification and addressing of vulnerabilities in the system components used to provide the cloud service?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented list of vulnerabilities in the system components used to provide the cloud service - Vulnerabilities addressing report
		OPS-17.2B	The CSP shall use a scoring system for the assessment of vulnerabilities that includes at least “critical” and “high” classes of vulnerabilities.	Q1-OPS-17.2B	Does the CSP use a scoring system for the assessment of vulnerabilities?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented scoring system
				Q2-OPS-17.2B	Does the scoring system for the assessment of vulnerabilities include at least “critical” and “high” classes of vulnerabilities?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Classes of vulnerabilities identified in the scoring system. ("critical" & "high" at least)
OPS-18	MANAGING VULNERABILITIES, MALFUNCTIONS AND ERRORS – ONLINE REGISTERS	OPS-18.1B	The CSP shall publish and maintain a publicly and easily accessible online register of vulnerabilities that affect the cloud service and assets provided by the CSP that the CSCs have to install or operate under their own responsibility.	Q1-OPS-18.1B	Does the CSP publish a publicly and easily accessible online register of vulnerabilities that affect the cloud service and assets provided by the CSP that the CSCs have to install or operate under their own responsibility?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -WEB -email - etc.
				Q2-OPS-18.1B	Does the CSP maintain a publicly and easily accessible online register of vulnerabilities that affect the cloud service and assets provided by the CSP that the CSCs have to install or operate under their own responsibility?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Register of vulnerabilities update date

		OPS-18.2B	The online register shall indicate at least the following information for every vulnerability: (1) A presentation of the vulnerability following an industry-accepted scoring system; (2) A description of the remediation options for that vulnerability; (3) Information on the availability of updates or patches for that vulnerability; (4) Information about the remediation or deployment of patches or updates by the CSP or CSC, including detailed instructions for operations to be performed by the CSC.	Q1-OPS-18.2B	Does the online register indicate for every vulnerability a presentation of the vulnerability following an industry-accepted scoring system?	- Vulnerability online register
				Q2-OPS-18.2B	Does the online register indicate for every vulnerability a description of the remediation options for that vulnerability?	- Vulnerability online register
				Q3-OPS-18.2B	Does the online register indicate for every vulnerability information on the availability of updates or patches for that vulnerability?	- Vulnerability online register
				Q4-OPS-18.2B	Does the online register indicate for every vulnerability information about the remediation or deployment of patches or updates by the CSP or CSC, including detailed instructions for operations to be performed by the CSC?	- Vulnerability online register
		OPS-18.3B	The CSP shall publish and maintain a publicly and easily accessible online register of vulnerabilities that affect the cloud service and assets provided by the CSP that the CSCs have to install, provide or operate under their own responsibility.	Q1-OPS-18.3B	Does the CSP publish a publicly and easily accessible online register of vulnerabilities that affect the cloud service and assets?	- Vulnerability online register

		OPS-18.4B	The CSP shall consult regularly the online registers published by its subservice providers and suppliers, analyse the potential impact of the published vulnerabilities on the cloud service, and handle them according to the vulnerability handling process (cf.OPS-17).	Q1-OPS-18.4B	Does the CSP regularly consult the online registers of vulnerabilities published by its subservice providers and suppliers?	
				Q2-OPS-18.4B	Does the CSP shall analyse the potential impact of the published vulnerabilities on the cloud service?	- Documented analysis of the potential impact of the published vulnerabilities on the cloud service
				Q3-OPS-18.4B	Does the CSP handle the vulnerabilities according to the vulnerability handling process (cf. OPS-17)?	Audit records concerning to the handled vulnerabilities
OPS-19	MANAGING VULNERABILITIES, MALFUNCTIONS AND ERRORS – VULNERABILITY IDENTIFICATION	OPS-19.1B	The CSP shall perform on a regular basis tests to detect publicly known vulnerabilities on the system components used to provide the cloud service, in accordance with policies for handling vulnerabilities (cf. OPS-17).	Q1-OPS-19.1B	Does the CSP perform on a regular basis tests to detect publicly known vulnerabilities on the system components used to provide the cloud service?	- Test report
OPS-20	MANAGING VULNERABILITIES, MALFUNCTIONS AND ERRORS – MEASUREMENTS, ANALYSES AND ASSESSMENTS OF PROCEDURES	OPS-20.1B	The CSP shall regularly measure, analyse and assess the procedures with which vulnerabilities and security incidents are handled to verify their continued suitability, appropriateness and effectiveness.	Q1-OPS-20.1B	Does the CSP regularly measure the procedures with which vulnerabilities and incidents are handled to verify their continued suitability, appropriateness and effectiveness?	- Documented procedures review - Procedures' review date

				Q2-OPS-20.1B	Does the CSP regularly analyse the procedures with which vulnerabilities and incidents are handled to verify their continued suitability, appropriateness and effectiveness?	- Documented procedures review - Procedures' review date
				Q3-OPS-20.1B	Does the CSP regularly assess the procedures with which vulnerabilities and incidents are handled to verify their continued suitability, appropriateness and effectiveness?	- Documented procedures review - Procedures' review date
OPS-21	MANAGING VULNERABILITIES, MALFUNCTIONS AND ERRORS – SYSTEM HARDENING	OPS-21.1B	The CSP shall harden all the system components under its responsibility that are used to provide the cloud service, according to accepted industry standards.	Q1-OPS-21.1B	Does the CSP harden all the system components under its responsibility that are used to provide the cloud service, according to accepted industry standards?	- Documented hardens to all the system components under its responsibility - Changes in the system components (encompasses the hardens)
OPS-21		OPS-21.2B	The hardening requirements for each system component shall be documented.	Q1-OPS-21.2B	Are the hardening requirements for each system component documented?	- Documented hardening requirements for each system component
OPS-22	SEPARATION OF DATASETS IN THE CLOUD INFRASTRUCTURE	OPS-22.1B	The CSP shall segregate from other CSCs the data stored and processed on shared virtual and physical resources on behalf of a CSC to ensure the confidentiality and integrity of this data.	Q1-OPS-22.1B	Does the CSP segregate the CSC data stored and processed on shared virtual and physical resources to ensure the confidentiality and integrity of this data?	- CSC data stored and processed on shared virtual and physical resources

8. Identity, Authentication and Access Management

Table 22. Checklist for IAM basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

Control ID	Control	ReqID	Requirement	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
IAM-01	POLICIES FOR ACCESS CONTROL TO INFORMATION	IAM-01.1B	The CSP shall define role and rights policies and procedures for controlling access to information resources, according to ISP-02 and based on the business and security requirements of the CSP, in which at least the following aspects are covered: (1) Parameters to be considered for making access control decisions; (2) Granting and modifying access rights based on the “least-privilege” principle and on the “need to-know” principle; (3) Segregation of duties between managing, approving and assigning access rights; (4) Dedicated rules for users with privileged access; (5) Requirements for the approval and documentation of the management of access rights.	Q1-IAM-01.1B	Have the CSP defined role and rights policies and procedures for controlling access to information resources?	- Documented role and rights policies and procedures for controlling access to information resources
				Q2-IAM-01.1B	Are the above defined policies and procedures aligned with the Global Information Security Policy defined in ISP-02?	- Cross references between role and rights policies and procedures for controlling access to information resources and Global Information Security Policy
				Q3-IAM-01.1B	Are the above defined policies and procedures based on the business and security requirements of the CSP?	- Policies and procedures review records (Approval signature)

				Q4-IAM-01.1B	Does the above defined policies and procedure contains at least: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parameters to be considered for making access control decisions • Granting and modifying access rights based on the “least-privilege” principle and on the “need-to-know” principle. • Use of a role-based mechanism for the assignment of access rights • Segregation of duties between managing, approving and assigning access rights • Dedicated rules for users with privileged access • Requirements for the approval and documentation of the management of access rights 	- Documented role and rights policies and procedures for controlling access to information resources (include these five topics) - Policies and procedures review records
		IAM-01.2B	The CSP shall link the access control policy defined in IAM-01.1 with the physical access control policy defined in PS-02.1, to guarantee that the access to the premises where information is located is also controlled.	Q1-IAM-01.2B	Does the IAM-01.1 documented policy and the PS-02.1 documented policy make cross reference between them?	- Cross references between IAM-01-1 policy and PS-02.1 policy
IAM-02	MANAGEMENT OF USER ACCOUNTS	IAM-02.1B	The CSP shall define policies for managing accounts, according to ISP-02, in which at least the following aspects are described: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Parameters to be considered for making access control decisions; (2) Assignment of unique usernames; (3) Definition of the different types of accounts supported, and assignment of access control parameters and roles to be considered for each type; (4) Events and periods of inactivity leading to blocking and revoking accounts. 	Q1-IAM-02.1B	Are the policies for managing accounts defined?	- Documented policies for managing accounts

				Q2-IAM-02.1B	Are the policies for managing accounts aligned with ISP-02 policy?	- Policies review records
				Q3-IAM-02.1B	Does the documented policies for managing accounts contain at least: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Parameters for making access control decisions Assignment of unique usernames Definition of the different types of accounts supported, and assignment of access control parameters and roles to be considered for each type Events and periods of inactivity leading to blocking and revoking accounts. 	- Documented policies (encompass assignment of unique usernames, definition of the different types of accounts supported, and assignment of access control parameters and roles to be considered for each type & events leading to blocking and revoking accounts) - Policies review records
		IAM-02.2B	The CSP shall define and implement according to ISP-02 procedures for managing user accounts and access rights to employees that comply with the role and rights policies (cf. IAM-01) and with the policies for managing accounts.	Q1-IAM-02.2B	Are the procedures for managing personal user accounts and access rights to employees specified in IAM-01 defined?	- Documented procedures for managing personal user accounts and access rights to employees
				Q2-IAM-02.2B	Are the previous documented policies complying the role and rights concept and with the policies for managing accounts?	- Policy assessment result
				Q3-IAM-02.2B	Are these procedures implemented for internal employees?	- Personal user account and access rights for internal employees
				Q4-IAM-02.2B	Are these procedures implemented for external employees?	- Personal user account and access rights for external employees
		IAM-02.3B	The CSP shall define and implement according to ISP-02 procedures for managing shared accounts and associated access rights that comply with the role and rights policies (cf.	Q1-IAM-02.3B	Are the procedures for managing non-personal shared accounts and associated access rights specified in IAM-01 documented?	- Documented procedures for managing non-personal shared accounts and associated access rights

			IAM-01) and with the policies for managing accounts.			
				Q2-IAM-02.3B	Are the previous documented policies complying the role and rights concept and with the policies for managing accounts?	- Policy assessment result
				Q3-IAM-02.3B	Are these procedures implemented?	- Non-personal shared accounts and associated access rights
		IAM-02.4B	The CSP shall define and implement according to ISP-02 procedures for managing non-human accounts and associated access rights to system components involved in the operation of the cloud service that comply with the role and rights policies (cf. IAM-01) and with the policies for managing accounts.	Q1-IAM-02.4B	Are the procedures for managing technical accounts and associated access rights to system components involved in the operation of the cloud service specified in ISP-02 defined?	- Documented procedures for managing technical accounts and associated access rights to system components involved in the operation of the cloud service
				Q2-IAM-02.4B	Are the previous documented policies complying the role and rights concept and with the policies for managing accounts?	- Policy assessment result
				Q3-IAM-02.4B	Are these procedures implemented?	- Technical accounts and associated access rights to system components involved in the operation of the cloud service
		IAM-02.5B	The CSP shall be able to provide, for a given user account, whether it falls under the responsibility of the CSP or of the CSC, as well as the list of the access rights currently granted to that account	Q1-IAM-02.5B	Can the CSP provide for a given user account, whether it falls under the responsibility of the CSP or of the CSC?	- Fault register associated to a user account in which it is specified if the faults responsibility is of CSP or CSC
				Q2-IAM-02.5B	Can the CSP provide for a given user account, the list of the access rights granted to that account?	- List of access right granted associated to a user account that has fault

IAM-03	LOCKING, UNLOCKING AND REVOCATION OF USER ACCOUNTS	IAM-03.1B	The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to block user accounts after a certain period of inactivity.	Q1-IAM-03.1B	Does the CSP document a mechanism that automatically block user accounts after a certain period of inactivity?	- Documented description of the mechanism to block user accounts after a certain period of inactivity
				Q2-IAM-03.1B	Is the "certain period of inactivity" quantified and documented somewhere?	- Document in which is specified the "certain period of time" after which the user account is automatically blocked
				Q3-IAM-03.1B	Does the automated mechanism in place executed when some user account overcome the specified period of time?	- Evidence of blocked user accounts that meet the defined requirements
		IAM-03.2B	The CSP shall document and implement an automated mechanism to block accounts after a certain number of failed authentication attempts.	Q1-IAM-03.2B	Does the CSP define a mechanism that automatically block user accounts after a certain number of failed authentication attempts?	- Documented description of the mechanism to block user accounts
				Q2-IAM-03.2B	Is the "certain number of failed authentication attempts" quantified and documented somewhere?	- Document in which is specified the "certain number of failed authentication attempts" after which the user account is automatically blocked
				Q3-IAM-03.2B	Does the automated mechanism in place executed after the specified certain number of failed authentication attempts?	- Evidence of blocked user accounts that meet the defined requirements
IAM-04	MANAGEMENT OF ACCESS RIGHTS	IAM-04.1B	The CSP shall document and implement procedures to grant, update, and revoke to an account under its responsibility access rights to resources of the information system of the cloud service, and these procedures shall be in conformity with the role and rights policies and with the policies for managing access rights.	Q1-IAM-04.1B	Has the CSP documented procedures to grant, update, and revoke to a user account under its responsibility access rights to resources of the information system of the cloud service?	- Documented procedures to grant, update, and revoke to a user account under its responsibility access rights to resources of the information system of the cloud service
				Q2-IAM-04.1B	Are these documented procedures compliant with the role and rights	- Procedure assessment results

					concept and with the policies for managing access rights?	
				Q3-IAM-04.1B	Are these procedures implemented within the CSP?	- Examples of user accounts to which access rights to resources of the information system of the cloud service have been granted, updated, revoked
		IAM-04.2B	The CSP shall document and implement a procedure to timely update or revoke the access rights of an internal or external employee when the role and responsibilities of the employee change.	Q1-IAM-04.2B	Has the CSP documented procedures to timely update or revoke the access rights of an internal or external employee when the role and responsibilities of the employee change?	- Documented procedures o timely update or revoke the access rights of an internal or external employee when the role and responsibilities of the employee change
				Q2-IAM-04.2B	Are the previous documented procedures implemented for internal employees?	- Example of internal employees whose access rights have been updated/revoked when their role and responsibilities has changed
				Q3-IAM-04.2B	Are the previous documented procedures implemented for external employees?	- Example of external employees whose access rights have been updated/revoked when their role and responsibilities has changed
IAM-05	REGULAR REVIEW OF ACCESS RIGHTS	IAM-05.1B	The CSP shall review the access rights of all the accounts under its responsibility at least once a year to ensure that they still correspond to the current needs.	Q1-IAM-05.1B	Does the CSP periodically review the access rights of all user accounts under its responsibility?	- Access rights review results (execution date less than 12 months).
				Q2-IAM-05.1B	Is the previous review executed at least annually for all the user accounts under the CSP responsibility?	- Review execution dates of the last 2/3 years
IAM-06	PRIVILEGED ACCESS RIGHTS	IAM-06.1B	Shared accounts under the responsibility of the CSP shall be assigned only to employees.	Q1-IAM-06.1B	Are the shared accounts under the responsibility of the CSP assigned only to employees?	- Assignment of the shared accounts

IAM-07	AUTHENTICATI ON MECHANISMS	IAM- 07.1B	The CSP shall define and implement according to ISP-02 policies and procedures about authentication mechanisms, covering at least the following aspects: (1) The selection of mechanisms suitable for every type of account and each level of risk; (2)The protection of credentials used by the authentication mechanism; (3) The generation and distribution of credentials for new accounts; (4) Rules for the renewal of credentials, including periodic renewals, renewals in case of loss or compromise; and (5) Rules on the required strength of credentials, together with mechanisms to communicate and enforce the rules.	Q1-IAM- 07.1B	Has the CSP defined policy and procedures about authentication mechanisms according to IPS-02?	- Documented policy and procedures
				Q2-IAM- 07.1B	Does these policy and procedures cover at least the following aspects: • The selection of mechanisms suitable for every type of account and each level of risk; • The protection of credentials used by the authentication mechanism; • The generation and distribution of credentials for new accounts; • Rules for the renewal of credentials, including periodic renewals, renewals in case of loss or compromise; and • Rules on the required strength of credentials, together with mechanisms to communicate and enforce the rules	- Documented policy and procedures (encompass the five topics) - Documented policy and procedures review records

				Q3-IAM-07.1B	Are these policy and procedures implemented within the CSP organization?	- Logs -Databases or any other software asset
		IAM-07.2B	The access to all environments of the CSP shall be authenticated, including non-production environments.	Q1-IAM-07.2B	Is the access to all the CSP environments authenticated?	- Access Logs to the -production environment, in order to see the authentication protocol applied to production environment
				Q2-IAM-07.2B	Are the non-production environment also included in the previous authentication?	- Access Logs to the non-production environments, in order to see the authentication protocol applied to non-production environment
		IAM-07.3B	All authentication mechanisms shall include a mechanism to block an account after a predefined number of unsuccessful attempts.	Q1-IAM-07.3B	Does every authentication mechanism in place within CSP include a mechanism to block an account after a predefined number of unsuccessful attempts?	- If this is something "static": documents that for each authentication mechanism document the blocking mechanism - If this is something "dynamic": examples of blocked account due to unsuccessful attempts
IAM-08	PROTECTION AND STRENGTH OF CREDENTIALS	IAM-08.1B	The CSP shall document, communicate and make available to all users under its responsibility rules and recommendations for the management of credentials, including at least: (1) Non-reuse of credentials; (2) Trade-offs between entropy and ability to memorize; (3) Recommendations for renewal of passwords; (4) Rules on storage of passwords.	Q1-IAM-08.1B	Have the CSP documented rules and recommendations for the management of credentials?	- Document with rules and recommendations for the management of credentials
				Q2-IAM-08.1B	Does the previous document contain at least:	- Document with rules and recommendations for the

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-reuse of credentials • Trade-offs between entropy and ability to memorize • Recommendations for renewal of passwords • Rules on storage of passwords 	management of credentials (encompass the four topics) - Document with rules and recommendations for the management of credentials review records
				Q3-IAM-08.1B	Have the CSP communicated to all users under its responsibility the rules and recommendations for the management of credentials?	- Communication mechanism: - Intranet/WEB - email - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
				Q4-IAM-08.1B	Have the CSP made available to all users under its responsibility the rules and recommendations for the management of credentials?	- Examples of documents with rules and recommendations for the management of credentials provided by sampled users
		IAM-08.2B	Passwords shall be only stored using cryptographically strong hash functions (cf. CKM-01)	Q1-IAM-08.2B	Are all the passwords stored using cryptographically strong hash functions according to the policy defined in CKM-01?	- Example of stored passwords randomly selected
		IAM-08.3B	If cryptographic authentication mechanisms are used, they shall follow the policies and procedures from CKM-01.	Q1-IAM-08.3B	If cryptographic authentication mechanisms are used, do they follow the policies and procedures specified in CKM-01?	- Example of cryptographic authentication mechanisms randomly selected + Review results against CKM-01 policies
IAM-09	GENERAL ACCESS RESTRICTIONS	IAM-09.1B	The CSP shall implement sufficient partitioning measures between the information system providing the cloud service and its other information systems.	Q1-IAM-09.1B	Have the CSP implemented partitioning measures between the information system providing the cloud service and its other information systems?	- Example of partitioning measures randomly identified
				Q2-IAM-09.1B	Are the partitioning measures sufficient?	N.B. Not possible to demonstrate with the current level of objectiveness
		IAM-09.2B	The CSP shall implement suitable measures for partitioning between the CSCs.	Q1-IAM-09.2B	Did the CSP implement measures for partitioning between the CSCs?	- Example of partitioning measures between CSCs randomly identified

9. Cryptography & Key management

Table 23. Checklist for CKM basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

Control ID	Control	ReqID	Requirement	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
CKM-01	POLICIES FOR THE USE OF ENCRYPTION MECHANISMS AND KEY MANAGEMENT	CKM-01.1B	The CSP shall define and implement policies with technical and organizational safeguards for cryptography and key management, according to ISP-02, in which at least the following aspects are described: (1) Usage of strong cryptographic mechanisms and secure network protocols; (2) Requirements for the secure generation, storage, archiving, retrieval, distribution, withdrawal and deletion of the keys; (3) Consideration of relevant legal and regulatory obligations and requirements.	Q1-CKM-01.1B	Does the CSP document policies with technical and organizational safeguards for encryption and key management, according to ISP-02?	-Documented policies with technical and organizational safeguards for encryption and key management (encompasses the three aspects)
				Q2-CKM-01.1B	Does the CSP implement policies with technical and organizational safeguards for encryption and key management, according to ISP-02?	- Audit records / Logs
				Q3-CKM-01.1B	Do policies describe usage of strong encryption procedures and secure network protocols?	- Policies (describe usage of strong encryption procedures and secure network protocols)
				Q4-CKM-01.1B	Do policies describe requirements for the secure generation, storage, archiving, retrieval, distribution, withdrawal and deletion of the keys?	- Policies (describe requirements for the secure generation, storage, archiving, retrieval, distribution, withdrawal and deletion of the keys)
				Q5-CKM-01.1B	Do policies describe consideration of relevant legal and regulatory obligations and requirements?	- Policies (describe consideration of relevant legal

						and regulatory obligations and requirements)
CKM-02	ENCRYPTION OF DATA IN TRANSIT	CKM-02.1B	The CSP shall define and implement strong cryptographic mechanisms for the transmission of CSC data over public networks, in order to protect the confidentiality, integrity and authenticity of data.	Q1-CKM-02.1B	Does the CSP define strong encryption mechanisms for the transmission of CSC data over public networks?	- Encryption mechanisms design
				Q2-CKM-02.1	Does the CSP implement strong encryption mechanisms for the transmission of cloud customer data over public networks?	- Audit records - Examples of encrypted data
CKM-03	ENCRYPTION OF DATA AT REST	CKM-03.1B	The CSP shall define and implement procedures and technical safeguards to protect the confidentiality of CSC data during storage, according to ISP-02.	Q1-CKM-03.1B	Does the CSP document procedures and technical safeguards to protect cloud customers' data during storage according to ISP-02?	- Documented procedures and technical safeguards to encrypt cloud customers' data during storage
				Q2-CKM-03.1B	Does the CSP implement technical safeguards to protect cloud customers' data during storage?	- Audit records - Examples of encrypted data
CKM-03		CKM-03.2B	The CSP shall notify CSCs of updates of these procedures and technical safeguards and to changes in the storage of CSC data that may affect the confidentiality of the data.	Q1-CKM-03.2B	Does the CSP notify customers about any updates to technical safeguards and to the procedures that protect the confidentiality of customers' data during storage that may affect the confidentiality of the data?	- Documented notifications to customers (email, reports, web, etc.)
				Q2-CKM-03.2B	Does the CSP notify customers about any changes in the storage of customer data that may affect the confidentiality of the data?	- Documented notifications to customers (email, reports, web, etc.)

CKM-04	SECURE KEY MANAGEMENT	CKM-04.1B	<p>Procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management in the area of responsibility of the CSP shall include at least the following aspects:</p> <p>(1) Generation of keys for different cryptographic systems and applications;</p> <p>(2) Issuing and obtaining public-key certificates;</p> <p>(3) Provisioning and activation of the keys;</p> <p>(4) Secure storage of keys including description of how authorised users get access;</p> <p>(5) Changing or updating cryptographic keys including policies defining under which conditions and in which manner the changes and/or updates are to be realised;</p> <p>(6) Handling of compromised keys; and</p> <p>(7) Withdrawal and deletion of keys;</p>	Q1-CKM-04.1B	Do procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management in the area of responsibility of the CSP shall include a generation of keys for different cryptographic systems and applications?	<p>- Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management (include a generation of keys for different cryptographic systems and applications)</p> <p>- Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management compliance review record</p>
				Q2-CKM-04.1B	Do procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management in the area of responsibility of the CSP include issuing and obtaining public-key certificates?	<p>- Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management (include issuing and obtaining public-key certificates)</p> <p>- Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management compliance review record</p>
				Q3-CKM-04.1B	Do procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management in the area of responsibility of the CSP include provisioning and activation of the keys?	<p>- Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management (include provisioning and activation of the keys)</p> <p>- Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management compliance review record</p>

				Q4-CKM-04.1B	Do procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management in the area of responsibility of the CSP include secure storage of keys including description of how authorised users get access?	- Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management (include secure storage of keys including description of how authorised users get access) - Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management compliance review record
				Q5-CKM-04.1B	Do procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management in the area of responsibility of the CSP include changing or updating cryptographic keys including policies defining under which conditions and in which manner the changes and/or updates are to be realised?	- Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management (include changing or updating cryptographic keys including policies defining under which conditions and in which manner the changes and/or updates are to be realised) - Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management compliance review record
				Q6-CKM-04.1B	Do procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management in the area of responsibility of the CSP include handling of compromised keys?	- Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management (include handling of compromised keys) - Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management compliance review record
				Q7-CKM-04.1B	Do procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management in the area of responsibility of the CSP include withdrawal and deletion of keys?	- Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management (include withdrawal and deletion of keys)

						- Documented procedures and technical safeguards for secure key management compliance review record
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10. Communications Security

Table 24. Checklist for CS basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

Control ID	Control	ReqID	Requirement	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
CS-01	TECHNICAL SAFEGUARDS	CS-01.1B	The CSP shall define and implement technical safeguards that are suitable to promptly detect and respond to network-based attacks and to ensure the protection of information and information processing systems, in accordance with ISP-02.	Q1-CS-01.1B	Does the CSP document technical safeguards to ensure the protection of information and information processing systems that are suitable to promptly detect and respond to network-based attacks?	- Documented technical safeguards
				Q2-CS-01.1B	Does the CSP communicate technical safeguards that are suitable to promptly detect and respond to network-based attacks?	- Intranet - email - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
				Q3-CS-01.1B	Does the CSP implement technical safeguards that are suitable to promptly detect and respond to network-based attacks?	- Event log and monitoring to allow the recording and detection of actions that could affect, or be relevant, for information security - Audit report
				Q4-CS-01.1B	Does the CSP document technical safeguards to ensure the protection of information and information processing systems?	- Documented technical safeguards

				Q5-CS-01.1B	Does the CSP communicate technical safeguards to ensure the protection of information and information processing systems?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intranet - email - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
				Q6-CS-01.1B	Does the CSP implement technical safeguards to ensure the protection of information and information processing systems?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Event log and monitoring to allow the recording and detection of actions that could affect, or be relevant, for information security - Audit report
CS-02	SECURITY REQUIREMENTS TO CONNECT WITHIN THE CSP'S NETWORK	CS-02.1B	The CSP shall define and implement according to ISP-02 specific security requirements to connect within its network, including at least: (1) When the security zones are to be separated and when the CSCs are to be logically or physically segregated; (2) What communication relationships and what network and application protocols are permitted in each case; (3) How the data traffic for administration and monitoring are segregated from each other at the network level; (4) What internal, cross-location communication is permitted; and (5) what cross-network communication is allowed.	Q1-CS-02-1B	Do the CSP document specific security requirements to connect within its network?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented specific security requirements to connect within its network
				Q2-CS-02-1B	Do the CSP communicate specific security requirements to connect within its network?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication mechanism: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Intranet/WEB -email - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
				Q3-CS-02-1B	Do the CSP make available specific security requirements to connect within its network?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Distribution mechanism: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information management system

						- Intranet/WEB - email - Etc.
				Q4-CS-02-1B	Do the CSP implement specific security requirements to connect within its network?	- Audit records
				Q5-CS-02-1B	Do specific security requirements to connect within its network address when the security zones are to be separated and when the cloud customers are to be logically or physically segregated?	- Documented specific security requirements to connect within its network review record
				Q6-CS-02-1B	Do specific security requirements to connect within its network address what communication relationships and what network and application protocols are permitted in each case?	- Documented specific security requirements to connect within its network review record
				Q7-CS-02-1B	Do specific security requirements to connect within its network address how the data traffic for administration and monitoring are segregated from each other at the network level?	- Documented specific security requirements to connect within its network review record
				Q8-CS-02-1B	Do specific security requirements to connect within its network address what internal, cross-location communication is permitted?	- Documented specific security requirements to connect within its network review record
				Q9-CS-02-1B	Do specific security requirements to connect within its network address what cross-network communication is allowed?	- Documented specific security requirements to connect within its network review record
CS-03	MONITORING OF CONNECTIONS WITHIN THE	CS-03.1B	The CSP shall distinguish between trusted and untrusted networks, based on a risk assessment.	Q1-CS-03.1B	Does the CSP distinguish between trusted and untrusted networks?	- Documented list of trusted and untrusted networks

	CSP'S NETWORK					
				Q2-CS-03.1B	Is that distinction based on a risk assessment?	- Documented risk assessment
		CS-03.2B	The CSP shall separate trusted and untrusted networks into different security zones for internal and external network areas (and DMZ, if applicable).	Q1-CS-03.2B	Does the CSP separate trusted and untrusted networks into different security zones for internal network areas?	- Documented network topology
				Q2-CS-03.2B	Does the CSP separate trusted and untrusted networks into different security zones for external network areas?	- Documented network topology
				Q3-CS-03.2B	Does the CSP separate trusted and untrusted networks into different security zones for DMZ, if applicable?	- Documented network topology
		CS-03.3B	The CSP shall design and configure both physical and virtualized network environments to restrict and monitor the connection to trusted or untrusted networks according to the defined security requirements (cf. CS-02).	Q1-CS-03.3B	Does the CSP shall design virtualized network environments to restrict and monitor the connection to trusted or untrusted networks according to the defined security requirements (cf. CS-02)?	- Documented physical network environments design
				Q2-CS-03.3B	Does the CSP shall design virtualized network environments to restrict and monitor the connection to trusted or untrusted networks according to the defined security requirements (cf. CS-02)?	- Documented virtualized network environments design
				Q3-CS-03.3B	Does the CSP configure physical network environments to restrict and monitor the connection to trusted or untrusted networks according to the defined security requirements (cf. CS-02)?	- Documented physical network environments configuration

				Q4-CS-03.3B	Does the CSP configure virtualized network environments to restrict and monitor the connection to trusted or untrusted networks according to the defined security requirements (cf. CS-02)	- Documented virtualized network environments configuration
		CS-03.4B	The CSP shall review at specified intervals the business justification for using all services, protocols, and ports. This review shall also include the compensatory measures used for protocols that are considered insecure.	Q1-CS-03.4B	Does the CSP review at specified intervals the business justification for using all services, protocols, and ports?	- Documented review records (last 2/3 years)
CS-04	NETWORKS FOR ADMINISTRATION	CS-04.1B	The CSP shall define and implement separate networks for the administrative management of the infrastructure and the operation of management consoles.	Q1-CS-04.1B	Does the CSP define separate networks for the administrative management of the infrastructure and the operation of management consoles?	- Documented network topology - Documented network design
				Q2-CS-04.1B	Does the CSP implement separate networks for the administrative management of the infrastructure and the operation of management consoles	- Audit records
		CS-04.2B	The CSP shall logically or physically separate the networks for administration from the CSCs' networks.	Q1-CS-04.2B	Does the CSP logically or physically separate the networks for administration from the CSCs' networks?	- Documented network topology - Documented network design
		CS-04.3B	The CSP shall segregate physically or logically the networks used to migrate or create virtual machines.	Q1-CS-04.3B	Does the CSP segregate physically or logically the networks used to migrate or create virtual machines?	- Documented network topology - Documented network design
CS-05	TRAFFIC SEGREGATION IN SHARED NETWORK ENVIRONMENTS	CS-05.1B	The CSP shall document and implement separation mechanisms at network level the data traffic of different CSCs.	Q1-CS-05.1B	Does the CSP define separation mechanisms at network level the data traffic of different CSCs?	- List of separation mechanisms at network level

				Q2-CS-05.1B	Does the CSP document separation mechanisms at network level the data traffic of different cloud customers?	- Documented separation mechanisms design at network level
				Q3-CS-05.1B	Does the CSP implement separation mechanisms at network level the data traffic of different cloud customers?	- Audit records
CS-06	NETWORK TOPOLOGY DOCUMENTATION	CS-06.1B	The CSP shall maintain up-to-date all documentation of the logical structure of the network used to provision or operate the cloud service.	Q1-CS-06.1B	Does the CSP maintain up-to-date all documentation of the logical structure of the network used to provision or operate the cloud service?	- Document version control box up-to-date - Configuration management audit record
				Q1-CS-06.2B	Does the documentation cover how the subnets are allocated?	- Documentation of the logical structure of the network used to provision or operate the cloud service review record
				Q2-CS-06.2B	Does the documentation cover how the network is zoned and segmented?	- Documentation of the logical structure of the network used to provision or operate the cloud service review record
				Q3-CS-06.2B	Does the documentation cover how it connects with third-party and public networks?	- Documentation of the logical structure of the network used to provision or operate the cloud service review record
				Q4-CS-06.2B	Does the documentation cover the geographical locations in which the CSC data is stored?	- Documentation of the logical structure of the network used to provision or operate the cloud service review record
		CS-06.2B	The documentation shall cover, at least, how the subnets are allocated, how the network is zoned and segmented, how it connects with third-party and public networks, and the geographical locations in which the CSC data is stored.	Q1-CS-06.2B	Does the documentation cover how the subnets are allocated?	

CS-07	SOFTWARE DEFINED NETWORKING	CS-07.1B	The CSP shall ensure the confidentiality of CSC data by suitable procedures when offering functions to CSCs for software-defined networking (SDN).	Q1-CS-07.1B	Does the CSP ensure the confidentiality of the cloud user data by suitable procedures when offering functions to CSCs for software-defined networking (SDN)?	- Documented suitable procedures to ensure the confidentiality of the cloud user data
		CS-07.2B	The CSP shall validate the functionality of the SDN functions before providing new SDN features to CSCs or modifying existing SDN features.	Q1-CS-07.2B	Does the CSP validate the functionality of the SDN functions before providing new SDN features to CSCs?	- SDN functions validation record
CS-08	DATA TRANSMISSIO N POLICIES	CS-08.1B	The CSP shall define and implement policies and procedures with technical and organisational safeguards to protect the transmission of data against unauthorised interception, manipulation, copying, modification, redirection or destruction, according to ISP-02.	Q1-CS-08.1B	Does the CSP define policies and procedures with technical and organisational safeguards to protect the transmission of data against unauthorised interception, manipulation, copying, modification, redirection or destruction, according to ISP-02?	- Documented policies and procedures with technical and organisational safeguards
				Q2-CS-08.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures with technical and organisational safeguards to protect the transmission of data against unauthorised interception, manipulation, copying, modification, redirection or destruction, according to ISP-02?	- Audit records

11. Portability and Interoperability

Table 25. Checklist for PI basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

Control ID	Control	ReqID	Requirement	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
PI-01	DOCUMENTATION AND SECURITY OF INPUT AND OUTPUT INTERFACES	PI-01.1B	Inbound and outbound interfaces that are made accessible for use by cloud services from other CSPs or CSCs' IT systems shall be documented.	Q1-PI-01.1B	Is the cloud service accessible by cloud services from other CSPs or cloud customers IT systems?	- Accessible APIs - Public URLs
				Q2-PI-01.1B	Are the inbound interfaces documented?	- Documented inbound interfaces (internal domain names)
				Q3-PI-01.1B	Are the outbound interfaces documented?	- Documented outbound interfaces
		PI-01.2B	The interfaces shall be clearly documented for subject matter experts to understand how they can be used to retrieve the data.	Q1-PI-01.2B	Are the interfaces clearly documented for subject matter experts to understand how they can be used to retrieve the data?	- Documented inbound and outbound interfaces (internal domain names and ports, mechanisms, username/pwd, etc.) - Peer review of the documented interfaces
		PI-01.3B	Communication on these interfaces shall use documented communication protocols that ensure the confidentiality and integrity of the transmitted information according to its protection requirements, and the adequate authentication of the user.	Q1-PI-01.3B	Does communication on these interfaces use standardized communication protocols?	- Documented list of supported communication protocols
				Q2-PI-01.3B	Do protocols ensure the confidentiality and integrity of the transmitted information according to its protection requirements and the adequate authentication of the user?	- Documented list of supported communication protocols

		PI-01.4B	Communication over untrusted networks shall be protected in confidentiality, integrity and authenticity according to CKM-02.	Q1-PI-01.4B	Is the communication over untrusted networks protected in confidentiality, integrity and authenticity according to CKM-02?	- Authentication and Protection Settings
PI-02	CONTRACTUAL AGREEMENTS FOR THE PROVISION OF DATA	PI-02.1B	The CSP shall include in cloud service contractual agreements, at least, the following aspects concerning the termination of the contractual relationship: (1) Type, scope and format of the data the CSP provides to the CSC; (2) Delivery methods of the data to the CSC; (3) Definition of the timeframe, within which the CSP makes the data available to the CSC; (4) Definition of the point in time as of which the CSP makes the data inaccessible to the CSC and deletes these; and (5) The CSC's responsibilities and obligations to cooperate for the provision of the data.	Q1-PI-02.1B	Does the CSP in cloud service contractual agreements concerning the termination of the contractual relationship include type, scope and format of the data the CSP provides to the CSC?	- Contractual agreements concerning the termination of the contractual relationship (include type, scope and format of the data the CSP provides to the CSC)
				Q2-PI-02.1B	Does the CSP in cloud service contractual agreements concerning the termination of the contractual relationship include delivery methods of the data to the cloud customer?	- Contractual agreements concerning the termination of the contractual relationship (include delivery methods of the data to the cloud customer)
				Q3-PI-02.1B	Does the CSP in cloud service contractual agreements concerning the termination of the contractual relationship include definition of the timeframe, within which the CSP makes the data available to the CSC?	- Contractual agreements concerning the termination of the contractual relationship (include definition of the timeframe, within which the CSP makes the data available to the CSC)
				Q4-PI-02.1B	Does the CSP in cloud service contractual agreements concerning the termination of the contractual relationship include definition of the point in time as of which the CSP	- Contractual agreements concerning the termination of the contractual relationship (include definition of the point in time as of which the CSP

					makes the data inaccessible to the CSC and deletes these?	makes the data inaccessible to the CSC and deletes these)
				Q5-PI-02.1B	Does the CSP in cloud service contractual agreements concerning the termination of the contractual relationship include the CSC's responsibilities and obligations to cooperate for the provision of the data?	- Contractual agreements concerning the termination of the contractual relationship (include the CSC's responsibilities and obligations to cooperate for the provision of the data)
PI-03	SECURE DELETION OF DATA	PI-03.1B	The CSP shall implement procedures for deleting its customers' data upon termination of their contract in compliance with the contractual agreements between them.	Q1-PI-03.1B	Does the CSP implement procedures for deleting its customers' data upon termination of their contract in compliance with the contractual agreements between them?	- Procedures for deleting customer's data - Data destruction tools - Data destruction records (a filled form or screenshot identifying the data deletion (successful / fail)
		PI-03.2B	The CSC's data deletion shall include all CSC data, as well as related metadata and cloud service derived data, such as data stored in data backups.	Q1-PI-03.2B	Does the CSC's data deletion include all CSC data, as well as related metadata and cloud service derived data?	- Procedures for deleting customer's data - Data destruction tools - Data destruction records (a filled form or screenshot identifying the data deletion (successful / fail)
				Q2-PI-03.2B	Does the CSC's data deletion include data stored in the data backups?	- Procedures for detecting customer's data - Data destruction tools - Data destruction records (a filled form or screenshot identifying the data deletion (successful / fail)
		PI-03.3B	At the end of the contract, the CSP shall delete the technical data concerning the CSC.	Q1-PI-03.3B	At the end of a contract, does the CSP delete the technical data concerning the CSC?	- Technical data erasure records

12. Change and configuration management

Table 26. Checklist for CCM basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

Control ID	Control	ReqID	Requirement	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
CCM-01	POLICIES FOR CHANGES TO INFORMATION SYSTEMS	CCM-01.1B	The CSP shall define and implement policies and procedures for change management of the IT systems supporting the cloud service according to ISP-02.	Q1-CCM-01.1B	Is there a document describing the policy for change management of the IT systems supporting the cloud service?	- Change management policy document
				Q2-CCM-01.1B	Are there documented procedures for change management of the IT systems supporting the cloud service?	- Documented procedures for change management
				Q3-CCM-01.1B	Does the CSP communicate the defined policies and procedures for change management of the IT systems supporting the cloud service?	-Intranet/WEB -email - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
				Q4-CCM-01.1B	Does the CSP implement the defined policies and procedures for change management of the IT systems supporting the cloud service?	- Change managements record & evidence - Audit records
CCM-02	RISK ASSESSMENT, CATEGORISATION AND PRIORITISATION OF CHANGES	CCM-02.1B	The CS shall categorise and prioritise changes considering the potential security effects on the system components concerned.	Q1-CCM-02.1B	Does the CSP categorize changes considering the potential security effects on the system components concerned?	-List of categorised changes
				Q2-CCM-02.1B	Does the CSP prioritise changes considering the potential security effects on the system components concerned?	-List of how changes are prioritized

CCM-03	TESTING CHANGES	CCM-03.1B	The CSP shall test proposed changes before deployment to the production environment.	Q1-CCM-03.1B	Does the CSP test proposed changes before deployment to the production environment?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Test plan - Tests (unit tests / continuous integration tests) - Documented test execution results
		CCM-03.2B	Before using CSC data for tests, the CSP shall first obtain approval from CSC and anonymise CSC data, and the CSP shall guarantee the confidentiality of the data during the whole process.	Q1-CCM-03.2B	Before using CSC data for tests, does the CSP first obtain approval from CSC?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented approval from CSC
				Q2-CCM-03.2B	Before using customer data for tests, does the CSP anonymise customer data?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented compliance review of anonymized customer data
				Q3-CCM-03.2B	Before using customer data for tests, does the CSP guarantee the confidentiality of the data during the whole process?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Confidentiality agreement
CCM-04	APPROVALS FOR PROVISION IN THE PRODUCTION ENVIRONMENT	CCM-04.1B	The CSP shall approve any change to the cloud service, based on defined criteria, before they are made available to CSCs in the production environment.	Q1-CCM-04.1B	Are there defined criteria to approve any change to the cloud service before they are made available to CSCs in the production environment?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented list of defined criteria to approve any change to the cloud service before they are made available to CSCs in the production environment
				Q2-CCM-04.1B	Does the CSP use the defined criteria to approve any change to the cloud service before they are made available to CSCs in the production environment?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evidence of use the defined criteria to approve any change to the cloud service before they are made available to CSCs in the production environment - Audit records
CCM-05	PERFORMING AND LOGGING CHANGES	CCM-05.1B	The CSP shall define roles and rights according to IAM-01 for the authorised personnel or system components who are allowed to make changes to the cloud service in the production environment.	Q1-CCM-05.1B	Does the CSP define roles for the authorised personnel or system components who are allowed to make changes to the cloud service in the production environment?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented list of roles and the changes they are allowed to make and to which components

				Q2-CCM-05.1B	Does the CSP shall define rights for the defined roles according to IAM-01 for the authorised personnel or system components who are allowed to make changes to the cloud service in the production environment?	- Documented list of rights for each role
		CCM-05.2B	All changes to the cloud service in the production environment shall be logged and shall be traceable back to the individual or system component that initiated the change.	Q1-CCM-05.2B	Are all changes to the cloud service in the production environment logged to the individual or system component that initiated the change?	- Log record of the session of the individual or system component that initiated the change
				Q2-CCM-05.2B	Are all changes to the cloud service in the production environment traceable back to the individual or system component that initiated the change?	- Log record of the session of the individual or system component that initiated the change
CCM-06	VERSION CONTROL	CCM-06.1B	The CSP shall implement version control procedures to track the dependencies of individual changes and to be able to restore affected system components back to their previous state as a result of errors or identified vulnerabilities.	Q1-CCM-06.1B	Does the CSP document version control procedures to track the dependencies of individual changes?	- Documented version control procedures
				Q2-CCM-06.1B	Does the CSP implement version control procedures to track the dependencies of individual changes?	- Documented list of dependencies of individual changes - Version control management tool - Tool for the management of binaries
				Q3-CCM-06.1B	Are the CSP document version control procedures able to restore affected system components back to their previous state as a result of errors or identified vulnerabilities?	- Documented version control procedures

				Q4-CCM-06.1B	Does the CSP implement version control procedures that are able to restore affected system components back to their previous state as a result of errors or identified vulnerabilities?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - System tags - Version control tool
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13. Development of Information Systems

Table 27. Checklist for DEV basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

Control ID	Control	ReqID	Requirement	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
DEV-01	POLICIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT AND PROCUREMENT OF INFORMATION SYSTEMS	DEV-01.1B	The CSP shall define and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 with technical and organisational measures for the secure development of the cloud service.	Q1-DEV-01.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures according to security policies and procedures (ISP-02) with technical and organisational measures for the secure development of the cloud service?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented policies and procedures
				Q2-DEV-01.1B	Does the CSP communicate policies and procedures according to security policies and procedures (ISP-02) with technical and organisational measures for the secure development of the cloud service?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intranet/WEB - email - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
				Q3-DEV-01.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures according to security policies and procedures (ISP-02) with technical and organisational measures for the secure development of the cloud service?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Safe development guides for each programming language used - Safety requirements in the design phase - Security checkpoints incorporated into project

						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> milestones - Secure repositories - Security by design practices
		DEV-01.2B	The policies and procedures for secure development shall consider information security from the earliest phases of design.	Q1-DEV-01.2B	Do the policies for secure development consider information security from the earliest phases of design?	- Documented policies (encompasses information security from the earliest phases of design)
				Q2-DEV-01.2B	Do the procedures for secure development consider information security from the earliest phases of design?	- Documented procedures (encompass information security from the earliest phases of design)
DEV-02	DEVELOPMENT SUPPLY CHAIN SECURITY	DEV-02.1B	The CSP shall maintain a list of dependencies to hardware and software products used in the development of its cloud service.	Q1-DEV-02.1B	Does the CSP maintain a list of dependencies to hardware products used in the development of its cloud service?	- Documented list of dependencies to hardware products used in the development of its cloud service
				Q2-DEV-02.1B	Does the CSP maintain a list of dependencies to software products used in the development of its cloud service?	- Documented list of dependencies to software products used in the development of its cloud service
DEV-03	SECURE DEVELOPMENT ENVIRONMENT	DEV-03.1B	The CSP shall ensure that the confidentiality and integrity of the source code is adequately protected at all stages of development.	Q1-DEV-03.1B	Does the CSP ensure that the confidentiality of the source code is adequately protected at all stages of development?	- Source code protection policy (e.g., NDA, IPR, License)
				Q2-DEV-03.1B	Does the CSP ensure that the integrity of the source code is adequately protected at all stages of development?	- SAST and DAST results - security code checks
		DEV-03.2B	The CSP shall use version control to keep a history of the changes in source code with an attribution of changes to individual developers.	Q1-DEV-03.2B	Does the CSP use version control to keep a history of the changes in source code?	- Version control tool in use
				Q2-DEV-03.2B	Is it maintained an attribution of changes to individual developers?	- Version control tool - Change log records

DEV-04	SEPARATION OF ENVIRONMENTS	DEV-04.1B	The CSP shall ensure that production environments are physically or logically separated from development, test or pre-production environments.	Q1-DEV-04.1B	Does the CSP ensure that production environments are physically or logically separated from development environments?	- Documented environments description
				Q2-DEV-04.1B	Does the CSP ensure that production environments are physically or logically separated from test environments?	- Documented environments description
				Q3-DEV-04.1B	Does the CSP ensure that production environments are physically or logically separated from pre-production environments?	- Documented environments description
		DEV-04.2B	CSC data contained in the production environments shall not be used in development, test or pre-production environments in order not to compromise their confidentiality.	Q1-DEV-04.2B	Is CSC data contained in the production environments being prevented to be used in development, test or pre-production environments?	- Data set used in test and pre-production environments
DEV-05	DEVELOPMENT OF SECURITY FEATURES	DEV-05.1B	The CSP shall define and implement according to ISP-02 specific procedures for the development of security features that implement technical mechanisms or safeguards required by the EUCS, with increased testing requirements.	Q1-DEV-05.1B	Does the CSP define specific procedures for the development of functions that implement technical mechanisms or safeguards required by the EUCS scheme, with increased testing requirements?	- Documented specific procedures for the development of functions
				Q2-DEV-05.1	Does the CSP implement specific procedures for the development of functions that implement technical mechanisms or safeguards required by the EUCS scheme, with increased testing requirements?	- Technical mechanisms or safeguards required by the EUCS scheme, with increased testing requirements
DEV-06	IDENTIFICATION OF VULNERABILITIES OF THE CLOUD SERVICE	DEV-06.1B	The CSP shall apply appropriate measures to check the cloud service for vulnerabilities that may have been integrated into the cloud service during the development process.	Q1-DEV-06.1B	Does the CSP apply appropriate measures to check the cloud service for vulnerabilities that may have been integrated into the cloud service during the development process?	-Vulnerability assessments results (manual)

DEV-06		DEV-06.2B	The CSP shall apply appropriate measures to check the cloud service for vulnerabilities that may have been integrated into the cloud service during the development process.	Q1-DEV-06.2B	Are the procedures for identifying vulnerabilities integrated in the development process?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented procedures for identifying vulnerabilities - Documented development process - Development process audit records
DEV-07	OUTSOURCING OF THE DEVELOPMENT	DEV-07.1B	<p>When outsourcing development of the cloud service or components thereof to a contractor, the CSP and the contractor shall contractually agree on specifications regarding at least the following aspects:</p> <p>(1) Security in software development (requirements, design, implementation, tests and verifications) in accordance with published standards and established methods;</p> <p>(2) Acceptance testing of the quality of the services provided in accordance with the agreed functional and nonfunctional requirements; and</p> <p>(3) Providing evidence that sufficient verifications have been carried out to rule out the existence of known vulnerabilities.</p>	Q1-DEV-07.1B	When outsourcing development of the cloud service or components thereof to a contractor, do the CSP and the contractor contractually agree on specifications regarding at security in software development (requirements, design, implementation, tests and verifications) in accordance with recognised standards and methods?	- Contract signed by both parts
				Q2-DEV-07.1B	When outsourcing development of the cloud service or components thereof to a contractor, do the CSP and the contractor contractually agree on specifications regarding at acceptance testing of the quality of the services provided in accordance with the agreed functional and non-functional requirements?	- Contract signed by both parts
				Q3-DEV-07.1B	When outsourcing development of the cloud service or components thereof to a contractor, do the CSP and the contractor contractually agree on specifications regarding	- Contract reviewed and signed by both parts

					providing evidence that sufficient verifications have been carried out to rule out the existence of known vulnerabilities?
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14. Procurement Management

Table 28. Checklist for PM basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

Control ID	Control	ReqID	Requirement	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
PM-01	POLICIES AND PROCEDURES FOR CONTROLLING AND MONITORING THIRD PARTIES	PM-01.1B	The CSP shall define and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 for controlling and monitoring third-parties whose products or services contribute to the provision of the cloud service.	Q1-PM-01.1B	Is there a document describing the policy for controlling and monitoring third parties whose products or services contribute to the provision of the cloud service?	-Controlling and monitoring third parties whose products or services contribute to the provision of the cloud service policy document
PM-02	RISK ASSESSMENT OF SUPPLIERS	PM-02.1B	The CSP shall perform a risk assessment of its suppliers in accordance with the policies and procedures for the control and monitoring of third parties before they start contributing to the provision of the cloud service.	Q1-PM-02.1B	Does the CSP perform a risk assessment of its suppliers or the control and monitoring of third parties before they start contributing to the provision of the cloud service?	- Documented risk assessment
		PM-02.2B	Following the risk assessment of a subservice provider, the CSP shall define for every applicable EUCS requirement a list of Complementary Subservice Organization Controls (CSOC) to be implemented by the subservice provider.	Q1-PM-02.2B	Following the risk assessment of a subservice provider, does the CSP define a list of Complementary Subservice Organization Controls (CSOC) to be implemented by the subservice provider?	- Documented list of Complementary Subservice Organization Controls
		PM-02.3B	The CSP shall ensure that the subservice provider has implemented the CSOCs, and that the subservice provider has made available to the CSP assurance information supporting the assessment of their suitability for the targeted evaluation level.	Q1-PM-02.3B	Does the CSP ensure that the subservice provider has implemented the CSOCs?	- Subservice provider CSOC documented implementation results review - Audit report to the Subservice provider

		PM-02.4B	The adequacy of the risk assessment and of the definition of CSOCs shall be reviewed regularly, at least annually.	Q1-PM-02.4B	Is the adequacy of the risk assessment reviewed regularly?	- Documented risk assessment review records (2/3 years)
PM-03	DIRECTORY OF SUPPLIERS	PM-03.1B	The CSP shall maintain a directory for controlling and monitoring the suppliers who contribute to the delivery of the cloud service.	Q1-PM-03.1B	Does the CSP maintain a directory for controlling and monitoring the suppliers who contribute to the delivery of the cloud service?	- Centralised directory of suppliers
		PM-03.2B	The CSP shall verify the directory for completeness, accuracy and validity at least annually.	Q1-PM-03.2B	Do the CSP shall verify the directory for completeness, accuracy and validity?	- Directory audit report
PM-04	MONITORING OF COMPLIANCE WITH REQUIREMENTS	PM-04.1B	The CSP shall monitor the compliance of its suppliers with information security requirements and applicable legal and regulatory requirements in accordance with policies and procedures concerning controlling and monitoring of third-parties.	Q1-PM-04.1B	Does the CSP monitor the compliance of its suppliers with information security requirements in accordance with policies and procedures concerning controlling and monitoring of third-parties?	- Documented compliance report of the monitoring
				Q2-PM-04.1B	Does the CSP monitor the compliance of its suppliers with applicable legal and regulatory requirements in accordance with policies and procedures concerning controlling and monitoring of third-parties?	- Documented compliance report of the monitoring
		PM-04.2B	The CSP shall monitor the compliance of its subservice providers with the CSOCs applicable to them following the risk assessment (cf. PM-02).	Q1-PM-04.2B	Does the CSP monitor the compliance of its subservice providers with the CSOCs applicable to them following the risk assessment?	- Documented compliance report of the monitoring
		PM-04.3B	The frequency of the monitoring shall correspond to the classification of the third party based on the risk assessment conducted by the CSP (cf. PM-02), and the results of the monitoring shall be considered in the review of the third party's risk assessment.	Q1-PM-04.3B	Does the frequency of the monitoring correspond to the classification of the third party based on the risk assessment conducted by the Cloud Service Provider?	- Documented compliance report of the monitoring version control and change history

				Q2-PM-04.2b	Are the results of the monitoring included in the review of the third party's risk assessment?	- Documented review of the third party's risk assessment
		PM-04.4B	Identified violations and deviations shall be analysed, evaluated and treated in accordance with the risk management procedure (cf. RM-01).	Q1-PM-04.4B	Are Identified violations and deviations analysed, in accordance with the risk management procedure?	- Documented review of the Identified violations and deviations management
				Q2-PM-04.4B	Are Identified violations and deviations evaluated in accordance with the risk management procedure?	- Documented review of the Identified violations and deviations management
				Q3-PM-04.4B	Are Identified violations and deviations treated in accordance with the risk management procedure?	- Documented review of the Identified violations and deviations management
		PM-04.5B	When a change in a third-party contributing to the provision of the cloud service affects its level of security, the CSP shall inform all of its CSCs without undue delay.	Q1-PM-04.5B	Does the CSP shall inform all of its CSCs without undue delay when a change in a third-party contributes to the delivery of the cloud service affects its level of security?	- Intranet/WEB - email - Etc.
PM-05	EXIT STRATEGY	PM-05.1B	The CSP shall define exit strategies for the purchase of products or services where the risk assessment of the suppliers identified a very high dependency.	Q1-.PM-05.1B	Does the CSP define exit strategies for the purchase of services where the risk assessment of the suppliers identified a very high dependency?	- Documented exit strategies for the purchase of services

15. Incident Management

Table 29. Checklist for IM basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

Control ID	Control	ReqID	Requirement	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
IM-01	POLICY FOR SECURITY	IM-01.1B	The CSP shall define and implement policies and procedures according to ISP-02 containing technical and organisational safeguards to	Q1-IM-01.1B	Are all known security incidents documented?	- Documented security incidents - Guidelines for the

	INCIDENT MANAGEMENT		ensure a fast, effective and proper response to all known security incidents, including: (1) Guidelines for the classification, prioritization, and escalation of security incidents; (2) Description of interfaces for incident management and business continuity management.			classification, prioritization, and escalation of security incidents; - Description of interfaces for incident management and business continuity management. - Security incidents communicated (a sample)
				Q2-IM-01.1B	Does the CSP document policies and procedures containing technical and organisational safeguards to ensure a response to all known security incidents?	- Documented policies and procedures about security incidents management
				Q3-IM-01.1B	Does the documented technical and organisational safeguards ensure a fast, effective and proper response to all know security incidents?	- Technical and organisational safeguards assessment result
				Q4-IM-01.1B	Are the previous policies and procedures aligned with the ISP-02 policy (Global Security Policy) and do they include: • Guidelines for the classification, prioritization, and escalation of security incidents; • Description of interfaces for incident management and business continuity management?	- Cross References between Global Security Policy and Security Incident management Policy
		IM-01.2B	The CSP shall establish a point of contact, which contributes to the coordinated resolution of security incidents.	Q5-IM-01.1B	Are the previous policies and procedures implemented?	- Example of policy/procedures implementation randomly sampled
IM-02	PROCESSING OF SECURITY INCIDENTS	IM-02.1B	The CSP shall classify and prioritize security events that could constitute a security incident, and perform root-cause analyses for these events, using their subject matter experts and external security providers where appropriate.	Q1-IM-02.1B	For the events that could constitute a security incident, does the CSP perform root-cause analysis?	- Security Incidents database - Root-Cause Analysis result document -Root-cause analysis

IM-03	DOCUMENTATION AND REPORTING OF SECURITY INCIDENTS	IM-03.1B	The CSP shall document the implemented measures after a security incident has been processed and, in accordance with contractual agreements between CSC and CSP, information shall be made available to the affected CSCs for final acknowledgment or, if applicable, as confirmation.	Q1-IM-03.1B	Does the CSP document the implemented measures after a security incident has been processed and, in accordance with contractual agreements between CSC and CSP?	- Documented measures derived from the root-cause analysis
				Q2-IM-03.1B	Is the information made available to the affected CSCs for final acknowledgment or, if applicable, as confirmation?	- Security Incident newsletter/document for the customers
		IM-03.2B	The CSP shall make information on security incidents or confirmed security breaches available to all affected CSCs.	Q1-IM-03.2B	Does the CSP make information on security incidents or confirmed security breaches available to all affected customers?	Information mechanism used - WEB - email - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
				Q2-IM-03.2B	Does the CSP send information of security incidents to all the documented affected customers?	- Security Incident Newsletter for each affected customer
IM-04	USER'S DUTY TO REPORT SECURITY INCIDENTS	IM-04.1B	The CSP shall inform employees and external business partners of their contractual obligations to report all security events that become known to them and are directly related to the cloud service.	Q1-IM-04.1B	Does the CSP inform employees of their contractual obligations to report all security events that become known to them and are directly related to the cloud service?	Information mechanism used -Intranet/WEB -email - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
				Q2-IM-04.1B	Does the CSP inform external business partners of their contractual obligations to report all security events that become known to them and are directly related to the cloud service?	Information mechanism used -Intranet/WEB -email - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		IM-04.2B	The CSP shall not take any negative action against those who report in good faith events that do not subsequently turn out to be incidents and shall make that policy known as	Q1-IM-04.2B	Does the security incident management policy contain an explicit mention that the CSP not take any negative action against	- Security incident management policy

			part of its communication to employees and external business partners.		those who communicate "false reports" of events that do not subsequently turn out to be incidents?	
				Q2-IM-04.2B	Is the previous policy communicated to employees?	Information mechanism used -Intranet/WEB -email - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
				Q3-IM-04.2B	Is the previous policy communicated to external business partners?	Information mechanism used -Intranet/WEB -email - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
		IM-04.3B	The CSP shall define, publish and implement a single point of contact to report security events and vulnerabilities.	Q1-IM-04.3B	Has the CSP established a single point of contact to report security events?	Documented Role and Responsibilities related to the Security Incidents Manager/Collector
				Q2-IM-04.3B	Is the single point of contact made public?	Information mechanism used -Intranet/WEB -email - Wallchart - Specific meetings minutes - Etc.
				Q3-IM-04.3B	Is the single point of contact operative?	- List of security incident received and managed by the single point of contact
IM-05	INVOLVEMENT OF CLOUD CUSTOMERS IN THE EVENT OF INCIDENTS	IM-05.1B	The CSP shall periodically inform its CSCs on the status of the security incidents affecting the CSC, or, where appropriate and necessary, involve them in the resolution, according to the contractual agreements	Q1-IM-05.1B	Does the CSP periodically inform its CSCs on the status of the incidents affecting the CSC?	- Security Incident Newsletter / periodic communication to customers

				Q2-IM-05.1B	Where appropriate and necessary, does the CSP involve customers in the incidents' resolution according to the contractual agreements?	- Requests of participations in incidents analysis - Contractual Agreements
		IM-05.2B	As soon as a security incident has been closed, the CSP shall inform the affected CSCs about the actions taken, according to the contractual agreements.	Q1-IM-05.2B	As soon as an incident has been closed, does the CSP inform the customers about the actions taken, according to the contractual agreements?	- Security Incident Newsletter - Contractual Agreements
IM-06	EVALUATION AND LEARNING PROCESS	IM-06.1B	The CSP shall perform an analysis of security incidents to identify recurrent or significant security events or incidents and to identify the need for further protection, if needed with the support of external bodies.	Q1-IM-06.1B	Does the CSP perform a security incidents analysis to identify recurrent and/or significant incidents?	- Security Incident Data Base with the classification of recurrent and significant incidents
				Q2-IM-06.1B	In case of recurrent or significant incidents detected, does the CSP identify need for further protection?	- Documented further protection associated to recurrent and significant incidents
				Q3-IM-06.1	Does the CSP involve external bodies if necessary?	- Contracts with external bodies
		IM-06.2B	If the CSP determines the need for external assistance, it shall select a competent and trustworthy incident response service provider or one that is recommended by its NCCA.	Q1-IM-06.2B	If the CSP determines the need for external assistance, is selected a competent and trustworthy incident response service provider or one that is recommended by its NCCA?	- Qualifications of the contracted external bodies
IM-07	INCIDENT EVIDENCE PRESERVATION	IM-07.1B	The CSP shall document and implement a procedure to archive all documents and evidence that provide details on security incidents.	Q1-IM-07.1B	Does the CSP document a procedure to archive all documents and evidence that provide details on security incidents?	- Documented procedure to archive security incidents
				Q2-IM-07.1B	Is the previous documented procedure implemented?	- Example of security incidents documentation randomly selected

		IM-07.2B	The CSP shall implement security mechanisms and processes for protecting all the information related to security incidents in accordance with criticality levels and legal requirements in effect.	Q1-IM-07.2B	Does the CSP implement security mechanisms and processes for protecting all the information related to security incidents?	- Example of security mechanisms and processes for protecting all the information related to security incidents randomly sampled
				Q2-IM-07.2B	Are the implemented security mechanism and processes in accordance with criticality levels and legal requirements in effect	- Audit records

16. Business Continuity

Table 30. Checklist for BC basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

Control ID	Control	ReqID	Requirement	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
BC-01	BUSINESS CONTINUITY POLICIES AND TOP MANAGEMENT RESPONSIBILITY	BC-01.1B	The CSP shall define policies and procedures according to ISP-02 establishing the strategy and guidelines to ensure business continuity and contingency management.	Q1-BC-01.1B	Has the CSP documented policies and procedures to ensure business continuity and contingency according to ISP-02?	- Documented policies and procedures related to business continuity and contingency
				Q2-BC-01.1B	Does the documented policies and procedures establish the strategy and guidelines to ensure business continuity and contingency?	- Documented policies and procedures related to business continuity and contingency (encompass the strategy and guidelines to ensure business continuity and contingency)
BC-02	BUSINESS IMPACT ANALYSIS PROCEDURES	BC-02.1B	The policies and procedures for business continuity and contingency management shall include the need to perform a business impact analysis to determine the impact of any malfunction to the cloud service or enterprise.	Q1-BC-02.1B	Does the CSP document all the possible malfunction to the cloud service or enterprise?	- Documented list of all the possible malfunction to the cloud service or enterprise

				Q2-BC-02.1B	Does the business continuity and contingency management policies and procedure contain the need to perform a business impact analysis related to all the documented malfunctions?	- Business continuity and contingency management policies and procedures (encompass the need to perform a business impact analysis related to all the documented malfunctions)
BC-03	BUSINESS CONTINUITY AND CONTINGENCY PLANNING	BC-03.1B	The CSP shall document and implement a business continuity plan and contingency plans to ensure continuity of the services, taking into account information security constraints and the results of the business impact analysis.	Q1-BC-03.1B	Does the CSP document a business continuity plan?	- Business Continuity Plan
				Q2-BC-03.1B	Does the CSP document a contingency plan to ensure continuity of the services?	- Contingency Plan
				Q3-BC-03.1B	Does the documented business continuity plan consider information security constraints and the results of the business impact analysis?	- Business Continuity Plan (encompasses information security constraints and the results of the business impact analysis) - Business Continuity Plan review
				Q4-BC-03.1B	Does the documented contingency plan consider information security constraints and the results of the business impact analysis?	- Contingency Plan (encompasses information security constraints and the results of the business impact analysis) - Contingency Plan Review
				Q5-BC-03.1B	Does the CSP implement the business continuity plan?	- According with the business continuity plan requirements, execution evidence randomly selected
				Q6-BC-03.1B	Does the CSP implement the contingency plan?	- According with the contingency plan requirements, execution evidence randomly selected

17. Compliance

Table 31. Checklist for CO basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

Control ID	Control	ReqID	Requirement	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
CO-01	IDENTIFICATION OF APPLICABLE COMPLIANCE REQUIREMENTS	CO-01.1B	The CSP shall document the legal, regulatory, self-imposed and contractual requirements relevant to the information security of the cloud service.	Q1-CO-01.1B	Does the CSP document the legal requirements relevant to the information security of the cloud service?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented list of requirements (encompasses the legal requirements relevant to the information security of the cloud service) - Documented review of the list of requirements
				Q2-CO-01.1B	Does the CSP document the regulatory requirements relevant to the information security of the cloud service?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented list of requirements (the regulatory requirements relevant to the information security of the cloud service) - Documented review of the list of requirements
				Q3-CO-01.1B	Does the CSP document the self-imposed requirements relevant to the information security of the cloud service?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented list of requirements (encompasses the self-imposed requirements relevant to the information security of the cloud service) - Documented review of the list of requirements
				Q4-CO-01.1B	Does the CSP shall document the contractual requirements relevant to the information security of the cloud service?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documented list of requirements (encompasses the contractual requirements relevant to the information security of the cloud service) - Documented review of the list of requirements

CO-02	POLICY FOR PLANNING AND CONDUCTING AUDITS	CO-02.1B	The CSP shall define and implement policies and procedures for planning and conducting audits, made in accordance with ISP-02 and that would not interfere with the operation of the cloud service.	Q1-CO-02.1B	Does the CSP define policies and procedures for planning and conducting audits?	- Audit policy document - Audit planning and conducting procedures
				Q2-CO-02.1B	Does the CSP implement policies and procedures for planning and conducting audits?	- Audit plan - Audit report - Documented list of nonconformities
CO-03	INTERNAL AUDITS OF THE INTERNAL CONTROL SYSTEM	CO-03.1B	The CSP shall perform at regular intervals and at least annually internal audits by subject matter experts to check the compliance of their internal security control system to the requirements defined in CO-01, and to the requirements of the EUCS scheme at the targeted evaluation level.	Q1-CO-03.1B	Does the CSP perform audits to check the compliance of their internal security control system to the requirements defined?	- Audit plan - Audit report - Documented list of nonconformities
				Q2-CO-03.1B	Are the internal audits performed by subject matter experts?	- Internal auditor's training records
				Q3-CO-03.1B	Are the internal audits performed at least annually?	- Documented audit plan
				Q4-CO-03.1B	Does the internal audit check the compliance to the requirements defined in CO1 and to the requirements of the EUCS scheme at the targeted evaluation level?	- Internal audit reports and/or checklist aligned with EUCS scheme at the targeted evaluation level
		CO-03.2B	The CSP shall document specifically deviations that are nonconformities from the EUCS requirements, including an assessment of their severity, and keep track of their remediation.	Q1-CO-03.2B	Does the CSP document specifically deviations that are nonconformities from the EUCS requirements?	- Audit report - Documented list of deviations that are nonconformities from the EUCS requirements
				Q2-CO-03.2B	Do the documented deviations include an assessment of their severity?	- Documented list of deviations including an assessment of their severity
				Q3-CO-03.2B	Does the CSP keep track of their remediation?	- Monitoring report of the non-conformities from the EUCS requirements remediation

CO-04	INFORMATION ON INTERNAL CONTROL SYSTEM ASSESSMENT	CO-04.1B	The CSP shall regular inform its top management about the information security performance within the scope of the internal control system.	Q1-CO-04.1B	Does the CSP regular inform its top management about the information security performance within the scope of the internal control system?	- Information security performance report to top management - email - Another specific document
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18. User documentation

Table 32. Checklist for DOC basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

Control ID	Control	ReqID	Requirement	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
DOC-01	GUIDELINES AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR CLOUD CUSTOMERS	DOC-01.1B	The CSP shall make publicly available guidelines and recommendations to assist the cloud service users with the secure configuration, installation, deployment, operation and maintenance of the cloud service provided.	Q1-DOC-01.1B	Does the CSP make publicly available guidelines and recommendations to assist the Cloud Service Users?	- Guidelines - Distribution mechanism: - Information management system - Intranet/WEB - Etc.
		DOC-01.2B	The CSP shall maintain guidelines and recommendations applicable to the cloud service in the version intended for productive use.	Q1-DOC-01.2B	Does the CSP maintain guidelines and recommendations applicable to the cloud service in the version intended for productive use?	- Guidelines and recommendations version control and change history
DOC-02	ONLINE REGISTER OF KNOWN VULNERABILITIES	DOC-02.1B	The CSP shall provide comprehensible and transparent information on: (1) Its jurisdiction; and (2) System component locations, including its subservice providers, where CSC data is processed, stored and backed up.	Q1-DOC-02.1B	Does the CSP operate or refer to a publicly available online register of known vulnerabilities that affect the provided cloud service?	- Online register of known vulnerabilities (Web, e-mail)
				Q2-DOC-02.1B	Is the online register of known vulnerabilities daily updated?	- Web page updated date - e-mail sent date

		DOC-02.2B	The CSP shall provide sufficient information for subject matter experts of the CSC to determine and to assess the suitability of the cloud service's jurisdiction and locations from a legal and regulatory perspective.	Q1-DOC-02.2B	Does the CSP provide sufficient information for subject matter experts of the CSC to determine and to assess the suitability of the cloud service's jurisdiction and locations from a legal and regulatory perspective?	
DOC-03	LOCATIONS OF DATA PROCESSING AND STORAGE	DOC-03.1B	The CSP shall provide a justification for the evaluation level targeted for certification, based on the risks associated to the cloud service's targeted customers and use cases.	Q1-DOC-03.1B	Does the CSP provide comprehensible and transparent information on its jurisdiction?	-Contractual agreement: it indicates the location and the jurisdiction, explicitly - Web - Service catalogue - e-mail
				Q2-DOC-03.1B	Does the CSP provide comprehensible and transparent information on system component locations?	- Web - Service catalogue - e-mail -Contractual agreement: it indicates the location and the jurisdiction, explicitly
				Q3-DOC-03.1B	Does the CSP provide comprehensible and transparent information on its subcontractors?	-Web - Service catalogue - e-mail -Contractual agreement: it indicates the location and the jurisdiction, explicitly
				Q4-DOC-03.1B	Does the CSP provide comprehensible and transparent information on where the cloud customer's data is processed, stored and backed up?	-Web - Service catalogue - e-mail -Contractual agreement: it indicates the location and the jurisdiction, explicitly

				Q5-DOC-03.1B	Does the CSP provide comprehensible and transparent information about the on where the cloud customer's data is processed, stored and backed up?	Service Catalogue Other internal Documentation -Contractual agreement: it shall indicate where the data is processed, stored and backed up
		DOC-03.2B	If the CSP claims compliance to extension profiles for its cloud service, the justification shall cover these extension profiles.	Q1-DOC-03.2B	Does the CSP provide sufficient information for subject matter experts of the CSC to determine to assess the suitability of the cloud service's jurisdiction and locations from a legal and regulatory perspective?	Service Catalogue Other internal Documentation -Contractual agreement: it shall indicate where the data is processed, stored and backed up
		DOC-03.3B	A summary of the justification shall be made publicly available as part of the certification package, which shall allow CSCs to perform a high-level analysis about their own use cases.	Q1- DOC-03.3B	Is there a summary of the justification made publicly available as part of the certification package?	- Public repository with the summary of the justification
DOC-04	JUSTIFICATION OF THE TARGETED ASSURANCE LEVEL	DOC-04.1B	If a CSP wants to allow CSCs to certify with EUCS their own cloud services based on the CSP's cloud service using composition, the CSP shall develop specific documentation and make it available to CSCs upon request, based on the complementary user entity controls (CUECs) that they have defined.	Q1-DOC-04.1B	If a CSP wants to allow CSCs to certify with EUCS their own services based on the CSP's cloud service using composition, does the CSP develop specific documentation based on the Complementary User Customer Controls (CUECs) that they have defined?	- Documented specific documentation
				Q2-DOC-04.1B	Does the CSP make documentation available to CSCs upon request?	- Requests for specific documentation by the CSC - Records showing that the documentation has been sent to the CSC.
		DOC-04.2B	The CSP shall include in the description provided for each CUEC a list of actionable requirements for the CSC, and it shall associate each CUEC to an EUCS requirement.	Q1-DOC-04.2B	Does the CSP include in the description provided for each CUEC a list of actionable requirements for the CSC?	- Documented list of actionable requirements

				Q2-DOC-04.2B	- Each CCC is associated with an EUCS requirement.	- Traceability between each CCC to an EUCS requirement
DOC-05	GUIDELINES AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR COMPOSITION	DOC-05.1B	If a CSP wants to allow CSCs to certify with EUCS their own services based on the CSP's cloud service using composition, it shall document for each EUCS requirement how its cloud service will contribute (if any) to the fulfilment of this requirement by the cloud service developed by the CSC using the CSP as subservice provider.	Q1-DOC-05.1B	If a CSP wants to allow CSCs to certify with EUCS their own services based on the CSP's cloud service using composition, it documents for each EUCS requirement how its cloud service will contribute (if any) to the fulfilment of the requirement by the cloud service developed by the CSC using the CSP as subservice provider.	- Documentation for each EUCS requirement on how its cloud service (if any) will contribute to the fulfilment of the requirement through the cloud service developed by the CSC using the CSP as a subservice organization.
		DOC-05.2B	The CSP shall make this documentation available to CSCs upon request.	Q1-DOC-05.2B	Does the CSP make this documentation available to CSCs upon request?	- CSS documentation request - Record of submission of the required documentation - e-mail - other

19. Dealing with Investigation Requests from Government Agencies

Table 33. Checklist for INQ basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

Control ID	Control	ReqID	Requirement	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
INQ-01	LEGAL ASSESSMENT OF INVESTIGATIVE INQUIRIES	INQ-01.1B	The CSP shall subject investigation requests from government agencies to a legal assessment by subject matter experts.	Q1-INQ-01.1B	Does the CSP execute a legal assessment of every investigation request received from government agencies?	- Legal assessment results
				Q2-INQ-01.1B	Is the assessor and expert of the subject matter?	- Assessor documented qualifications
		INQ-01.2B	The legal assessment shall determine whether the government agency has an applicable and legally valid basis and what further steps need to be taken.	Q1-INQ-01.2B	Does the government agency that sent the request has an applicable and legally valid basis?	

				Q2-INQ-01.2B	Does the legal assessment results contain the further steps need to be taken in response of the investigation request received?	- Legal assessment results (contain the further steps need to be taken in response of the investigation request received)
INQ-02	INFORMING CLOUD CUSTOMERS ABOUT INVESTIGATION REQUESTS	INQ-02.1B	The CSP shall inform the affected CSC(s) about investigation requests without undue delay unless the applicable legal basis on which the government agency is based prohibits this or there are clear indications of illegal actions in connection with the use of the cloud service.	Q1-INQ-02.1B	Does the CSP inform without undue delay the affected CSC(s) about the received investigation requests?	- Documented notice sent to every CSC affected by the investigation request. This document must include the delivery date
				Q2-INQ-02.1B	In case CSP did not inform the affected CSC(s) was because the applicable legal basis on which the government agency is based prohibits this or because there are clear indications of illegal actions in connection with the use of the cloud service?	- Investigation Request + Legal Assessment Results
INQ-03	CONDITIONS FOR ACCESS TO OR DISCLOSURE OF DATA IN INVESTIGATION REQUESTS	INQ-03.1B	The CSP shall only provide access to or disclose CSC data in the context of government investigation requests after the CSP's legal assessment (cf. INQ-01) has shown that an applicable and valid legal basis exists, and that the investigation request must be granted on that basis.	Q1-INQ-03.1B	Has the CSP provided access to or disclose CSC data to government agency only after the legal assessment has shown that an applicable and valid legal basis exists?	- Record of the data in which CSP has provided access to customer data to the government agency - Assessment Results
		INQ-03.2B	The CSP shall document and implement procedures to ensure that government agencies only have access to the data they need to investigate.	Q1-INQ-03.2B	Does the CSP document procedures to ensure that government agencies only have access to the data they need to investigate?	- Documented procedure that describe the mechanism to provide access to customer data to government agency by limiting the scope to only that data they need to investigate according to the investigation request
				Q2-INQ-03.2B	Does the CSP implement the documented procedures to ensure that government agencies only have	- Examples of Investigation Requests+Data needed for the investigation+evidence that the

					access to the data they need to investigate?	access has been authorized ONLY to that data
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20. Product Safety and security

Table 34. Checklist for PSS basic assurance requirements (source: MEDINA's own contribution)

Control ID	Control	ReqID	Requirement	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Evidence
PSS-01	ERROR HANDLING AND LOGGING MECHANISMS	PSS-01.1B	The CSP shall offer to their CSCs error handling and logging mechanisms that allow them to obtain security-related information about the status of the cloud service as well as the data, services or functions it provides.	Q1-PSS-01.1B	Does the CSP offer to their CSCs error handling mechanisms?	- Error handling mechanism instantiated to every customer
				Q2-PSS-01.1B	Does error handling mechanisms allow customers to obtain security-related information about the security status of the cloud service as well as the data, services or functions it provides?	- Operation manual of the error handling mechanism
				Q3-PSS-01.1B	Does the CSP offer to their CSCs logging mechanisms?	- Logging mechanism instantiated to every customer
				Q4-PSS-01.1B	Does logging mechanisms allow customers to obtain security-related information about the security status of the cloud service as well as the data, services or functions it provides?	- Operation manual of the logging mechanism
PSS-02	SESSION MANAGEMENT	PSS-02.1B	A state-of-the-art session management system shall be used that is suitably protected against known attacks.	Q1-PSS-02.1B	Is a state-of-the-art session management system used? Is it protected against known attacks?	- Session management system description (functional)
PSS-03	SOFTWARE DEFINED NETWORKING	PSS-03.1B	The CSP shall document and implement procedures to ensure the confidentiality of CSC data when offering functions for software-defined networking (SDN).	Q1-PSS-03.1B	Does the CSP document procedures to ensure the confidentiality of CSC data when offering functions for	- Documented procedures

					software-defined networking (SDN).?	
				Q2-PSS-03.1B	Does the CSP implement the procedures to ensure the confidentiality of CSC data when offering functions for software-defined networking (SDN).?	- Audit
		PSS-03.2B	The CSP shall validate the functionality of the SDN functions before providing new SDN features to CSCs or modifying existing SDN features.	Q1-PSS-03.2B	Does the CSP validate the functionality of the SDN functions before providing new SDN features to CSCs?	- Validation Report
PSS-04	IMAGES FOR VIRTUAL MACHINES AND CONTAINERS	PSS-04.1B	The CSP shall ensure the following aspects if CSCs operate virtual machines or containers with the cloud service: The CSP can restrict the selection of images of virtual machines or containers, so that users of this CSC can only launch the images or containers released according to these restrictions. Images made available by the CSP to the CSC are labelled with information about their origin (CSP or third-party) and about their security, and those provided by the CSP are hardened according to generally accepted industry standards.	Q1-PSS-04.1B	When the CSC operates virtual machine, does the CSP ensure that the CSC can restrict the selection of images of virtual machines according to its specifications?	-Authorization authentication procedures to access containers and the registry where they are stored
				Q2-PSS-04.1B	When the CSC operates container, does the CSP ensure that the CSC can restrict the selection of images of containers according to its specifications?	-Authorization authentication procedures to access containers and the registry where they are stored
				Q3-PSS-04.1B	Are the mages made available by the CSP to the CSC labelled with information about their origin (CSP or third-party)?	- Images origin information

				Q3-PSS-04.1B	Are the images provided by the CSP hardened according to generally accepted industry standards?	
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